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User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage.

D2.4 Heritage living labs context and requirements report and KPIs

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the outcomes obtained in the activities performed for Task 2.4 and Task 2.5.

The deliverable D2.4 analyses the context and the requirements of the project demonstration sites with the aim of establishing the baseline for the comparison of a before and after implementation of the renovation solutions. The study included an evaluation of geographic location, climate conditions and its situation with respect to the building location and its surroundings. The characteristics of the demonstration buildings was analysed where aspects such as construction materials, structural aspects, building components, interior distribution, orientation were considered. In a second part of the study, a subjective evaluation provided insights on the perception of the users of the interior environment in the demonstration sites, their impressions about the quality of the interior environment were collected, as well as in regard to the historic significance of the building architecture and historic features for them. The final section of the deliverable presents the KPIs that were determined with the collaboration of the all the project partners, in which four categories of KPIs were defined.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

HL	Heritage Labs
HLL	Heritage Living Labs
FSMLR	Fundacion Santa Maria la Real
PSMLR	Posada Santa Maria la Real
KP-IBS	Korposatsioon Vironia, Institute of Baltic Studies
FEUB	Faculty of Engineering, University of Bologna
DHW	Domestic heat water

1. Planned criteria

This report will gather all the information from the project demo sites to establish the baseline for evaluation of Herit4ages solutions. This will be based on evaluation of available data such as construction information, bills, systems, occupancy survey, study of the legal context, protection grade, history of the building, etc. Each demo site will be studied and surveys with the users/ owners will be conducted to identify main problems and targets to address with the renovation start the co-creation design of the strategy and tailoring of the solutions (in WP3). Examining the context and requirements of demonstration sites as accessible places and buildings, determining the needs, objectives, and next steps of the research work for each site - study and audit visits.

2. Herit4ages Demonstration sites

The situation of the demonstration sites is described in the following chapters, 2-demonstration sites, 3-the demonstration buildings, 4-the selected room for the implementation of the Herit4ages solutions, 5-the subjective survey, 6-accessibility analysis, 7-definition of the KPIs, 8-Conclusions. The demonstration sites are located in Palencia, Spain (ES); Bologna, Italia (IT); Tartu, Estonia (EE); and Funchal, in Portugal (PT), and are described as follows.

2.1 General Context

2.1.1 Geographic location

The Herit4ages project intends to address the challenges to adapt historic buildings to new uses, and the use of equipment to improve the interior environment, as well as the energy performance. The goal is to ensure that historic buildings provide energy conditions and performance similar to those of new buildings, offering good comfort and a healthy environment for users, while remaining affordable. The design criteria for the renovation solution in the Herit4ages project include strategies to adapt the buildings to new contexts, such as reversible and low-disruption solutions, as well as considerations for the intervention processes involved in the renovation. Digital solutions are also part of the strategy to assess the performance of the buildings according to dynamic conditions such as changing weather conditions or the occupant's decisions regarding comfort or aesthetic preferences. The renovation solutions are validated in five different locations in Europe considering four climate conditions according to the Köppen climate classification [1]. The list is shown according to the geographical location in Table 1 and illustrated in Figure 1.

TABLE 1 DEMONSTRATION SITES GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION DETAILS

Location	Project's ID	Type	Building Typology	Geographical Coordinates	Elevation
Tartu, EE	EE-KV	HLL	Office, working open space.	58° 23'N, 26° 43'W	39
Canduela, Palencia, ES	ES-RHC	HL	Religious space	42° 1'N, 4°32' 0'W	910
Santa María la Real, Palencia ES	ES-PSMR	HLL	Accommodation, hotel		
Bologna, IT	IT-FEUB	HLL	Educational, classroom	44° 29'N, 11° 20'W	54
Funchal, PT	PT-SM25	HLL	Residential building (apartment).	32° 39'N, 16° 55'W	550

2.1.2 Köppen climate classification

A summary of the weather conditions at the Herit4ages demo-sites, based on the Köppen classification, is provided here, while a detailed description can be found in D2.1. The five demo sites are distributed in three regions in Europe: The Baltic zone (Estonia), the mediterranean (Spain and Italy), while one demo site is found bordered by the Atlantic Ocean. According to Köppen, this would correspond to, one demo site in a Temperate oceanic climate or Cfb (Tartu, Estonia), two demo sites in a Temperate mediterranean climate or Csb (Palencia, Spain), one demo site in a Humid subtropical climate or Cfa (Bologna, Italy), and the last one in a Temperate continental climate namely Dfb (Funchal, Portugal).

Demonstration site	Climate Köppen classification
1 Tartu, EE	Cfb
2 Canduela, Palencia, ES	Csb
3 Santa María la Real, Palencia, ES	Csb
4 Bologna, IT	Cfa
5 Funchal, PT	Dfb

- Cold semi-arid climate (BSk)
- Warm mediterranean climate (Csa)
- Temperate mediterranean climate (Csb)
- Warm oceanic climate/ Humid subtropical climate (Cfa)
- Temperate oceanic climate (Cfb)
- Cool oceanic climate (Cfc)
- Warm continental climate/ Humid continental climate (Dfa)
- Temperate continental climate/ Humid continental climate (Dfb)
- Cool continental climate/ Subarctic climate (Dfc)
- Warm continental climate/ Mediterranean continental climate (Dsa)
- Temperate continental climate/ Mediterranean continental climate (Dsb)
- Cool continental climate (Dsc)
- Tundra climate (ET)
- Ice cap climate (EF)

FIGURE 1 DEMONSTRATION SITES KÖPPEN CLASSIFICATION ACCORDING TO GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION.

A Cfb climate corresponding to the demo site in Tartu, Estonia, is known as oceanic or marine climate, or the humid temperate climate sub-type, typical of west coasts in higher middle latitudes. Cfb is characterized by cool summers and mild winters, the temperature is generally cool and varies in a very limited range, showing few extreme temperatures. These locations are frequently cloudy as rain happens frequently in the year,

while snow fall is normal at least once a year, extreme weather is rare. Indeed, from the four demo site locations, Tartu is the one receiving the highest rate of precipitation in a year (630 mm), therefore, is the one with the lowest number of sunshine days per year (only 114). The map indicating the demonstration sites corresponding classification is shown in Figure 2.

The coldest temperature in Cfb regions is frequently below zero, in Tartu is -4°C average, while the warmest temperature is 18°C , since summertime in this type of weather is warm but not hot, usually below 22°C . The Temperate mediterranean climate (Csb), is typical of latitudes between 30° and 45° , with moderate temperatures and hot/dry conditions in summer, warm but not hot. The coldest temperature in Palencia, Spain, the zone where the demo site is located is slightly above zero (4°C), while the warmest is above 20°C , in accordance with the characteristics of this type of climate, warm but not hot. The Cfa climate (humid subtropical), is characterized by humid and hot summers, the lowest temperature in Bologna, Italy is -5°C , showing long and warm summers above 22°C .

FIGURE 2 DEMONSTRATION SITES' KÖPPEN CLIMATE CLASSIFICATION.

The winter temperatures do not allow long permanence of snow in these locations, while in some regions there is an extreme contrast between summer and winter, as in Bologna, the warmest temperature in summer is 36°C , compared to the average in winter below 5°C . There are varying rainfall cycles in summertime while in winter large storms can be observed. The Dfb climate (warm-summer humid continental) in Funchal, Portugal, is a climate region characterized by four seasons and an extensive variation of temperatures, warm to hot and humid summer and cold, freezing and in severe cold winters sometimes. This climate can have dry seasons, while rainfall occurs across the year. The average temperature in the warmest months is usually below 22°C , while the highest can be between 22°C and 28°C , while the coldest months can be below zero degrees. The demo site in Bologna would be the warmest of the Herit4ages demo sites as it shows an average of 247 sunshine days, and the lowest precipitation in a year, on the contrary side,

Palencia in Spain, shows one of the highest precipitation averages, and far fewer sunshine days compared to Bologna (159 days).

2.1.3 Demonstration sites – weather conditions.

The local weather conditions of the demonstration sites were also examined to offer an overview of the environmental factors influencing the performance of the renovation solutions. As for instance, Tartu is Temperate oceanic climate, therefore it experiences relatively short and overcast winters, with few sunshine days during the colder months, in contrast in summer there is significantly more sunshine with few cloudy or rainy days. The average global horizontal solar radiation is approximately 900 to 1,100 kWh/m² per year, monthly average around 107 W/m². In contrast, Palencia enjoys a Mediterranean climate with sufficient sunshine days per year, as is one of the sunniest regions in northern Spain, in winter shows few overcast and rainy days. Compared to Tartu, Palencia shows a much higher levels of global solar radiation, within a range of 1,600 to 1,800 kWh/m² per year, a seasonal variation is shown in the winter months between 50-70 kWh/m² and increasing between 200-250 kWh/m² in summer months, thanks to long days and high sun angles. This is also reflected in the monthly average figures with 180 W/m². Bologna shows an average of 2,042 sunshine hours annually, with about 9.7 hours of sunshine per day in summertime and 2.5 hours daily in wintertime, which signifies an average of 247 hours of sunshine per month. Bologna also shows a reduced precipitation compared to Tartu and Palencia, with only 70 mm monthly average. Funchal, located on Madeira Island, enjoys a mild climate with substantial amounts of sunshine through the year. With Bologna, is the Herit4ages location that presents higher sunshine hours per year (about 5.9 to 6.7 hours daily), August would be the sunniest month (7.5 to 8.5 hours) and December the least averaging 4.5 to 5.3 hours daily. Funchal is also the Herit4ages location with less precipitation, only 48 mm monthly average. Additional details are shown in Table 2 comparing relevant weather parameters between the fourth Herit4ages demonstration locations.

TABLE 2 DETAILS OF AVERAGE WEATHER CONDITIONS IN THE DEMONSTRATION SITES (MONTHLY AVERAGE).

Demo	Sunshine days	Air temperature (°C)	Precipitation Rainfall (mm)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Coldest/ Warmest Month (°C)	Global Horizontal Solar Radiation (W/m ²)
Tartu, EE	114	6.77	630.5	77.26	3.2	February - 4.4, July 18.0	107.12
Palencia, ES	159	11.53	493.9	69.82	3.37	January 3.8, July 21	180.22
Bologna, IT	247	14.84	70.642	69.6	2.58	January -5, July 36.0	167.58
Funchal, PT	189	16.7	48.5	74.3	5.63	February 11	130.35

						August 24	
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2.2 Specific context for Herit4age demonstration sites.

As part of the survey, the context of the surroundings and the environment surrounding the demo site buildings was also analysed. Details in regard to the characteristics of the location (rural, urban), and the access to the building sites were obtained, in Table 3, details and images of the surroundings are shown. As it can be observed, the demonstration sites in Spain, are mostly located in the vicinity areas of the city, as the Posada is in a suburban area at the western side of the city, while the Hermitage (Heritage Lab), is at the northern are in the Town of Canduela, counting with a single access point. The demonstration sites in Tartu, Bologna and Funchal are all located within urban areas, surrounded by buildings and small green areas or parking lots, in the case of Funchal, the demo site is located in the historical city centre, which is characterized by narrow streets. The stereographic images are also shown to represent the sun path in each demonstration location, relative to the demo sites building orientation. As for instance, the office building in Tartu and the residential building in Funchal are both facing the south with slight inclination to west-east orientations respectively. In Funchal, the characteristic narrow streets reduce the amount of solar radiation that enters the interiors of buildings.

TABLE 3 SURROUNDINGS CONTEXT AND SUN PATH IN RELATION TO THE DEMONSTRATION BUILDING.

Tartu, EE		Office building	
Surroundings	Access points	Site View	Stereographic Sun Path
Urban, adjacent areas: other buildings to the North and East, West, street to the South.	Front door, two-way street		
Palencia, ES		Hermitage Canduela	
North: Town of Canduela. West: Cantabria-Meseta highway. South/East: Camesa river.	Single access point – 400 m one-way dirt road.		
Palencia, ES		Posada La Canduela	

<p>Suburban area, at the western edge of the city.</p>	<p>Green areas at the West side, CL-626 road and Montana Palentina to the North, High School to the South.</p>		
<p>Bologna, IT Classroom in the University Campus</p>			
<p>Urban, green areas, parking and squares.</p>	<p>Access to the building is through multiple entrances adjacent to public courtyards. Private parking, through two vehicular and pedestrian entrances, one with two lanes and the other with a single lane.</p>		
<p>Funchal, PT Residential Building</p>			
<p>Urban, Historic centre in the city of Funchal, Madeira</p>	<p>Access to the building is one way street, residential buildings to the East, West and North, the access to the building is via the South facing façade.</p>		

3. The Herit4ages demonstration buildings.

The following sections include detailed description of the demo site buildings, first as a brief introduction, then by describing the structural components, materials, architectural features and installed energy systems.

3.1 The Heritage Lab (HL), Romanesque Hermitage of Canduela.

The Hermitage Santa Maria de la Canduela is the only Heritage Lab in the Herit4ages project, HL indicates that the building is permanently unoccupied. Its original typology is a religious construction, a former church

of Romanesque architectural style, built in the XIII century and restored in 1990. Its historical importance lies in its role as a religious site dating back to the 13th century, serving as a place of worship and pilgrimage. It was recognized as a cultural heritage site with monumental status since 1993. As a Heritage Laboratory, the Hermitage is currently used for testing restoration and construction materials. Its unoccupied status offers a significant advantage, allowing for minimal alteration during testing and monitoring activities without the interference of human activity. The Hermitage la Canduela is located at 98 km from the city of Palencia in Spain, it consists of a single space of 52 m², with a single access point at approximately 300 m distance to the junction with the Meseta-Cantabria highway. It is located between the Town of Canduela (to the north), and the Camesa river (to the south), it is surrounded by green areas, while the closest populated area is located at a short distance of about 500 m. In Figure 3, few exterior images of the Hermitage are shown, the building consisting of a single nave of sturdy stone construction, it features a pitched roof covered with terracotta tiles, and a small bell gable at the main entrance. The small windows (0.8 by 0.1 m height and width) at the extreme side of the nave allows limited admission of natural daylight, presenting a window to wall ratio (WWR) of only 0.32% and 0.12%. The lack of natural illumination is compensated using 17 ceiling hanging halogen luminaires of 1.5 W power.

FIGURE 3 EXTERIOR AND INTERIOR VIEWS OF THE HERMITAGE SANTA MARIA LA REAL, PALENCIA, SPAIN

3.1.1 Historical Context of the Hermitage Santa Maria la Canduela.

The first mention of Canduela appears in a document from 999, where properties in Palencia were granted to Abbot Juan de Cervatos. By 1193, the monastery of San Salvador de Canduela and its estate were sold to the monastery of Santa María la Real de Aguilar. In 1205, the church of San Salvador and its estate were donated to the Premonstratensian monastery, with confirmations from King Alfonso VIII and Pope Honorius in 1224. The *Libro Becerro de las Behetrías* notes Canduela as part of the Aguilar district, with inhabitants as vassals of Don Tello. The connection between the current hermitage and the former monastery is unclear, though nearby remnants of walls and medieval pottery suggest a medieval village once existed as part of the Canduela complex. Before its restoration in 1990 by the Romanesque Studies Centre of Aguilar de Campoo, the Hermitage of Santa María, often misidentified as San Pedro, was in ruins due to the loss of its nave roofs. The restoration involved replacing the wooden framework, rebuilding the collapsed wall above the doorway,

repairing the bell gable, and replacing corner ashlar and corbels, preserving the structure's integrity. The Hermitage was recognized as a cultural Heritage site with Monument Status since 1993 [3] [2].

3.1.2 Construction features the Heritage Laboratory.

The church, constructed entirely from sandstone walls and flooring, features a single rectangular nave and a flat apse separated by a plain pointed triumphal arch. The areas exposed are of 70 m² (North and South orientation) and 13 m² (East) and 22 m² (West orientation). Notable elements include a wooden door with automatic opening, a gabled roof with oak wood structure from 1990 does not count with roof insulation and is topped with ceramic tile. The apse is covered with a pointed barrel vault, while the nave was originally topped with a wooden frame. Its gable wall incorporates a three-tiered bell gable, unattached to the side walls. The bell gable includes a smooth lower section, a middle section with two semicircular openings, and a gabled top with an embrasure for the bell tower. The southern wall contains the doorway, defined by a simple pointed arch with a jamb featuring a nacelle profile. The apse is minimally decorated, featuring only a nacelle-profiled impost that extends from the cornice crowning the pillars supporting the triumphal arch. It is lit by two arrow-slit windows with interior splays—one in the headwall, flanked by spaces for Calderones shields, and the other in the epistle wall. Additionally, a small niche is present in the gospel wall. The Church of Santa María de Canduela, primarily built in the 13th century, reflects the late use of Romanesque traditions, despite exceeding the typical timeframe of this style. Its design is characterized by structural simplicity and a lack of decoration, common in late-period constructions, making it difficult to determine precise affiliations or chronology. Modern additions, such as a possible high choir, have minimal impact on the original structure or its relevance [3].

3.1.3 Relevant energy features - Hermitage Santa Maria la Canduela.

The building as Heritage Laboratory, consumes an average of 0.5 kWh/year.

3.1.4 Building technical details - Hermitage Santa Maria la Canduela.

The Hermitage is powered by solar energy with a solar PV system and micro-wind generation system available on-site. The solar energy production is of approximate 800 kW/year, while energy production from wind as renewable source is of approximately 80 kWh/year. The installation is free-standing due to the historic building value.

3.2 Korporatsioon Vironia, Institute of Baltic Studies, Tartu EE.

3.2.1 The Historical Context of the Korporatsioon Vironia building.

The residence was built as a representative noble residence in the 4th quarter of the 18th century, the mason was P. Opel. In the years 1803-1923, the house was owned by v. Liphart, who rebuilt the house, giving it Neo-Renaissance look added a wing and outbuildings. First completed in 1829 (architect C. A. Kranhals) in winged stone with Venetian window. In 1878 (architect H. v. Stavenhagen) the mansard floor was built into a full

floor, and the house was designed in the Neo-Renaissance style. In the years 1923-1940, the building belonged to the corporation Vironia. In the 1930s, the basement floor was somewhat altered and rebuilt. After World War II, the building has been owned by the University of Tartu and the Estonian University of Agriculture. The building was registered as a cultural monument in March 1997, and is protected under the Heritage Protection Act by the Republic of Estonia. Exterior images of the building are shown in Figure 4.

3.2.2 The Korporatsioon Vironia building energy and technical systems.

The building counts with central heating, for cooling the rooms are climatized with 10kW Mitsubishi inverter cooling units. The building's average energy consumption is about 100,000 kWh/year.

FIGURE 4 EXTERIOR VIEWS OF THE KORPORATSIION VIRONIA DEMO SITE IN TARTU, ESTONIA

3.3 Posada Santa Maria la Real, Palencia Spain.

3.3.1 The Historical Context of Posada Santa Maria la Real.

The building of the Posada Santa Maria la Real dates to the end of the 18th century (1995). The Posada is part of the larger Santa Maria la Real Monastery, a Romanesque monastery founded in the 12th century originally served as stables for the monastery. It served as a hub of monastic life and home of a community of Premonstratensian monks, known for their contemplative and pastoral activities. The architecture of the monastery, including intricate carvings, semi-circular arches, and later Gothic and Renaissance elements due to renovations and expansions over centuries. Following the Ecclesiastical Confiscations of Mendizabal in the early 19th century, the monastery was abandoned, while in the late 20th century it was restored to preserve its historical character to adapt it to modern use as a Posada and tourist destination. As restored accommodation facility, the Posada offers the opportunity to explore the Romanesque art and architecture. The Monastery of Santa María la Real has been designated as a Monument of Cultural Interest since 1914. The Posada is located adjacent to the Monastery but is not individually protected as a heritage building.

3.3.2 The Posada, building construction and features.

The building has a net floor area of 1456 m², and counts with two floor levels, at the east side adjoins the Monastery of Santa Maria la Real, and to the south a High School facility, to the west and north area the building is surrounded by green areas or the CL-626 road (See Table 3). Two-storey building with a wooden structure and a gabled roof topped with corbels, ground floor with masonry walls and window openings with

wooden lintel embedded in the wall, first floor with brick façade finish and lintelled windows with traditional carpentry and stained-glass windows. In 1995, the building was renovated to make it suitable for tourist accommodation. Figure 5 shows exterior images of the building.

3.3.3 The Posada, relevant energy features.

For energy consumption, the building is heated with approximate consumption of gasoil of 16,000 L/year (considering the data provided by the demo site partner for 2021). The average energy consumption is of about 78.800 kWh/year.

3.3.4 The Posada, building technical details.

The building does not count with air conditioning system. The heating system consist of one boiler of 220 kW fuelled with gasoil to warm the interior areas using radiant heaters. A boiler of 60 kW is used to provide domestic hot water (DHW). The interior space is illuminated with 4 LED wall mounted luminaires of 15 W.

FIGURE 5 EXTERIOR VIEWS OF THE POSADA LA CANDUELA, DEMO SITE BUILDING IN PALENCIA, SPAIN

3.4 Faculty of Engineering Building– Bologna, Italy.

3.4.1 The Historical Context of the FEB building.

The design of the Faculty of Engineering was affected by a long sequence of events, starting from the site selection in Bologna’s urban area. It was overseen by the Technical Office of the Consortium for University Buildings regarding its internal planning and by Giuseppe Grazzini & Figli company concerning the structural design of the construction works. From 1931 onwards, the architect Giuseppe Vaccaro was involved in the project, giving the building its architectural forms and defining its functional and distributive scheme. The accuracy of his design marked a pivotal moment for Bolognese architecture in the first half of the Twentieth century. The project was approved in February 1933. The construction work began in December and was completed on the 28th of October 1935. The effective inauguration was on the 2nd of January 1936. Since then, the building has undergone multiple modifications. Initially, these were aimed at repairing damages from the Second World War. Subsequently, interventions were made to align with evolving university standards and functional requirements over time. These changes mainly involved the installation of new heating and ventilation systems, improvements in fire safety, and the replacement of windows. As a result of

these changes, the original configuration of the building has been partially altered. As historical added value, the building is the Historical seat of engineering at the University of Bologna, it is one of the first XX century buildings to be listed in Bologna under ministerial protection in 1995. Regarding relevant architectural features, built between 1932 and 1935, the Faculty of Engineering was designed by the architect Giuseppe Vaccaro following the main principles of Modernism declined to the local context. The building is considered a jewel of local rationalist heritage. The use of industrial systems and materials for the most advanced plant equipment, the innovative nature in finishing components, and the refusal of decorations thanks to introducing a reinforced concrete structure, definitively confirm its compliance with the principles and the lexicon of Modern Architecture [4]. The whole result is a solid architecture based on the balance between the static nature derived by the full masses and the typical dynamic sense of layout articulation and windowed façades. Images of the exterior building are shown in Figure 6.

Heritage Protection Grade

The building was listed under ministerial protection in 1995 and is protected according to the Codice dei Beni Culturali e del Paesaggio (Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape, d.lgs. n.42/2004) [5].

FIGURE 6–EXTERIOR VIEWS OF THE DEMONSTRATION SITE BUILDING, IN THE FACULTY OF ENGINEERING, BOLOGNA, ITALY

3.4.2 The FEUB building, relevant energy features.

The building uses electricity for lighting, cooling, for laboratory equipment and other typical appliances, natural gas for heating and domestic heat water (DHW). As average energy consumption, the building consumes a total of 331.97 kWh/m², the distribution is normalized in Table 4, per floor area of the building (18.860 m²), and per person considering 4255 occupants.

Table 4 Distribution of Energy use in the FEUB.

	Electricity	Natural Gas	Water	Total
Per floor area	72.56 kWh/m ²	24,27 smc/m ²	0.69 m ³ /m ²	331.97 kWh/m ²
Per person	321.61 kWh/person	107.56 smc/person	3.08 m ³ /person	1481.89 kWh/person

3.4.3 The FEUB building, technical details.

The FEUB building does not count with renewable energy sources. In the monitored room (classroom), is cooled by an external DAIKIN VRV (variable refrigerant volume) RY200FW1 cooling unit, which emits cold air through ceiling-mounted fan coil units installed behind the false ceiling (Figure 7, left and centre). The classroom is heated by a centralized heating generation in the building, which was replaced in the 2010s, it comprises of three modulating natural gas condensing boilers, each one with a thermal output of 750 kW and an efficiency rate of 98% at 80°C. The hot water distribution system utilizes outdated steel pipes with no insulation (from post-war era). In the classroom, heat is emitted through 4 radiators positioned below the windows (Figure 7, right). The lighting consists of 24 ceiling mounted fluorescent luminaires, each with four lamps of 18W, for a total of 1.73 kW (Figure 7, left).

FIGURE 7 ENERGY SYSTEMS IN THE FEUB, SERVING THE MONITORED CLASSROOM.

3.5 Residential building – Funchal, PT.

3.5.1 The Historical Context of the residential building.

The building is located in the historical area of the city of Funchal. History tells us that the first settlement in the city of Funchal emerged in the area that is currently known as 'Zona Velha' (Downtown). The great heritage and architectural value of this part of the city makes it a must-see that deserves to be experienced both by day and by night. Funchal Downtown is known for its narrow-cobbled streets, embellished by the typical façades of old houses. With the 'Portas Pintadas' (Painted Doors) project, this urban scenario has become even more attractive. The artistic community was invited to make interventions on buildings' doors and façades, turning this area into an alfresco art gallery. At the heart of this historic area, we find the Corpo Santo Chapel, one of the few 15th-century buildings that survives to this day. In turn, on one of the oldest streets in Funchal, Santa Maria Street, we can find several traditional local businesses, such as the 'Fábrica de Chapéus' and the 'Fábrica de Botas de Vilão'. If you continue walking along this cobbled street, you will find the Baroque-style Socorro Church and a small viewpoint. In addition to a detailed daytime visit, Funchal Downtown should also be experienced by night, as nightlife is one of the island's major attractions: In "zona Velha visit madeira". An image of the exterior of the building is shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8 EXTERIOR VIEW, RESIDENTIAL BUILDING FUNCHAL.

3.5.2 The residential building, relevant energy features.

The residential building net floor area is 56.58 m². According to data provided from the year 2022, the building energy uses about 170 kWh/month, for an average energy consumption of 2048 kWh/year. No information was available regarding gas consumption.

3.5.3 The residential building technical details.

The building counts with nine ceiling mounted luminaires, with two fluorescent tubes and 7 LEDs type lamps of 36W and 10W respectively. The building does not count with heating and cooling systems. A sunshade is installed on the façade for solar protection.

4. The selected room for the implementation of the Herit4ages renovation solutions.

The selected room (floor plan, location in the building – floor plan of building-, area, dimensions, exposed surfaces, orientation, interior surfaces – area, materials, thickness-), doors and windows features (orientation, dimensions, materials), an overview of the main features is shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5 OVERVIEW OF THE SELECTED ROOM MAIN FEATURES.

Demo site	Selected room	Location in the building	Net floor area (m ²)	Occupancy Type	Occupancy patterns
Hermitage, ES	404, 405	Single space	32.9, 36.8	n/a	n/a
Office room, EE	HL	Floor level	52	4 to 6 people	variable
Posada, ES	18	North wing area	12	2 people	variable
Bologna, IT	Aula 0.4	Ground floor, North-East Wing area.	204	64 people	From 9am to 19pm. During lecture months March/June and September/December. In examination periods (Jan, Feb, July and September). Unoccupied during vacations time: December 23 to January 6; August 5 to 25 th .
Residential building, PT	n/a			2 people	Irregular patterns.

4.1 The Posada hotel room, Santa Maria la Real.

The selected hotel room selected for the implementation of the Herit4ages renovation solutions is identified as room number 18 and is located in the north wing of the posada complex. It consists of a room for accommodation of maximum 3 persons. It has a net floor area of 12 m², with dimensions of 2.7 m by 4.7 m (width and length), and 4.0 m height. Views from the interior of the selected room are shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9 INTERIOR VIEWS OF THE HOTEL ROOM IN POSADA SANTA MARIA LA REAL.

4.1.1 Construction and Structural features – room hotel.

The Posada counts with a 20 cm wooden structure (pillars and beams), and a combination of masonry and brick walls of 25 cm, the roof is gabled roof topped with corbels, and the floor finished is of timbered parquet. The exposed surface of the facade has 6.4 m², consist of walls made of a combination of masonry and bricks with a thickness of 0.2 m. The roof of the room area has a surface area of 18 m² and covered with roof terracotta tiles.

4.1.2 Building components – room hotel.

The door leading to the hallway, is made of wood, of dimensions 0.75 by 2.0 m, with traditional rustic white colour, the only window faces south, with dimensions 1.50 m by 1.50 m and a WWR of 32%. As solar protection only interior textile curtains are used in the Posada.

4.2 The classroom - Faculty of Engineering, University of Bologna.

The room is located in the north-east wing area of the building on the ground floor, with approximate dimensions of 3.8 m height, 10.2 m width and 19.4 m length, consisting of a net floor area of 204 m². It is occupied by approximate 64 people, as regular schedules, the classroom is occupied almost at full capacity during the normal lecture periods (March to June, and September to December). During the exam period, there is an occasional use of the building in January-February, July and September. The occupation hours are from 9:00 am to 19:00 pm. Vacation periods are usually from December 23rd to January 6th, and from August 5th to 25th. Interior views of the classroom are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Interior views of the classroom in the demo site in University of Bologna.

4.2.1 Construction and Structural features – classroom area.

The area of the building where the classroom is located is made of reinforced concrete framework with rectangular pillars of varying dimensions that goes from level to level (from 20 cm x 30 cm to 60 cm x 135 cm), and beams with different shapes and dimensions according to the span area (from 20 cm x 30 cm to 60 cm x 185 cm). The walls in the classroom have a variable U-value, estimated from 0.45 to 0.85 W/m²K, detailed description can be found in [6]. The roof U-value is 140 W/m²K, while the floor slab is from 1.15 to 1.35 W/m²K. Detailed information of the exposed surfaces is provided in Table 6.

TABLE 6 EXPOSED SURFACES OF THE CLASSROOM DEMO SITE IN THE UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA.

	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4	Wall 5	Floor slab
Surface area m ²	10.4	8.24	10.4	4.29	74.61	n/a
Material and thickness	Solid brick 28 cm, Air 28 cm, solid brick 14 cm and gypsum plaster 2 cm. Total 72 cm.	Solid brick 28 cm, Air 70 cm, solid brick 28cm and gypsum plaster 2 cm. Total 128 cm.	Solid brick 28 cm, gypsum plaster 2cm. Total 30 cm.	Solid brick 28 cm, Air 70 cm, solid brick 28 cm and gypsum plaster 2 cm. Total 128cm.	Solid brick 14 cm/28 cm Air 30 cm, solid brick 14 cm and gypsum plaster 2 cm. Total 77 cm.	n/a
Thermal transmittance U-value W/m ² K	0.50 W/m ² K	0.32 W/m ² K	0.85 W/m ² K	0.32 W/m ² K	0.5 W/m ² K	2.5-3.0 W/m ² K

4.2.2 Building components – classroom area.

The classroom counts with exterior metal door of 3.15 m x 2.0 m from 1935 (modern style), U-value 5.70 W/m²K, an interior door that leads to the corridor made of wood of dimensions 2.10 by 1.20 m. It counts with a first type of window with single clear glazing facing East, with metal frame of dimensions 2.05 by 2.0 m and U-value 5.70 W/m²K and g-value 0.85, as solar protection the window has fabric indoor blinds. A second type of window facing south, with single clear glazing of dimensions 2.05 m by 2.0 m, with a U-value of 5.70 W/m²K, and g-value 0.85. A third type of window is also facing south, with 2.05 m and 4.0 m dimensions.

4.3 Residential building – Funchal, PT.

The apartment to be monitored in the residential building is located on the third floor, with a net floor area of 50.35 m² with dimensions of 2.60 m x 5.37 m x 4.63 m, or regular shape, the apartment is occupied by two persons.

4.3.1 Construction and Structural features – residential building.

The building is made of stone masonry and concrete blocks, floor and roof or reinforced concrete and roof tiles for the roof.

4.3.2 Building components – residential building.

The doors are made of wood of dimensions of 2.0 by 0.8 m leading to the exterior, and similar characteristics for those in the interior of the apartment. The windows have clear single glazing of 3mm, frame made of

wood, and dimensions of 1.80 m by 1.20 m facing south and a similar one faces north, as solar protection it has a sun shading device.

5. Data-based subjective evaluation, survey cards

In order to assess the perception of the occupants in regard to the buildings, a survey was applied in two different periods of the year, considering first wintertime (between January and March 2024) and summertime (between July and September 2024). The survey was applied in different formats depending on the demo-site (online based or paper based) as they responsible partners found more convenient. The assessment involved the perception of the users in regard to visual, thermal comfort as well as air quality and acoustic environment indoors. Also, it the occupants were requested to give their opinion in regard to the historic character of the building and provide details of their occupation patterns. The results are presented in the following sections, while the survey applied for summertime can be found in Annex I.

5.1 Korporatsioon Vironia, Institute of Baltic Studies (IBS), Tartu Estonia.

In wintertime, nine occupants were interviewed, between the 5th and the 20th of March 2024, at different times of the day, mostly in the afternoon (between 14:00 pm and 19:00 pm) and one at 9:00 am. In summertime, five users were interviewed about their opinion on different aspects related to the demo site building. The survey was applied in different days in June and July 2024 in the afternoon between 13:00 to 17:00 pm, first on sunny days (afternoon hours) and also in a rainy day (13:00 pm).

5.1.1 IBS, Demographic data and occupancy patterns

Wintertime Survey

Five women and four men were interviewed, three occupants are between the ages of 26 to 35, five in the age range of 18-25 and one between 46 to 55 years old. They are present in the room on daily basis, and two of them once a week (for a maximum of 6 hours). The occupancy is mostly regular, from those attending daily, four are for a maximum of 8 hours, one for a maximum of 10 hours, their schedule is mostly regular from 9:00 to 17:00 pm, two of them work in the evening and one in the mornings.

Summertime Survey

Three women and two men with age ranges between 18 to 45 years old were interviewed during summertime. The age range of the women is from 26 to 45, and of the men from 18 to 25 years old, mostly with University or Postgraduate degree level. The occupants are present in the office room several times a week for a maximum of eight hours and one maximum of one hour. Their presence in the room is mostly of a fix term from 9:00 to 17:00 hours in varying days.

5.1.2 IBS, Thermal and visual environment

Wintertime Survey

For the users, in Wintertime the thermal environment is 'Slightly cold' (3 users), neutral (2 users) and cold (2 users), they find the environment 'Acceptable' (5 users) and 'Slightly Acceptable' (4 users) and would prefer a warmer environment (5 users) or 'no change' (2 users). They mostly find the thermal environment with the use of the heating to be sufficient, only one find it 'non-sufficient'. Regarding the need of a solar protection device, they feel the room would benefit from the use of interior vertical blinds or roll blinds (5 users), while two answered that it was not necessary. Regarding visual performance, in the morning, most of them find the lighting environment to be 'slightly' or 'too dark', while three of them find it 'adequate'. Most of them would prefer the lighting conditions to be 'slightly lighter' or 'Lighter' while two of them would prefer 'No change'. In the late afternoon, they find the interior environment to be 'Too dark' and two of them 'slightly dark', they would prefer it to be 'lighter' or 'slightly lighter'. When the artificial lights are on, only two of them find it adequate, and three find it 'Too bright', most of them find it to be 'slightly dark'. The users don't feel that there is sufficient natural light in their office and usually need to turn on the artificial lighting to get sufficient illumination for working activities. They all have a preference for natural lighting, and regarding the colour of electric light, they would prefer it to be 'natural white' (4 users) or 'Warm white' (5 users).

Summertime Survey

The survey was applied in outdoor conditions where a temperature minimum of 20°C (intermediate sky conditions, humidity 54%), and between 25°C and 28°C (sunny day, 47% relative humidity). In the case of the survey applied in sunny conditions, the occupants declared to feel mostly a 'Warm' environment indoors and one 'Hot' where the outdoor temperature was 28°C. They declared the environment to be 'Slightly Not acceptable' or 'Slightly Acceptable' while, at 28°C the user declared the interior environment as 'Not Acceptable'. In the case of the interview made under rainy conditions (17°C outdoors), the user felt the interior conditions to be 'Neutral' and 'Acceptable'. They all declared to prefer a 'Cooler' interior environment, with exception of the one interviewed in a rainy day which declares 'No change'. They also indicate that they usually need to remove some clothes to feel more comfortable, in regard to the need of a solar protection device, two of them declare it was needed for glare control, one for controlling the excessive heat and two did not find the need of using such device.

Regarding the visual environment, they found the interior of the office 'Slightly Dark' without the use of artificial lighting, two of them found it 'Adequate' lighting environment. About their preferences, the opinions are divided as two would prefer a 'slightly lighter' environment, one 'No change' and two a 'Lighter' luminous environment. One finds the need of turning the artificial lights on when there are cloudy outdoor conditions, while three occupants do not find the need of artificial light. Regarding their preference for natural or artificial light, they all prefer natural light and a 'Natural white' colour of artificial light, only one preferred a 'Warm white' colour.

5.1.3 Korporatsioon Vironia, IBS, IEQ (acoustic, air quality, humidity)

Wintertime Survey

Regarding the acoustic environment, they find it would be better 'slightly quieter' or 'much quieter' but most of them would prefer 'no change'. The source of noises could be from exterior (road noise very loud) or sometimes neighbouring rooms, simple actions like closing doors or windows would help to solve the problem. Regarding the quality of the air environment, they find it mostly 'somewhat acceptable' (5 users), 'somewhat unacceptable' (2 users) and one 'clearly unacceptable' and 'clearly acceptable'. Regarding the perception of humidity in the office room, they find the room to be 'dry' (3 users), 'slightly dry' (4 users) and 'neutral' (2 users). They would prefer it to be more humid or 'no change' (2 users).

Summer survey

Regarding the acoustic environment, the users interviewed in summertime, the opinions were divided as they found that the environment would be better 'slightly quieter' (2 occupants), 'Quieter' or 'Much quieter' and one prefer 'No change'. The noise in the building mostly has its origin on the street, and traffic outside. Regarding the air quality indoors, they found it mostly 'Just unacceptable', as they qualify it as 'dense', 'enclosed', 'dull', 'stuffy' and 'stagnant', and there is constant need to open the windows to clean the air. They also find the room mostly 'Dry' (3 users), 'Slightly Dry' or 'Too dry', and would prefer a more humid environment indoors.

5.1.4 IBS, Value and impact of the historic building from user's perspective

Wintertime Survey

The group interviewed during the wintertime period, have in overall around one to two years being regular users of the building, two have 3 to 5 years and one has been using the building for already 20 years. Their perception of the building is rather 'Positive' (6 users) or 'Indifferent' (2 users) only one declared to have a 'Negative' opinion. The features of the building that they find relevant are the 'Façade' and the interior staircase. They find the state of conservation of the building as 'neither good or bad' (4 users), 'In good state of conservation' (3 users), or 'Slightly deteriorated' (2 users). In regard to the level of intervention that would be acceptable for them, most of them would accept a 'Renovation for less energy use' (6 users), a 'Low maintenance level intervention' (2 users) and one, would prefer a 'High adaptive renovation for reuse' of the building. The opinions are divided in regards if the interventions should be permanent or reversible, two of them would prefer it to be reversible, two of them would agree with the renovation to be 'permanent', one conditions the idea to maintain the original façade and stairwell, the rest show no preference.

Summer survey

The interviewees in summer have been occupying the office room mostly about 1 to 2 years (3 users) and two of them for about 10 years. Their perception of the building is mostly 'Indifferent' (3 users) and two of

them declared to feel 'Positive' about the building they occupy. They feel the most important feature of the building is the 'Façade' and the 'Windows', one found the interior design also important, and the historic architecture. Regarding the conservation of the building, two of them found it in good state of conservation, two declared it as 'Neither good nor bad' and one found it 'Slightly deteriorated'. Regarding the level of intervention that could be implemented in the building, they would prefer a 'Renovation for less energy use' (3 occupants) and two of them would renovate the building for 'Preservation, to stop the deterioration'. In regard to their agreement with the implementation of permanent renovation measures, they mostly agree, if 'carefully planned', to 'improve the interior conditions' and if the 'prominent features of the building are respected'.

5.1.5 Korporatsioon Vironia, IBS, Overall analysis

The occupants found the thermal interior environment in general 'acceptable', with a natural inclination to have it 'warmer' in wintertime, while in summer they feel it as 'warm' and sometimes 'hot' as sometimes they need to remove some clothes to feel more comfortable. Regarding visual environment, they find that is slightly dark, they would prefer it 'lighter' as they need to turn the lights ON when is cloudy. For electric light, they prefer a natural white light colour. In regard to the acoustic environment, they feel that the interior is slightly noisy and would prefer a quieter environment, as they have noises from the outside. The humidity is acceptable, slightly dry and in overall they find no need of change, while slight increased levels in humidity seems to be acceptable. Their opinion of the building is either positive or indifferent, and they believe the renovation should be done for energy efficiency purposes and would accept permanent interventions if they are properly planned.

5.2 Posada la Canduela, Palencia Spain.

The survey corresponding to wintertime was applied in March 2024 between 17:00 and 19:00 pm, under overcast sky conditions and exterior temperature of maximum 13.6°C. In summertime it was applied in July between 14:00 and 15:00 pm on sunny conditions of about 31°C.

5.2.1 Posada, Demographic data and occupancy patterns

Wintertime

Due to the vacation season, few people were available during this time in the hotel, hence only two people was reported to answer the survey. This consisted of two men, the first between the ages of 26-36 years old, and a second one between 46 and 55 years old. Both work in the posada and can give very accurate responses regarding the rooms and the building. As they spend time in the area between 8 and 10 hours in daily basis, mostly during the morning and afternoon hours on weekdays/weekends.

Summertime

In summertime, two women and one man answered the survey, ages about 26-35 years old and 56-65 for the women, and 46-55 years old for the man, they were all temporary visitors to the hotel from Spain and a woman from Luxembourg. Their presence in the room is then occasional and when it happens, they are in the room a minimum of 4 hours, while the women declared to be in the room more than 10 hours.

5.2.2 Posada, Thermal and visual environment

Wintertime

They felt that the thermal environment in the room was slightly cold (-1) during morning hours between 8:00 am and 12:00 pm. While they both found the environment 'Acceptable', one of them would prefer the environment to be 'warmer' while the second would prefer 'no change'. In afternoon hours, they found the room also 'slightly cold', both finding it 'acceptable' and only one would prefer it to be warmer. In the late afternoon hours (15:00 to 18:00 pm), they found the room still 'slightly cold' with similar opinions as earlier hours. They replied indistinctly ('yes' and 'no') to the question of needing additional clothes to feel more comfortable, and similarly, to the question of the sufficiency of the use of heating to warm the room. Regarding visual comfort, similarly, the older interviewed found the environment adequately lit, while the younger person found it 'slightly dark', the former would prefer to have it 'slightly lighter', while the latter would prefer 'no change'. Similar answers were provided for the afternoon and late afternoon, however, in summary it seems that the room is found just 'slightly dark' by the occupants, as they do not feel the need to turn the lights ON to feel comfortable. They both prefer the room to be lit naturally (daylight), while the preferred colour for electric light would be warm and cool white respectively (See Annex I).

Summertime

In summertime, the interviewees found the room 'neutral' and would prefer it to be 'cooler' (-1), in the afternoon the room was 'warm' and they found it 'slightly not acceptable' they would prefer it 'cooler'. For visual performance, they found the room 'slightly dark' or 'adequate' in the afternoon and would prefer 'slight change' or 'no change' (2 persons). They found the place sufficiently lit and prefer natural light, and warm white for electric lighting, one person would prefer natural white electric light.

5.2.3 Posada, IEQ (acoustic, air quality and humidity).

Wintertime

Regarding acoustic environment, they would prefer the room to be quieter, as there is some noise from the outside and adjacent rooms, this happens during nighttime and in the mornings, a solution would be to insulate the room acoustically. Regarding the air quality environment, they found it acceptable and qualified it as 'breezy' and 'fresh', however, they feel the need to open the windows often to clear the air. Regarding humidity, they found the humidity in the room 'neutral' and would prefer 'no change'.

Summertime

Regarding acoustic environment, they would prefer the room to be 'quieter' or 'no change', the noise discomfort is caused by noises from the kitchen, a solution would be to use acoustic insulation or make request the noise to be quieter. The air quality is clearly acceptable, and described as 'clean', 'dry', 'sufficient', 'pure', 'fresh', 'clean', they mostly do not feel the need to open the window to clear the air (one person answered 'yes'). For humidity they found the environment, 'neutral' and would prefer 'no-change'.

5.2.4 Posada, Value and impact of the historic building from user's perspective.

Wintertime

Regarding the perception of the building, they found it to be 'positive' with emotional (family or personal history) and practical (work, studies), connections respectively. They are both familiar with the building/room, and the most important feature of the building is its architecture. They found the room to be 'slightly deteriorated' and in 'good state of conservation' respectively, and they didn't show opposition to the implementation of renovation measures to the building. They believe that the level of intervention should be done to preserve the building (stop deterioration), and to reduce the use of energy, respectively. They would prefer a 'permanent' and a 'reversible' intervention respectively.

Summertime

The persons interviewed in summertime declared to have a 'positive' perception of the building historic character, with their attachment linked to the 'cultural, historical appreciation'. They found the building to be 'in good state of conservation' (2 persons) and 'slightly deteriorated' (one person). They would agree with a preservation to stop deterioration, and one to reduce energy use. And only one answered to the question of 'permanent' or 'reversible' renovation measures, saying she would prefer 'reversible' measures.

5.2.5 Posada, Overall analysis

The occupants found the room alternatively slightly cold in winter, preferring a warmer environment, and would prefer it 'cooler' in summertime. Regarding visual environment, in the occupant's opinion, the room is slightly dark in wintertime but would prefer no change or have it slightly lit. They declared that they don't feel the need of turning ON the lights, for electric light they prefer warm and cool light colour. They would prefer a quieter environment as there are noises from the outside or the kitchen, for air quality conditions, they find it has an acceptable air quality environment even if sometimes opening the windows helps to clear the air. They don't find needs to make changes in regard to the humidity in the room. An interviewed familiar with the topic, found the use of energy very high and would prefer to have energy efficient appliances to reduce the energy consumption and to use space heating as little as possible. They have a positive opinion of the building, as they found it slightly deteriorated or in a good state or conservation. In their opinion, the intervention should be done to stop deterioration, but they would prefer reversible measures to be implemented.

5.3 Faculty of Engineering – Bologna, Italy.

The survey in the FEUB for wintertime was implemented on 27th February 2024 between 9:00 am 12:00 pm, corresponding to data collection for wintertime, the day was reported to be rainy with outdoor temperature between 9°C and 10°C. In summertime, the survey was applied on the 26th of September 2024, in two sessions, first in the morning at 9:00 to 9:30 am with an outdoor temperature of 18°C and a Relative Humidity of 84% in mostly cloudy conditions. The session in the afternoon, was from 12:00 to 15:00 pm with outdoor temperature of 26°C to 27°C and 59% Relative Humidity. The results of the session in the afternoon are presented graphically in each of the corresponding sections, while for the session in the morning are included in the description.

5.3.1 FEUB Demographic data and Occupancy Patterns

Wintertime Survey

In wintertime, eighty users of the classroom participated in the survey, which was applied online, a total of 43 females and 36 males. Most participants are female students between 18 and 25 years old (40), a slightly reduced number is shown for the male students between the same age (31). The rest of the participants are employees between 26 and 45 years old, five men and three women, the distribution is shown in Figure 10 (left). Regarding occupancy, the participants are present in the room on daily basis or several times a week, only 12% correspond to participants present in the room once a week.

FIGURE 10 DEMOGRAPHICS ANALYSIS FOR THE FEUB DEMO SITE CORRESPONDING TO WINTERTIME.

Summertime Survey

The participants were asked how many hours they were spending in the classroom; most participants are students between 18-25 years old and spend between eight and ten continuous hours in the room. As shown in Figure 10 (left), the day of most occupancy is on Wednesday by students, while the second most occupied day would be Monday, occupancy period is 9:00 to 19:00 hours. In the survey for summertime participated a total of 71 interviewees, the majority is women between 18-25 years old (48), and less than half is men of the same age (21), about two of the persons interviewed are women of age between 26 and 35 years old. Regarding occupancy, most students spent a maximum of 6 hours in the room, a reduced but similar proportion spent a maximum of 8 hours (38%), and few around 10 hours (28% of the interviewees).

5.3.2 FEUB Thermal and Visual Environment

Wintertime Survey

To assess the perception of the interior environment regarding thermal and visual conditions, participants were asked to judge the thermal environment according to a rating scale, first, of seven degrees to declare their sensation 'now'. In a subsequent scale of four levels, they will indicate if they environment was acceptable or not, and finally if they would prefer any changes to be implemented, as shown in Figure 11.

2.1.1 How do you feel about the thermal environment in this room in this moment?

-3 very cold	-2 cold	-1 cold	0 Neutral	1 Warm	2 Hot	3 Very hot
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2.1.2 Do you find that the thermal environment at this moment is...

Acceptable	Slightly Acceptable	Not acceptable	Slightly not acceptable
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2.1.3 How do you prefer the environment to be in this moment?

-1 would prefer cooler	0 no change	1 would prefer warmer
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FIGURE 11 RATING SCALE TO JUDGE THE THERMAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE DEMO SITE ROOMS.

Most users found the thermal environment to be '0 neutral', also most of them felt the environment to be 'acceptable' or 'slightly acceptable'. This is reflected in the results also shown in Figure 12 (up left) where most of them declared to prefer a 'no change' or some of them would prefer a bit 'cooler' thermal environment in the classroom.

FIGURE 12 THERMAL ENVIRONMENT AS JUDGED BY THE OCCUPANTS IN WINTERTIME.

The participants were also asked if they would need to wear additional clothes to feel comfortable, to what they reply mostly 'No'. Similar answers were given to the question, if the thermal environment was sufficiently warm with the heating conditions, to what they reply mostly 'Yes', to this question, about 9% answered 'sometimes is too much' (Figure 12, low-left). Participants were also asked if they felt there was need of additional solar shading device to protect the interior environment of overheating or glare, the answer was mostly 'No' and a reduced group of people provide an answer to indicate 'Maybe' or 'Sometimes' (Figure 12, low-right).

FIGURE 13 PERCEPTION OF THE VISUAL ENVIRONMENT BY THE OCCUPANTS IN WINTERTIME.

Regarding the visual environment, the occupants were asked to judge the lighting conditions of the room with the lights off, and how they would prefer it to be. As shown in Figure 13, to the question of ‘how they found the lighting conditions’ (up-left graph) they indicated that they found the room ‘slightly dark’ or ‘too dark’. Consequently, they would prefer the room to be ‘slightly lighter’ and a smaller number of participants would prefer no changes in the room lighting conditions (up-right graph in Figure 13).

Subsequently, occupants were asked if they found the room sufficiently ‘naturally lit’ to what they answered mostly ‘Yes’, but also a good proportion of occupants answered ‘No’ (Figure 13, low-left graph). Finally,

regarding their colour preference for artificial lighting, most of the participants would prefer a neutral white colour. The ‘Winter’ written version of the questionnaire is included in this Report as Annex 1.

Summertime Survey

The occupants in the survey in summer afternoon, in a similar proportion found the thermal environment indoors as ‘Neutral’ in the ranking scale, qualifying it as ‘Acceptable’ or ‘Slightly acceptable’, a lower proportion found it ‘Warm’ but still ‘Acceptable’ or ‘Slightly acceptable’. Only one interviewee qualified the thermal environment as ‘Slightly hot’ but ‘Not acceptable’ (Figure 14, up left). To the question to indicate their preferences for any change in the environment, in a similar proportion indicated ‘No change’ or ‘Prefer it Warmer’, Figure 14 (up-right) showing the results also according to age. To the question if the thermal environment was sufficiently comfortable with the cooling system, they replied mostly ‘No’, while a reduced number of participants replied ‘Yes’ (50% and 35% respectively) (Fig.14, down left). The next question was about their opinion on the need of a solar shading protection, their answer was related to the use, mostly answered that shading would be needed for ‘Glare control’, then a smaller number of interviewees indicated that shading protection was ‘Not’ needed according to their perception of the interior environment. ‘Excessive heat’ was the answer with less representation (Fig.14, down-right).

FIGURE 14 PERCEPTION OF THE THERMAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE CLASSROOM IN SUMMERTIME.

Regarding visual environment in summertime (Figure 15), the interior luminous environment is perceived as ‘Slightly Dark’ with no preference to change for most users. Also, ‘Slightly Dark’ with preference for a ‘Slightly brighter environment’ for a similar proportion of users, and ‘Too Dark’ with preference for a ‘Slightly brighter’ luminous environment for almost the same number of users.

FIGURE 15 VISUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE CLASSROOM IN SUMMERTIME.

When asked if they found there is sufficiency of natural light, and if they have the need of turning on the artificial light in the morning or in the afternoon. They replied, mostly ‘No’ and ‘Yes’ stating, they need artificial light for an adequate lighting indoors. Some replied that they need artificial light in the afternoon as the natural light does not provide sufficient illuminance in the room (Figure 15, right). Some occupants manifested that the lack of sufficient natural light, they need to turn on the artificial light in both, morning and afternoon hours. In summertime, the preference of artificial light colour is also ‘natural white’.

5.3.3 FEUB Interior Environment Indoors (IEQ)

Wintertime Survey

In a following part of the survey, the quality of the interior environment the sensations perceived by the occupants were also assessed regarding noise, humidity and air quality. To the question about the acoustic environment indoors, they found it acceptable and declared that would prefer ‘no change’ in majority, while few participants would prefer a ‘slightly quieter’ environment (Figure 16, up-left graph). They mostly declared to perceive no noise that could be perceived as uncomfortable, or that the source would be external from the street or other adjacent rooms, and that it could be easily fixable by closing the doors.

FIGURE 16 INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT BY THE CLASSROOM OCCUPANTS IN WINTERTIME.

Regarding the air quality in the classroom, they mostly declare it as ‘just acceptable’ and only a 10% of the interviewees declared it as ‘just unacceptable’. Interestingly, only 3 occupants found the air quality in the room to be ‘clearly acceptable’ and only one found it to be ‘clearly unacceptable’ which represents the two extremes of the questionnaire (Figure 16, up-right graph). Regarding the humidity in the room, the participants were asked to use a ranking scale of seven levels, from ‘0 neutral’ to ‘-3 too dry’ or ‘3 too humid’. They found the environment to be ‘neutral’ most of the occupants, and few of them found it to be in the rank ‘2 humid’ (Figure 16, down-left graph). To the question of, if they would prefer any change, their answer was ‘no change’ or would prefer it ‘drier’ (Figure 16, down-right graph).

Summertime Survey

Regarding the acoustic environment, the answers of the group interviewed in summertime were similar to those interviewed in wintertime, they mostly found no need to change, or that the room should be ‘Slightly quieter’. Regarding the air quality in the interior environment, as shown in Figure 17, the ‘summertime’ group declared that they found it ‘Just acceptable’ but that they need to open the windows quite often to change the air. In regard to humidity, they found the interior environment ‘Neutral’ and no need to change, some found the environment ‘Humid’ and they would prefer it to be ‘less humid’.

FIGURE 17 INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY IN THE CLASSROOM IN SUMMERTIME.

5.3.4 FEUB Value and impact of the historic building from user’s perspective.

Finally, the occupants were asked to give their opinion of the Heritage building, and judge their state of conservation, the historic and architectural value, as well as if they felt any connection with it, and their appreciation of spending time in a Heritage building. In both surveys in winter and summer, they mostly declared to feel ‘indifferent’ in regards to their connection to the building, while the other options were to indicate if they felt a ‘negative’ or ‘positive’ perception of the building (Figure 18, left), while their opinion of the conservation of the building, they answered ‘neither good, neither bad’ or to be ‘slightly deteriorated’ (25 opinions in both cases), a good proportion of occupants also declared to find the building ‘highly deteriorated’ (15 opinions), while around 10 occupants found it to be in ‘good state of conservation’ and only one found it to be ‘highly conserved, in good conditions’. Finally, the occupants were asked to give their opinion to the level of renovation that the building would need. In wintertime, a number corresponding to almost 50% of the occupants that answered the survey indicated that a renovation for ‘less energy use’ would be the most appropriate to do. From those, 25% indicated that a ‘low maintenance level’ of renovation would be the appropriate one, and the rest of the occupants declared in a similar proportion to perform a renovation to ‘stop the deterioration’ or a ‘high level intervention’ to reuse the building would be better. In summertime, 11% declared the need of a ‘high level intervention’ to adapt the building to reuse, and 39% of the need to perform a ‘Low maintenance level’ intervention, 35% opinion is that a ‘Renovation for less energy use’ is required.

FIGURE 18 PERCEPTION OF HISTORICAL BUILDING AND STATE OF CONSERVATION OF THE HERIT4AGES IN WINTER.

5.3.5 FEUB Overall analysis

As an overall analysis, the users found that the thermal environment is neutral, and slightly acceptable in both seasons, and they don't feel the need to use additional clothes in wintertime. For the visual environment, they find it slightly dark or too dark also in both seasons, and with preference for the natural white light colour for electric lighting. The users said to feel comfortable with the acoustic environment, with no change, while for humidity they would prefer it drier. The air quality seems to be in a tight space of preference, as the users found it 'just acceptable' or 'just non-acceptable', while a very reduced number of occupants declared to feel the air indoors as 'clearly acceptable'. For many of them, opening the windows to clear the air seems necessary. In regard to the historical character of the building, they declared to feel 'indifferent', in overall finding the state of the building to be 'slightly deteriorated', the user's interviewed think that the building should be renovated to use less energy and also to stop its deterioration.

5.4 Residential building – Funchal, PT.

The survey in the residential building was applied in February 2024 for the winter session, on an overcast day, and was answered by only one person, a woman between 46-55 years old who is living there permanently. In summertime, the survey was answered in June 2024, in sunny conditions but some rain (20°C and 60% humidity) by the same person that answered in wintertime.

5.4.1 Demographic data and occupancy patterns

The user that answered the survey was a woman 46-55 years old, who is a permanent resident in the apartment.

5.4.2 Thermal and visual environment

Wintertime

She found the room 'neutral' in terms of thermal environment in morning hours (8am to 12pm), and so 'acceptable', but she would prefer it warmer, in the afternoon (12pm to 15pm) she finds it 'warm' and would prefer it 'warmer' and 'neutral' in the late afternoon (15pm to 18pm). For visual environment, she found it 'adequate' in the morning, afternoon and late afternoon, with 'no change' preferences, declaring the place to be 'sufficiently' naturally lit, and would prefer the electric light to be of a 'natural white' colour. For acoustics, she would prefer the place to be 'quieter' as noises come from the outside in the evening (from 19:00 pm to 4:00 am), she would prefer to have double glazing windows to fix the noise.

Summertime

During the survey in summertime, she declared to find the room to be 'warm' (1) in the morning (11:00 am), but still 'acceptable', she would prefer it 'cooler' (-1). In the afternoon (15:00 pm), with intermediate sky conditions and outdoor temperature of 22°C, humidity 70% she finds the room 'warm', 'slightly acceptable' and 'no change'. The late afternoon (18:00pm), similar conditions the room is found 'acceptable', but would prefer it 'cooler'. She doesn't feel the need to remove clothes to feel more comfortable, she sometimes needs to control the excessive heat by closing the movable blinds in the room. A comfortable temperature for her would be between 20°C to 30°C. For visual environment, she finds the room adequately lit, would prefer 'no change' in the afternoon and late-afternoon, also adequate, and 'no change'. She found the place to be sufficiently naturally lit and does not need to turn on the lights to feel more comfortable, she would prefer a natural white colour for the artificial light.

5.4.3 IEQ (humidity, air quality and acoustic).

Wintertime

The air quality environment is found 'just acceptable', but she feels the need to open the window to clear the air. The humidity in the environment feels also 'neutral' and 'no change' is preferred.

Summertime

For acoustic environment, she would prefer the room to be 'quieter' because of noises from the exterior in the evening time. The air environment feels 'sufficient' and sometimes she needs to open the windows to clean the air. The humidity, she found the place 'humid' and would prefer it to be 'drier', but she doesn't observe a permanent manifestation of humidity in the building.

5.4.4 Value and impact of the historic building from user's perspective

While she has been living in the place for about four years, she is not familiar with the history of the building. The user feels 'indifferent' to the historic character of the building, she has personal history with the building so her connection is 'emotional'. She thinks that the building is in a good state of conservation and feels that the building needs renovation for less energy use, she would agree with a permanent renovation.

5.4.5 Overall analysis

The user finds the thermal environment neutral, and acceptable, but would prefer it warmer, regarding visual environment, is adequate and there is no need to change, is sufficiently naturally lit. She would prefer it to be quieter as there are noises coming from the outside, the problem would be fixed using double glazing in the windows. The air quality is acceptable, but she feels the need to open the window to clean the air, the humidity is found as 'neutral'. She feels indifferent regarding the significance of the building in terms of history or architectural meaning, but she feels that is in a good state of conservation. The energy use is 'normal', and the user would prefer to have more energy efficient appliances or use less artificial light, to reduce the consumption.

6. Herit4ages demo site's accessibility Analysis

The content of this chapter is based on the work performed for T3.4 'Integration of the soft and hard measures and solutions for universal design in the project', which oversees the limitations and challenges for the implementation of Universal design principles.

6.1 Introduction

Integrating soft and hard measures in universal design project is essential for creating environments and products that are truly inclusive and accessible. This comprehensive approach (CEN-CENELEC 2019) [7] ensures that accessibility solutions address both physical and social barriers, leading to more sustainable and user-friendly outcomes. By engaging stakeholders, providing training and education, developing supportive policies, and continuously monitoring and evaluating progress, Herit4ages guidance will effectively integrate various measures in the Herit4ages Co-creation Toolkit. Understanding the soft and hard measures:

Soft measures refer to non-physical strategies and policies that support universal design. These include training, education, policy development, community engagement, and advocacy. Soft measures aim to change attitudes, increase awareness, and foster a culture of inclusivity and accessibility.

Hard measures, on the other hand, involve physical modifications and technological solutions that make environments and products accessible. These include architectural adjustments, installation of assistive technologies, and design features that accommodate a wide range of abilities and needs.

The abilities and characteristics of people change as they advance from childhood to old age and vary substantially among individuals in any age group (ISO / IEC 2014) [8]. Activity limitations and participation restrictions can be experienced by all people and can be the result of unsuccessful interaction between individuals with impairments or health conditions and barriers such as personal and environmental factors. Although some impairments are minor in nature, combinations of impairments can impose significant limitations, as is often the case in ageing.

Heritage4Age guidance emphasis on the implementation of UD approach (CEN-CENELEC, 2019)[7] throughout the entire organization of the specific Demo site, in all policies, processes, organizational activities, and strive to expand the scope of users in its products and services, taking into account the diversity of people, including older adults and people with disabilities. The UD approach focuses on accessibility and usability as efficiently as possible, at all stages of the lifecycle of products and services, including the interaction within the "comprehensive user chain." This Heritage4Age guidance will identify internal and external factors that are relevant to its purpose and strategic direction, which impact the UD approach:

- User needs, characteristics, abilities, and preferences,
- Feedback on existing products and services, particularly regarding their accessibility and usability, and the range of users they reach,
- The organization's reputation in terms of existing measures related to the range of users,
- Legal and regulatory commitments,
- Competitor activities,
- Functional factors provided by assistive technologies,
- Compatibility and interoperability with assistive technologies,
- Technological factors and changes/progress in technical capabilities,
- Supply chain capacity/procurement,
- Comprehensive chain of accessibility,
- Economic factors,
- Accessibility standards and guidelines which are applicable in the specific demo sites.

The Planned Criteria consists of the analysis, monitoring and control of the project's ongoing design work in the context of universal design, which assumes that the built environment should be accessed, understood and used to the greatest extent possible by all people regardless of their age, size, ability or disability. Universal design pays special attention to shaping an environment friendly to the elderly, blind, hearing and mobility -impaired people, as well as to neurodiverse users.

6.2 Users' needs in universal design principles.

The prime objective in designing, constructing and managing the accessible built environment is to ensure that it satisfies the diverse needs of all its intended users. Such an environment should reasonably satisfy the needs of any one individual without unreasonably compromising those of another. Every effort should be made to address constraints such as limitation of space, topography, conservation restrictions due to the historical values of the building. Designing to address and integrate the access requirements of all people, irrespective of their personal circumstances, as part of the mainstream design, and thus achieve an inclusive and accessible environment, is always preferable to designing separate or specific features.

Content of this report focuses on aspects:

- 1) how to get started with ensuring relevant stakeholders are part of the cultural heritage renovation process.
- 2) insight on how to engage individuals and groups in the process of design and development as a part of public participation.
- 3) how to design the final product including users' needs and universal design principles.

6.3 Method of implementation UD approach and extending the range of users.

The authors of the Guide for addressing accessibility in standards (ISO / IEC 2014)[8] defined 11 goals to be followed when determining user accessibility needs and defining requirements and recommendations in implementing design for all. These goals are:

- Suitability for the widest range of users,
- Conformity with user expectations,
- Support for individualization,
- Approachability,
- Perceivability,
- Understandability,
- Controllability,
- Usability,
- Error tolerance,
- Equitable use,
- Compatibility with other systems.

The Guide (ISO / IEC, 2014) identifies two complementary approaches to addressing accessibility in a specific standard:

— an accessibility goals approach, which can be used to identify user accessibility needs that can, in turn, be used to identify accessibility requirements and recommendations for a standardization project.

— a human abilities and characteristics approach, which can be used to identify design considerations that can, in turn, also be used to identify accessibility requirements and recommendations for a standardization project.

When the Universal Design (UD) approach has to be implemented in the organizational planning and process management, it shall be aligned with the following seven steps (CEN-CENELEC, 2019):

1. **Understanding the Context of the Organization:** This involves identifying the needs and expectations of stakeholders, including people with disabilities, and integrating a design-for-all approach within established systems and processes.
2. **Leadership, Policy, and Responsibilities:** Supporting the UD approach through leadership, policymaking, and assigning responsibilities to achieve accessibility outcomes.
3. **Planning Goals and How to Achieve Them:** Setting objectives and determining how to reach them in alignment with the UD approach.
4. **Organizing Support and Resources:** This includes gathering the necessary information and other resources needed to implement the UD approach and deliver accessibility outcomes.
5. **Processes to Meet User Requirements:** Developing processes to meet the requirements of users, including people with disabilities, and designing products and services across the comprehensive chain in accordance with the UD approach.
6. **Processes for Monitoring, Measuring, Analysing, and Evaluating:** Establishing processes to monitor, measure, analyse, and evaluate the effectiveness and correctness of the UD approach and its accessibility outcomes.
7. **Continuous Improvement of the UD Approach:** Regularly refining and enhancing the UD approach.

6.4 Tools applicable in the process of range of user's extending.

Activities that help to widen the diversity of users include (CEN-CENELEC, 2019):

- Providing multiple ways of presenting information and user interactions,
- Using solutions with fixed parameters that address the widest possible range of users,
- Minimizing unnecessary complexities,

- Eliminating unnecessary restrictions and obstacles in user interactions with services and products,
- Ensuring compatibility with assistive technologies,
- Conducting evaluations: of concepts, prototypes, specifications, compliance with specifications, and testing of products and services,
- Involving users as early as possible in the design and development process. Early user involvement is crucial to facilitate the identification of user needs, as later changes are more costly and time-consuming to implement,
- Identifying risks and opportunities in terms of accessibility in the comprehensive chain by identifying internal factors during presales, sales, and implementation, during installation and configuration, and during post-sales support,
- Applying accessibility and usability criteria concerning external suppliers.

6.5 Human abilities that imply on the design considerations.

Physical, sensory and mental, intellectual and cognitive abilities vary from person to person. Some differences can be heightened through age, social conditions, as a result from accident or illness. Disability can be temporarily or permanent or in transition. Different constraints are likely to be encountered when attempting to modify the Demo site's layout, structure of an existing building or external environment. However, the individual provisions shall be adopted as much as possible in order to develop the process to meet the requirements of users, including people with disabilities, and built – in the requirements and guidance into the comprehensive chain in accordance with the UD approach. In addressing the various need of users, the principal consideration depend on the specific abilities and factors (CEN-CENELEC, 2019):

1. Moving abilities – physical difficulties include walking, balance, handling, pulling, lifting and reaching.
2. Sensory abilities – are abilities by which the body perceived an external stimulus. They include sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste.
3. Mental abilities – include processes that are carried out in the mind of the individual. They include cognition, intellect, interpretation, learning and memory. To provide a usable environment for the population at large, all means of communication should have an immediate impact and be easily understood.
4. Accommodating the development of child
5. Accommodating ageing adults
6. Accommodating the diversity of stature
7. Accommodating the allergy or certain sensitivity

Demo sites face numerous challenges such as population growth/decrease, influx into the city, diversity of the population in terms of origin, socio-demographic characteristics, lifestyles, and managing open conflicts of values and interests among various individuals and groups. The model guiding in this report involves an

active co-creation by residents, where social participation ensures good conditions and involvement in Herit4Ages project's development.

When we speak of disability, we consider the relationship between a person's health (taking into account their age, gender, and education) and the society and environment that surrounds them. The World Health Organization (WHO) in the "International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF)" (2001) introduces the following concepts of disability, considering the health condition of a person:

1. **Impairment:** Any loss of function or abnormality in the structure or functioning of the body in psychological, psychophysical, or anatomical terms.
2. **Disability:** Any limitation or inability (resulting from impairment) to lead an active life in a manner or to an extent considered typical for a human being.
3. **Handicap:** The disadvantage experienced by a person resulting from impairment or disability, which limits or prevents the full realization of a social role that is appropriate to their age, gender, and in line with social and cultural conditions.

The social context of disability has been discussed in the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF), adopted during the World Health Assembly in 2001. This document emphasizes that disability affects all of humanity; it is not a problem that should be attributed solely to minority groups, as anyone can experience a deterioration in health and become disabled. According to the WHO (2022), a person with a disability is someone whose functional ability or life activities are impaired to the extent that it hinders their ability to perform roles deemed appropriate for them within their society. According to this definition, individuals considered disabled include:

- Individuals using wheelchairs,
- Individuals having difficulty moving independently without the use of assistive devices such as crutches, canes, walkers, etc.,
- Elderly individuals (over 60 years of age),
- Young children (under 5 years of age),
- Individuals suffering from arthritis, asthma, or heart conditions,
- Individuals with visual and/or hearing impairments,
- Individuals with personality disorders such as delirium or amnesia,
- Pregnant women,
- Individuals disabled due to substance abuse, including alcohol, cocaine, heroin, and psychotropic drugs,
- Individuals suffering from partial or total loss of voice,
- Contemporary and potentially future generations exposed to disability due to environmental pollution and/or irresponsible human actions regarding the environment and communities,

- Individuals who easily panic in situations such as fires or alarms,
- Individuals, including firefighters, who are injured during or as a result of a fire, poisoning from toxic substances, and/or exposure to high temperatures.

The following user classification defined in the EN 17161:2019 Design for All (CEN-CENELEC, 2019) standard indicates that each user has a profile of needs, characteristics, abilities, and preferences. For most of us, this profile changes multiple times throughout life, evolving from childhood through adulthood and into old age.

Diversity of different needs and possible problems with accessibility are presented for the main groups of users in the Table 2. Results of presented data show that diversity of different design solutions are needed concentrated on differentiation of possible senses needed to be used by user.

TABLE 7 DIVERSITY OF NEEDS FOR DIFFERENT USER'S GROUPS.

Users group	User needs and problems									
	Low vision	Hypersensitivity to visual stimulation	Low mobility	High need to move	Low muscle strength	Low hearing	Hypersensitivity to hearing stimulation	Low level of focus	Memory issues	Communication problems
Children				X	X				X	
Teenagers				X	X					
Adults										
Elderly	X		X		X	X		X	X	
Foreigner										X
Pregnant			X		X					
Blindness	X									
Low vision	X									
Speech disability										X
Physical and mobility disability			X		X					
Auditory						X				
Learning disabilities								X	X	X
Autism		X					X			X

6.6 Accessibility Analysis of Herit4ages demo sites.

6.6.1 Office room, Institute of Baltic Studies, Tartu Estonia

The universal design and barriers for the office room were assessed in Table 8.

TABLE 8 ANALYSIS OF THE OFFICE ROOM, INSTITUTE OF BALTIC STUDIES (IBS).

UNIVERSAL DESIGN SOLUTIONS AND MEASUREMENTS; ANALYSIS OF CHOSEN ROOMS IN BUILDINGS ON DEMO SITES IN THE CONTEXT OF LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING UNIVERSAL DESIGN PRINCIPLES
Demo-site and demo-site ID: Vironia Fraternity building, Institute of Baltic Studies (Tartu, Estonia), IBS
Room ID (classroom, office): offices – Room 1 and Room 2
Location: Lai 30, Tartu city, Estonia
Function/users: staff of 8 institutions (including Institute of Baltic Studies)
Regular occupancy: office building: 8 institutions, around 50 workers and 100 clients. In selected rooms: room 1 (404) 4 users, room 2 (405) 6 users
4th floor plan – SELECTED ROOMS numbers 404 (Room 1) and 405 (Room 2)
<p>Legend: Selected rooms Passage from staircase</p>
FIGURE 19 FLOOR PLAN OF THE SELECTED ROOM.

FIGURE 20 CLOSER VIEW OF THE SELECTED ROOM.

RELEVANT PHOTOS WITH DESCRIPTIONS

FIGURE 21 DIFFERENT VIEWS OF ROOM-1 (404).

Photo 1. Room 1 (404)

FIGURE 22 DIFFERENT VIEWS OF ROOM-2 (405).

Photo 2. Room 2 (405)

The two rooms are rectangular (walls have faults and niches), each with large double-leaf windows (room 1 – 3 windows; room 2 – 4 windows, all windows are the same size), starting about a meter above the floor. Both rooms are furnished with desks, chairs, shelves, and various decorations like wall art and potted plants. The ceiling height in both rooms is standard, around 2.5 to 3 meters. They receive ample natural

<p>light from the windows and have additional lighting from suspended linear fluorescent lights and string lights. The floors in both rooms are wooden, light brown, and arranged in a herringbone pattern, appearing smooth and even. The walls are light yellow, plain, and rather contrast with the white ceilings and window frames.</p>	
<p>CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM</p>	<p>EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN</p>
<p>General description of the access route from the main entrance to the building to the selected room (is the access adapted to the requirements of users with special needs)? A wide corridor (more than 2 meters wide) runs to selected rooms. To room 2 (office number 405) it is necessary to pass between columns where the minimum width is 110 cm. The corridor leads from the staircase which is vertical circulation in the building. There is no elevator in the building, and no information was provided as to whether the staircase is equipped to overcome the difference in level for people with limited mobility, but the documentation provided does not include this. According to the provided building documentation, the floor in the corridor and in the rooms is on the same level everywhere.</p>	<p>In general, the corridors and passageways are wide enough and have a comfortable surface and one level so are comfortable for users, including those with disabilities. The problem is the lack of an elevator. When an elevator is not available, several solutions can facilitate the transport of people with disabilities up and down stairs. It is recommended that any of these solutions be used in the analysed building. The best and most comfortable solution for people in wheelchairs is typically the platform lift:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclined Platform Lifts: These are similar to platform lifts but are designed to move along the angle of the stairs, carrying the wheelchair user and the wheelchair itself. • Stairlifts: These are motorized chairs that run on a track installed along the stairs. They can carry individuals who can transfer themselves or with minimal assistance from a wheelchair to the stairlift seat. • Portable Stair Climbers: These are devices that can be attached to a wheelchair, allowing it to be moved up and down stairs by a caregiver. They are portable and can be used in various locations.
<p>General description of the selected room geometry (shape, windows, doors, other openings and other features): Shape and Layout: The two rooms are rectangular (walls have faults and niches). Windows: there are large double-leaf windows in both rooms (room 1 – 3 windows; room 2 – 4 windows, all windows are the same size), starting about a meter above the floor; width x height – 110cm x ca. 165cm. Doors: One door leads to each room from the corridor. There is also one door between both rooms. However,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room is sufficiently large and ergonomically shaped to allow for a comfortable arrangement. Slight rearrangement of the space may be necessary to achieve a manoeuvring space of 150x150 cm (room 1, 404) • It seems that the arrangement of the rooms allows people with special needs (including wheelchair users) to manoeuvre between pieces of equipment (furniture). If

<p>judging by the furniture, which partially blocks access to these doors, they are not used on a daily basis.</p> <p>Additional Features: Both rooms are furnished with desks, chairs, shelves, and various decorations like wall art and potted plants. Each room has desks (office workstations) 4 in room 1 (404) and 6 in room 2 (405).</p>	<p>necessary, the arrangement of furniture can be rearranged to provide manoeuvring space at the entrance and at the workstation 150x150 cm and a passage of at least 120 cm.</p>
<p>Area and height of the room: the ceiling height appears to be standard, around 2.5 to 3 meters. Room 1 (404) 32,9m²; Room 2 (405) 36,8 m²</p>	
<p>Description of levels in the selected room (one level or more, level difference between the corridor/outdoor room and the selected room): According to the provided building documentation, the floor in the corridor and in the rooms is on the same level everywhere.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no difference in level either in the room or in the passages from the room to other rooms, which is optimal and convenient for all users.
<p>Orientation of the selected room in relation to the cardinal system (which sides of the world do the windows face?): The windows of both rooms face west, room 2 faces north, and room 1 faces south.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room receives ample natural light from the large windows. The inflow of sunlight from outside is controlled by red roller blinds.
<p>Size of doors in the selected room: According to the documentation, the door openings are 90 cm wide and 210 cm high. This means that the door's clear width is narrower.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For people with limited mobility, a clear door width of 90 cm (and a minimum of 85 cm) is recommended. If the building is modernized, it is recommended to replace the doors with wider ones.
<p>Colour and material of doors (frame) in the selected room, handle height and shape: no information provided</p>	<p>Recommendations for the door frame and handle in the room based on universal design principles, ensuring accessibility, safety, and aesthetic appeal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour: A colour that contrasts well with the light-yellow walls should be chosen to make the door easily identifiable for people with visual impairments. Darker colours like deep brown, charcoal, or navy blue can be provided for striking contrast. Alternatively, a bright colour such as bold red or green can also work well. • Material: Durable materials like solid wood or high-quality composite materials should be used. These materials are robust, provide good insulation, and can be easily maintained. • Height: According to universal design principles, door handles should be placed at

	<p>a height that is accessible to both standing and seated users. The standard recommended height for door handles is between 80 to 110/120 cm from the floor. A height of around 90 cm is commonly used and is considered comfortable for most users.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Shape</u>: Lever handles are preferred over round knobs because they are easier to use, especially for people with limited hand strength or dexterity. Lever handles can be operated using a closed fist, elbow, or even a hip, making them more accessible. • <u>Contrast</u>: It should be ensured that the door handle contrasts with the door colour to make it more visible.
<p>Size of windows and possibility to open them (height above the floor): The windows each have two handles, one about 110 cm above the floor, the other much higher.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If windows need to be opened, the mechanisms should be reachable for people of all heights and abilities. The upper opening height of the window (handle) is too high and should be changed to a lower position (between 80 and 110 cm above floor level) when replacing the windows or the opening mechanism.
<p>Description of lighting in the selected room: The room receives ample natural light from the large windows. There are suspended linear fluorescent lights running along the ceilings in both rooms. The lights are evenly spaced, providing balanced illumination.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizontal and vertical surfaces in the selected room of the building are well-lit by the windows and light fittings. The windows have roller blinds to prevent too much sunlight, the spacing of lighting fixtures allow for even light distribution. Light source is positioned high enough to reduce glare. • Fluorescent lights should be well-maintained to avoid flickering, which can be discomforting or problematic for some individuals. • Adequate lighting is crucial to help visually impaired individuals navigate the room. It must be ensured all lights are functional and provide even illumination without creating harsh shadows.
<p>Position of light switches in the selected room: no information provided</p>	<p>In the context of universal design, the position of light switches in a room should adhere to the following requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Height</u>: Light switches should be installed at a height that is accessible to both standing

	<p>and seated users. The recommended height is typically between 80 cm and 110 cm from the floor. A common height is around 110 cm, which accommodates the majority of users, including those in wheelchairs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location: Light switches should be located near room entrances, both inside and outside of the room, to allow easy access when entering or exiting. Ideally, they should be placed within 12 to 24 inches (30 to 61 cm) of the door frame. • Visibility and Contrast: Light switches should have a contrasting colour or texture to the wall to make them easily identifiable for individuals with visual impairments. • Type of Switch: Rocker or paddle switches are preferred over traditional toggle switches. These types are easier to use for individuals with limited hand strength or dexterity. They can be operated on with a closed fist, elbow, or even by leaning against them. • Lighting: it may be considered to use illuminated switches or switches with backlighting to improve visibility in low-light conditions. This feature is particularly useful for individuals with visual impairments. • Clear Space: it must be ensured that there is clear space around the switch to allow easy access. Avoid placing switches behind furniture or other obstacles that could impede access. • Smart Controls: Implementing smart lighting controls can offer additional accessibility. Voice-activated or app-controlled switches allow individuals to operate lighting without needing to physically interact with the switch.
<p>Suspended/elevated/protruding elements in the selected room: Linear fluorescent light fixtures are suspended from the ceiling. The desks and shelves protrude slightly into the room space but are arranged to allow easy movement.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elements are installed correctly and do not pose a risk to people with special needs are not a barrier to the daily use of the room.

<p>Floor in selected room (material, colour, contrast, pattern, slip/non-slip floor, even/ uneven etc.): <u>Material:</u> wooden parquet <u>Colour and pattern:</u> natural wood colour; the wood is arranged in a herringbone pattern. <u>Slipperiness:</u> the wood floor is smooth but not slippery. The floor is even and well-maintained.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The flooring in both rooms is both comfortable and safe. • Generally good for wheelchairs as the hard surface allows for easy rolling. • The flat and hard surface is suitable for use with canes, walkers, and other mobility aids.
<p>Walls in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast): <u>Material and colour:</u> bricks, plastered, light yellow. The walls are plain without any visible pattern. There is a slight contrast between the light-yellow walls and the white window frames and ceiling.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plain walls can sometimes cause echoes in a large room. Adding elements like wall panels, bulletin boards, or acoustic treatments can help in reducing noise levels. • There is no significant colour contrast between the walls and the floor. Recommended more contrast between wall and floor colour if renovating or installing wall panels.
<p>Ceiling in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast): <u>Material:</u> plaster <u>Colour:</u> white, plain, no visible pattern <u>Lighting:</u> There are suspended linear fluorescent lights running along the ceiling.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ceilings of the rooms are designed to be functional, providing necessary lighting. By ensuring regular maintenance and considering potential upgrades for improved energy efficiency and acoustic comfort, the ceiling can continue to support a safe and comfortable environment for all users.
<p>Information boards and tactile maps: no information provided</p>	<p>Universal design requirements for information boards and tactile maps in an office or office building:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Accessible Height:</u> Information boards should be installed at a height that is easily reachable for both standing and seated users. The centre of the board should be approximately 120 to 150 cm from the floor. • <u>Location:</u> Place information boards in prominent, easily accessible locations such as near entrances, lobbies, elevators, and other high-traffic areas. • <u>Visibility and Contrast:</u> high-contrast colours must be used for text and background to ensure readability for individuals with visual impairments. • <u>Readable Fonts:</u> large, sans-serif fonts such must be used. • <u>Clear Language:</u> simple, concise language that is easy to understand should be used.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Braille and Tactile Elements: it's recommended to include Braille translations of all essential information. Braille should be positioned below or alongside the printed text. • Raised Characters: it's also recommended to use raised characters for text to aid individuals who read by touch. • Logical Layout: information should be arranged in a logical and clear manner. • Icons and Graphics: universally recognized icons and graphics to supplement text and convey information visually should be used. • Adequate Lighting: information boards must be well-lit without creating glare. <p>Tactile Maps: tactile maps should be installed at a height that allows wheelchair users and standing users to easily reach and read them, the recommended height is 90 to 120 cm from the floor to the centre of the map, tactile maps should be located near entrances and other key points where users need directional information.</p>
<p>Possibility for a person with reduced mobility or who is visually impaired to move around the chosen room (issue of obstacles, width of passageways, possibility of changing direction, guidance elements):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tables and chairs (workstations) are arranged in such a way that this space, which was once designed for other purposes (the building is old, heritage), can be arranged as efficiently as possible for the needs of the office. • There are no tactile orientation paths in the room. There are no specific solutions in the room to make orientation easier. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It seems that the arrangement of the rooms allows people with special needs (including wheelchair users) to manoeuvre between pieces of equipment (furniture). If necessary (room 1, 404), the arrangement of furniture can be rearranged to provide manoeuvring space at the entrance and at the workstation 150x150 cm and a passage of at least 120 cm. • There are no specific solutions in the room to make orientation easier, but they can be easily introduced if needed.
<p>Adaptation of furniture and furnishings to the needs of impaired persons:</p> <p>Both rooms are furnished with desks, chairs, shelves, and various decorations like wall art and potted plants. Each room has desks (office workstations) 4 in room 1 (404) and 6 in room 2 (405).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room appears to have sufficient space to manoeuvre (manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m) a wheelchair or mobility device, including turning and changing direction, and to drive to the chosen seat at the table. Changes in the arrangement of the space are possible, if necessary. • The standard height of tables is suitable for most users but may need adjustments for wheelchair accessibility in some cases.

An induction loop or other devices for the hearing impaired: no information provided	not applicable
Is an evacuation plan posted in a clearly visible place in the room? no information provided	-

SUMMARY - PANEL REQUIREMENTS

CEILING PANELS:

Material: Materials should be chosen that are durable, easy to clean, and have sound-absorbing properties. Easy-to-clean and maintain materials should be selected, avoiding materials prone to moisture absorption or mold growth. A finish that complements the existing room decor should be chosen. Panels are available in various colours, textures, and patterns.

Placement and Installation: when installing the panels, it is important to remember that they should be easily removable in case of any upgrades to the main walls (for example, installation running in the ceiling structure).

Access to ceiling fixtures (lighting) and other utilities must be maintained. Removable panels or access hatches should be installed as needed. Mounting lighting should be changed.

WALL PANELS:

Material: Materials should be chosen that are durable, easy to clean, and have sound-absorbing properties, such as acoustic foam or fabric-covered panels.

Colour and Contrast, surface: Contrast colours should be used to aid visually impaired individuals. Light-coloured panels with dark borders can help in defining the space better. Attention should be paid to the contrast between the panels and the floor. Textured surfaces may be incorporated to provide tactile feedback for individuals with visual impairments.

Placement and Installation:

It must be ensured that panels do not cover or obstruct important features such as:

- When installing the panels, it is important to remember that they should be easily removable in case of any upgrades to the main walls (for example, installation ruining in the walls).
- Emergency Exits and Signs: Panels should be installed without covering them. Contrast colours should be used around exits and signs to enhance visibility.
- Fire Extinguishers and Safety Equipment: Panels should be cut to fit around these items or items should be fixed to panels in a safe way, ensuring they remain easily accessible.
- Power Outlets and Switches: Panels should not block access to electrical outlets or light switches. These areas should be marked clearly if they are embedded in the panels.

Mounting Height and place: panels must be at a height that does not interfere with the general use of the room. The reach of individuals in wheelchairs or those with limited mobility must be considered. Panels must not block or restrict movement and manoeuvring space.

Continuous Surface: It must be ensured that panels provide a continuous surface, avoiding gaps that could catch on clothing or mobility aids.

Acoustic Considerations:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound Absorption: Panels should be strategically positioned to reduce noise and echo in the room. Areas behind and around speaking areas, such as the front where the projector screen is located, are ideal. • It's better if panels are spread evenly across the room to provide uniform sound absorption. <p><u>Tactile Indicators:</u> It is recommended to add tactile markers or signs to assist visually impaired users in navigating the space if panel are located along the path/passage.</p> <p><u>Additional Features:</u> Integrated Whiteboards/Bulletin Boards: Panels may be combined panels with functional elements like whiteboards or bulletin boards for multipurpose use.</p>
FLOOR PANELS: not applicable
FINAL COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both rooms are not accessible to people with limited mobility mainly due to the lack of an elevator in the building. Other elements of the interior allow people with different needs to use them, possibly changes that do not generate special costs (such as changing the location of furniture) are possible. (see EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN column above). • In the selected room, wall panels will be installed as part of the ongoing project, so the final recommendations are consistent with the recommendations for panels detailed above (see "SUMMARY - PANEL REQUIREMENTS")

6.6.2 Posada Santa Maria la Real, Palencia, Spain

The universal design and barriers for the hotel-room demo site were assessed in Table 9.

TABLE 9 ANALYSIS OF THE HOTEL-ROOM, POSADA SANTA MARIA LA REAL, AGUILAR DE CAMPOO, SPAIN

<u>UNIVERSAL DESIGN SOLUTIONS AND MEASUREMENTS; ANALYSIS OF CHOSEN ROOMS IN BUILDINGS ON DEMO SITES IN THE CONTEXT OF LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING UNIVERSAL DESIGN PRINCIPLES</u>
Demo-site and demo-site ID: Posada Santa Maria la Real - FMS Heritage Living Lab
Room ID (classroom, office): Hotel room nr 18
Location: Aguilar de Campoo, Spain
Function/users: hotel /guests & hotel service
Regular occupancy: max 3 people: 1 person (single bed) and 2 people (double bed on mezzanine)

TECHNICAL DRAWINGS WITH DESCRIPTIONS

Building plan with location of selected room marked (drawing):

FIGURE 23 BUILDING PLAN OF SELECTED ROOM.

RELEVANT PHOTOS WITH DESCRIPTIONS

FIGURE 24 STEP AT THE ENTRANCE DOOR ON GROUND FLOOR.

FIGURE 25 ROOM NUMBER ON THE OUTSIDE OF ROOM.

FIGURE 26 VIEW OF THE MAIN CORRIDOR.

Artificial light and daylight in the main corridor are not enough to light up all the space. Structural elements are not flashed with walls and ceiling and especially on vertical surfaces they can hurt people with low vision.

FIGURE 27 BATHROOM INTERIOR VIEW, WALL LIGHT AND GLASS DOORS WITH GEOMETRY PATTERN.

FIGURE 28 INTERIOR VIEW OF BATHROOM, WHICH IS NOT ACCESSIBLE.

FIGURE 29 MAIN ACCESS TO THE ROOM.

FIGURE 30 INTERIOR VIEW OF THE WINDOW IN THE HOTEL ROOM.

FIGURE 31 VIEW FROM THE MEZZANINE AREA OF THE ROOM.

Structural elements are visible on the ceiling, which are not aligned with the surface of ceiling.

FIGURE 32 VIEW TOWARDS THE MEZZANINE.

FIGURE 33 MEZZANINE AREA SHOWING THE DOUBLE BED.

FIGURE 34 INTERNAL STAIRS TO THE MEZZANINE.

FIGURE 35 INTERIOR VIEW OF THE ROOM.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM	EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN
<p>1. General description of the access route from the main entrance to the building to the selected room (is the access adapted to the requirements of users with special needs)?</p>	
<p>Ramp to cross the threshold before the entrance to the plot. External pavement could be problematic for people with disabilities. No tactile information on the floor (path to the reception desk and hotel rooms) and tactile model of building are available. Access to the hotel rooms is not served via main entrance and reception desk. Selected room is located on the first floor. Access to the first floor is only possible by external stairs. Handrails are too short. No lift or platform is available. No threshold to the room. No tactile information is provided. Door to the first floor has only 0.8 m wide in clearness (within the door frame). Wide of corridors is too small for easy rotate the wheelchair in most of the length of it. Timber, old floor and painted white, finished with plaster walls. Radiator hanged on the</p>	<p>If the connection through the main entrance to the building and reception desk because of the protection of the heritage to the external stairs should be added lift or platform to make it accessible. Lift or platform should have a control panel with multisensorial information and intuitively designed. Tactile information should be added on handrail. Tactile plan should be added next to the main entrance and on each of the floors next to the entrance. Ramp could be bigger. Pavement needs checking. Specific requirements will be shown in wp4. Doors wide measured within the door frame should be at least 0.9 m wide and a minimum height of 2.0 m. Strength needed to open a door should be checked on site.</p>

<p>wall makes wide of corridor smaller. Roof framing elements are painted in dark brown. No threshold to the room. No lift or platform is available. No tactile information is provided. Ramp to cross the threshold before the entrance to the plot. External pavement could be problematic for people with disabilities. Door to the first floor has only 0.8 m wide in clearness (within the door frame). Wide of corridors is too small for easy rotate the wheelchair. Main entrance is not clearly recognisable, because there are more doors than one. Entrance is not specially underlined. No tactile information in the pavement.</p>	
<p>2. General description of the selected room geometry (shape, windows, doors, other openings and other features)</p>	
<p>Room is L shaped with private bathroom. Above the bathroom and internal corridor is located mezzanine. In the room are visible timber structural elements painted white which are decreasing the hight and wide of the room in some areas (are not flashed with walls and ceiling). Windows are located on the wall on opposite side to the entrance to the room.</p>	<p>Structural elements which are not flashed with the wall should be underlined with the contrast colour. All furniture should be placed in the way to increase accessibility.</p>
<p>Bathroom is shaped as rectangular. Posts are decreasing dimensions of bathroom in some places. Sloping ceiling. No windows. Doors from the internal corridor.</p>	<p>No space for moving the wheelchair. No accessible facilities are added in the room.</p>
<p>3. Area and height of the room</p>	
<p>Total hotel room area without mezzanine: 13,0 m²</p>	<p>Total hotel room area can be increased by attaching 2,4 m² to room from corridor.</p>
<p>Total hotel room area with mezzanine: 17,7 m²</p>	
<p>Usable hotel room area without mezzanine: 12,6 m²</p>	
<p>Usable hotel room area with mezzanine: 17,3 m²</p>	
<p>Usable room area: 10,5 m²</p>	<p>It is possible to increase room area by adding 1,6 m² to the room from corridor.</p>
<p>Usable bathroom area: 2,1 m²</p>	<p>Too small to make it fully accessible. It is possible to make bathroom bigger by adding minimum 0,8 m² of area from corridor.</p>
<p>Usable mezzanine area: 4,7 m²</p>	<p>Usable mezzanine area could be increased by increasing room area.</p>
<p>Total height of the room net: 3,69 m</p>	<p>Post and purlin level could be too low from some users. Those elements if they are not</p>
<p>Minimum height of the room net: 2,34 m</p>	
<p>Maximum height of the room net: 3,69 m</p>	

Maximum height of the room to the roof frame elements net: 3,54 m	flushed with the wall should be underlined with the contrast colour.
Height of post and localisation of purlin net: 1,89 m	
Minimum height of the mezzanine net: 0,91 m	Mezzanine is too low for normal usable. It can be used only as a sleeping area. It won't be accessible.
Maximum height of the mezzanine net: 1,59 m	
Maximum height of the mezzanine to the roof frame elements net: 1,43 m	
Minimum height of the bathroom net: 2,20 m	Height of the bathroom is correct.
Maximum height of the bathroom net: 3,00 m	
4. Description of levels in the selected room (one level or more, level difference between the corridor/outdoor room and the selected room)	
Room with low high mezzanine accessible only by stairs. Access not possible for people with low mobility. No threshold and differences of levels between the hotel corridor and internal corridor and bathroom are visible.	If it is possible in room should be skipped mezzanine or should be added platform and height of mezzanine should be increased. Without platform mezzanine won't be accessible. Small hight of mezzanine could be problematic for users with special needs.
5. Orientation of the selected room in relation to the cardinal system (which sides of the world do the windows face?)	
Room has only one external wall with windows. Windows of room are facing south.	The proportions of glazed elevation and non-glazed should be checked to protect room against overheating. Heat capacity of used construction materials should be checked to protect room against overheating. Shading analysis should be done to check possibility of overheating and possibility because of small eaves. For make it more accessible maybe air conditioning should be used or other solutions to increase air movement or technical solutions for external shading system or special glazing protecting against overheating.
6. Size of doors in the selected room	
The wide of the doors in the clearness to the room and bathroom is less than 80 cm.	Measured within the door frame, at least 0.9 m wide and a minimum height of 2.0 m, for double doors, is the movable leaf at least 0.9 m wide.
7. Size, colour and material of doors (frame) in the selected room, handle height and shape	
No contrast of the door frame to the finishing of walls in the corridor and inside the hotel room.	Contrast colour of frame and walls should be used.
8. Size of windows and possibility to open them (height above the floor):	
No contrast of the windows frame to the finishing of walls in the corridor and inside the hotel room.	Ceiling structure should be also marked in contrast colour because of the low high.

<p>Ceiling structure should be also marked in contrast colour because of the low high.</p>	
<p>9. Description of lighting in the selected room</p>	
<p>Lightening in the room and bathroom is not good visible. Materials on the walls make room brighter but without too much of reflection surfaces.</p>	<p>Horizontal and vertical surfaces in the selected room of the building should be well-lit and does the spacing of lighting fixtures allow for even light distribution. All poorly lit areas should be changed.</p>
<p>10. Position of light switches in the selected room</p>	
<p>No data.</p>	<p>Light switches in the building should be positioned at a height of 0.8-1.1 m.</p>
<p>11. Suspended/elevated/protruding elements in the selected room</p>	
<p>Post is not flashed with the walls.</p>	<p>Suspended (under 2,2 m), protruding elements such as technical equipment housings, display cases should be positioned and secured to not pose a threat to blind or visually impaired individuals by adding contrast colour and kerb strip on the floor level (or covered with the furniture).</p>
<p>12. Floor in selected room (material, colour, contrast, pattern, slip/non-slip floor, even/ uneven etc.)</p>	
<p>Wooden parquet floor in the contrast with colour of the walls. Main pattern crosses, underlined windows and doors area with horizontal pattern.</p>	<p>The properties of slip resistance should be checked on site.</p>
<p>In bathroom are used dark, timber like tiles. The contrast is visible between the floor, wall and facilities.</p>	<p>The properties of slip resistance should be checked on site including shower tray.</p>
<p>13. Walls in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast)</p>	
<p>Wall finished with white, internal plaster. Contrast colour with the floor finishing. No additional elements on the walls expect radiator, mirror and wall sconce (lamp in contrast colour).</p>	<p>Structural elements that extend beyond the wall or ceiling surface at a height of up to 2.20 m should be marked in a contrasting manner.</p>
<p>14. Ceiling in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast)</p>	
<p>Ceiling made from wood with visible historical timber, structural elements which need preservation. All elements painted white.</p>	<p>Structural elements that extend beyond the wall or ceiling surface at a height of up to 2.20 m should be marked in a contrasting manner.</p>
<p>15. Information boards and tactile maps</p>	
<p>No tactile information or information written in Braille with the room number and in the room. No information boards and tactile maps illustrating the most important elements of the room and the layout of each floor's spatial functionality provided.</p>	<p>No tactile information or information written in Braille with the room number and in the room. I No information boards and tactile maps illustrating the most important elements of the</p>

<p>No symbols and infographics are used to indicate basic facility functions and directions. Background is not readable. Frame could be in contrast colour.</p>	<p>room and the layout of each floor's spatial functionality provided. Information boards should be placed at a height of 1.2 - 1.6 m. Sans-serif fonts, such as Arial, Helvetica, or Verdana should be used in the written text, with both uppercase and lowercase letters. No symbols and infographics are used to indicate basic facility functions and directions. All written, lettered, and graphic markings should be contrasted in colour with the background (LRV60). Sufficiently large font size should be used (minimum text height of 15 mm, calculated based on the formula: $HT = 0.02-0.03 \times L$, where HT represents the text height, and L represents the distance from the text).</p>
<p>16. Possibility for a person with reduced mobility or who is visually impaired to move around the chosen room (issue of obstacles, width of passageways, possibility of changing direction, guidance elements)</p>	
<p>Low possibility of movement. Circulation possible in the middle of room if furniture position will be changed. No possibility of movement for person with reduced mobility in the bathroom.</p>	<p>Manoeuvring space with minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 m. In the room should be a manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m near the entrance that is also used to access the door. Directional signs and floor markings should be visible and legible. Arrangement and layout of tables and seating should be changed to allow mobility by a person in a wheelchair. In a room should be at least one of the seat designated for wheelchair users or should be a place for wheelchair (the dimension of the space allocated for a person in a wheelchair must not be less than 0.9 x 1.4 m.).</p>
<p>17. Adaptation of furniture and furnishings to the needs of impaired persons</p>	
<p>Localisation of furniture doesn't allow to have right manoeuvring area. Desk is blocking the area. Bed is accessible from one side. Mezzanine is not accessible. Bathroom no accessible. Accessible facilities are needed.</p>	<p>Manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m near the conference table, near the work desk and in the bathroom. The seated workstation should provide free space under the desk (height x width x depth) min. 0.70 m x 0.90 m x 0.60 m. Bed should be</p>

	<p>accessible from minimum 1 side (good practice from 2).</p> <p>An integrated power strip should be above the desk.</p> <p>The desktop at a height of 0.7 - 0.8 meters.</p> <p>Additional access to electrical outlets from the desk levels should also been provided in the work areas, conference rooms.</p> <p>Bathroom facilities should be placed on accessible hight and with the accessible facilities. Alarm should be added in room and bathroom to increase the safety.</p>
18. An induction loop or other devices for the hearing impaired	
No. TV should have a possibility with adding subtitles with description or signed language.	The conference/auditorium room/ meeting room should be equipped with fixed induction loops or other devices for the hearing impaired.
19. Is an evacuation plan posted in a clearly visible place in the room?	
Yes, but not as a tactile information. Probably no provision been made for evacuating the building for people with disabilities. The width of collision-free evacuation accesses and accessible evacuation routh are too small.	Elements of evacuation should be improved according to accessibility guidelines.
20. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION (SPECIFIC TO THE SELECTED ROOM)	
Curtains ad drapers could not be accessible and easy to move because of the placement of the furniture. Wardrobe should be check according to the accessibility. Some fitting as handrail should be added for elderly people. Accessibility of radiator should be checked.	
SUMMARY - PANEL REQUIREMENTS	
<p>CEILING PANELS:</p> <p><u>Material:</u> Materials should be chosen that are durable, easy to clean, and have sound-absorbing properties. Easy-to-clean and maintain materials should be selected, avoiding materials prone to moisture absorption or mold growth. A finish that complements the existing room decor should be chosen. Panels are available in various colours, textures, and patterns. Panels should be easy cleaned, non-dusting, non-allergenic. With possibility to add colour if needed.</p> <p><u>Dimensions:</u> Thickness not bigger than 4,5 cm – mezzanine is not accessible but because of the low height it could be not usable with thicker panels. In other parts of the room panels could have a thickness of at most 12 cm (depending on the thickness of structural elements).</p>	

Placement and Installation: when installing the panels, it is important to remember that they should be easily removable in case of any upgrades to the main walls (for example, installation running in the ceiling structure). Because of the aesthetic and historic value is not recommended to cover the ceiling. It will be best to put insulation panels on the top of rafters (external side of roof structural elements) or use transparent materials or shaped panels (but original value of historic elements could be destroyed). It is not recommended to cover the timber finishing of the ceiling. Consider the possibility of introducing panels on the ceiling of the mezzanine floor.

Access to ceiling fixtures (lighting) and other utilities must be maintained. Removable panels or access hatches should be installed as needed. Lightening should be changed.

WALL PANELS:

Material: Materials should be chosen that are durable, easy to clean, and have sound-absorbing properties, such as acoustic foam or fabric-covered panels. Panels should be easy cleaned, non-dusting, non-allergenic. With possibility to add colour if needed.

Dimensions: Thickness not bigger than 5 cm – mezzanine is not accessible but because of thickness of structural elements in the wall. Because of the aesthetic and historic value at most it should be flashed with the surface of the post.

Colour and Contrast, surface: Textured surfaces may be incorporated to provide tactile feedback for individuals with visual impairments. Panels should be done in neutral colours.

Placement and Installation:

It must be ensured that panels do not cover or obstruct important features such as:

- The historic value of the structure extended from the wall. Panels should not cover them.
- Installation of the panels should not destroy the historic value of post (probably it should be joined).
- When installing the panels, it is important to remember that they should be easily removable in case of any upgrades to the main walls (for example, installation ruining in the walls).
- Emergency Exits and Signs: Panels should be installed without covering them. Contrast colours should be used around exits and signs to enhance visibility.
- Fire Extinguishers and Safety Equipment: Panels should be cut to fit around these items or items should be fixed to panels in a safe way, ensuring they remain easily accessible.
- Power Outlets and Switches: Panels should not block access to electrical outlets or light switches. These areas should be marked clearly if they are embedded in the panels.

Height and Reach:

The maximum height of the panels to touch structural elements of roof and lintels, beams. Do not cover structural elements.

Mounting Height and place: panels must be at a height that does not interfere with the general use of the room. The reach of individuals in wheelchairs or those with limited mobility must be considered. Panels must not block or restrict movement and manoeuvring space.

Continuous Surface: It must be ensured that panels provide a continuous surface, avoiding gaps that could catch on clothing or mobility aids. There should not be any possibility to keep dust.

Acoustic Considerations:

- Sound Absorption: Panels should be strategically positioned to reduce noise and echo in the room. Areas behind and around speaking areas, such as the front where the projector screen is located, are ideal.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's better if panels are spread evenly across the room to provide uniform sound absorption. <p><u>Tactile Indicators:</u> It is recommended to add tactile markers or signs to assist visually impaired users in navigating the space if panel are located along the path/passage.</p> <p><u>Additional Features:</u> There should be possibility to add the handrail to the panels to help elderly people in movement.</p>
<p>FLOOR PANELS:</p> <p>It is not recommended to add floor panels on the main level of the room because of the historic and aesthetic value of the floor. It is recommended to add panels on the mezzanine floor.</p> <p><u>Materials:</u> According to protection of historic value used materials should be transparent or added below the historic finishing of the floor. The materials used should be non-slip, abrasion-resistant, with high sound insulation, hard, durable, with tactile elements if possible. Wedge ramps should be added where the threshold is not used. Panels should be easy cleaned, non-dusting, non-allergenic. With possibility to add colour if needed.</p> <p><u>Dimensions:</u> Height at most to the level of the thresholds if they are. If any panels on the floor will be added if the thresholds are not placed high of the doors should be checked (maybe they should be cut) and on the external part should be added wedge ramps to make it accessible. Because of it panels should be not thicker than 2 cm to minimize the impact. Hight of the door should be checked to specify the dimensions. If it wants to be possible to use transparent material with placing on the original floor the pavement and placement of the elements should be done the same pattern.</p> <p><u>Tactile Indicators:</u> It is recommended to add tactile markers or signs to assist visually impaired users in navigating the space if panel are located along the path/passage.</p> <p><u>Colour and Contrast, surface:</u> Textured surfaces may be incorporated to provide tactile feedback for individuals with visual impairments. Panels should be made in the contrast colour.</p> <p><u>Placement and Installation:</u> If panels are placed under the existing finishing of floor should be combined with the original wood panels as a finishing layer. Shapes should be the same as pattern. If the placement will do with elements added on existing finishing should be done in the way not to destroy the historic finishing and expose it. To add floor panels on the mezzanine it is recommended to replace structural board finishing with the new panel because of the low height of the mezzanine. In this case some ribs could be added in the structure of panels which will be connected with the beams and structure of the mezzanine (in parts with ribs thickness of the panels can be thicker then approximately 22,5 cm (depends on the height of the structural beams/purlin etc.). With adding panels on the mezzanine, it is important to flash the surface with the finishing of last step.</p> <p><u>Additional Features:</u> There should be a possibility to add to the panels some vertical elements or barriers to mark elements which are below 2 m height and could be dangerous for visually impaired people.</p>
<p>FINAL COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:</p>
<p>Room is not accessible. Room and bathroom should be redesigned to make it accessible.</p>
<p>Building is not accessible. Recommendations will be provided in next WP.</p>
<p>Because of the historic value of timber structural elements visible on the walls and ceiling it is not recommended to cover it. Also, the historic floor should not be covered.</p>

6.6.3 Classroom, Faculty of Engineering – Bologna, Italy

The universal design solutions and barriers were assessed in Table 10.

TABLE 10 ANALYSIS OF THE CLASSROOM, UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA.

UNIVERSAL DESIGN SOLUTIONS AND MEASUREMENTS; ANALYSIS OF CHOSEN ROOMS IN BUILDINGS ON DEMO SITES IN THE CONTEXT OF LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTING UNIVERSAL DESIGN PRINCIPLES
Demo-site and demo-site ID: University of Bologna (Building of School of Engineering and Architecture) UNIBO
Room ID (classroom, office): AULA 04 large classroom (auditorium)
Location: Viale del Risorgimento 2, 40128, Bologna (Italy)
Function/users: Higher Education Building/students and lecturers
Regular occupancy: yes; capacity (seating) 64, seating for non-frontal lectures 128
FIGURE 36 BUILDING PLAN WITH LOCATION, THE SELECTED ROOM IS MARKED.

FIGURE 37 FLOOR PLAN OF THE SELECTED ROOM, CLOSED VIEW.

RELEVANT PHOTOS WITH DESCRIPTIONS

FIGURE 38 SELECTED ROOM IN THE FEUB DEMO SITE WITH ENTRANCES MARKED.

Entrance A is the main entrance for students, leads to the corridor; entrance B leads to the other corridor (there are academic staff offices in this part of the building); entrance C leads to the adjacent room where the library is located but this entrance is not used on a daily basis; entrance D leads directly outside but is also not used for daily use.

FIGURE 39 VIEW OF ENTRANCE -A.

Entrance A is a two-wing door, the wider wing when opened leaves a clear opening of approximately 85 cm, the other part can also be opened, which widens the door clear width to around 120 cm. Entrance A has a panic door - corridor side traditional handle, classroom side - panic push bar (easy to open). There is no threshold or level difference between the rooms.

FIGURE 40 INTERIOR AND EXTERIOR VIEWS OF ENTRANCE 'D'.

Entrance D leads directly to the outside. It has two wings of equal size which, when opened, have a clear width of at least 2 meters. Entrance D has a panic door - outside traditional handle, classroom side - panic push bar (easy to open). There is a slight difference in level between the room and the outside pavement.

FIGURE 41 INTERIOR VIEWS OF THE SELECTED ROOM SHOWING THE FURNITURE ARRANGEMENT.

Equipment and arrangement of the selected room:

- structural column in the middle of the room
- typical grid suspended ceiling with integrated lighting and ventilation elements
- plaster walls with surface-mounted electrical installation
- ceramic tile floor
- barred metal windows
- furnishings: desks, chairs, teacher's desk, blackboards, overhead projector, screen, curtains, wall-mounted fire extinguishers, radiators under windows

The arrangement of the space (mainly tables/work desk and chairs) is logical and simple. The distances between tables are considerable and generally about minimum 1.00 meter (or more). In some places, access to the window is partly restricted by the positioning of desks. Seated workstation provides free space under the desk (height x width x depth) min. 0.70 m x 0.90 m x 0.60.

A structural column in the middle of the room narrows the aisle between the rows of desks and can limit the view from the back desks.

FIGURE 42 INTERIOR VIEW OF WINDOW IN THE FEUB DEMO SITE ROOM.

As shown, the possibility of opening windows is relatively high, more than 130 cm from the floor.

FIGURE 43 DETAIL OF LIGHT SWITCHES IN THE ROOM.

As shown in the picture, the light switches and electrical contacts are approximately 80cm above the floor.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM	EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN
<p>General description of the access route from the main entrance to the building to the selected room (is the access adapted to the requirements of users with special needs)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Look at Building plan with location of selected room marked) There is no fully covered passage on the ground floor that leads from the main entrance to the room. Usually, users enter through the main entrance, walk down the main corridor until they reach the courtyard, and from there they access the room (see the path marked in red). Alternatively, others enter directly through the secondary entrance of the lot (path in blue). If you want to get 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The fact that it is not possible inside the building to get directly from the main entrance to the chosen room by taking a straightforward and intuitive route must be assessed negatively, especially in the context of not always good weather. At the same time, people in wheelchairs cannot do this at all because there is no lift in the part of the building where

<p>to the room from the main entrance without going outside, you need to follow the route: going up to the first floor and then coming back down to the ground floor using the staircase next to the selected room. There is no elevator in this part of the building.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The main corridor running from the main entrance to the building (like the other corridors) is wide (more than 150 cm), with no changes in level a single story, with a smooth floor surface (stone or tiles). The width of the corridor is locally limited by structural columns. Fixtures are located along the walls and radiators in niches. The haphazard placement of waste bins of various shapes and sizes can be a hindrance. 	<p>the selected room is located (so it is not possible to go up to the first floor and back down to the ground floor, which people using the staircase can do).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrance to the Herit4Ages classroom is guaranteed through access from a mixed pedestrian and vehicle road or from an internal cobblestone courtyard, which does not make it easy for users with special needs to move. There are no tactile orientation paths in the building. In general, the corridors and passageways are wide enough and have a comfortable surface and one level so are comfortable for users, including those with disabilities.
<p>General description of the selected room geometry (shape, windows, doors, other openings and other features): Shape and Layout: The room has a rectangular shape with a series of tables and chairs arranged in rows. The tables are rectangular, and the chairs may be positioned on both sides of the tables (a setup for group work) or on one side (lectures). Windows: There are 4 large windows allowing natural light to enter the room. The windows are fitted with horizontal bars and have the capability to be opened for ventilation. The window elements (apart from the glass) are brown which creates a contrast against the white wall. Doors: There are 4 doors in the selected room. Additional Features: There is a projector mounted on the ceiling, centrally positioned to project onto a screen or wall at the front of the room next to the teacher's place. Ventilation or air conditioning units are on the ceiling, contributing to a controlled climate within the room. The walls are equipped with various electrical outlets and possibly network ports, indicating that the room is designed to accommodate electronic devices. There are signs and safety equipment on the walls, such as an emergency exit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The room is sufficiently large and ergonomically shaped to allow for a comfortable arrangement, the only barrier also visually may be the column placed in the middle.

<p>sign and extinguishers, indicating compliance with safety regulations.</p>	
<p>Area and height of the room: The selected room is roughly rectangular in shape, measuring approximately 20 by 10 meters (there are window niches, a column, wall offsets), with an area of approximately 215.5 meters. The room is about 3.70 meters high, but the structural height is probably about 4 meters (the usable height is reduced by the suspended ceiling).</p>	
<p>Description of levels in the selected room (one level or more, level difference between the corridor/outdoor room and the selected room): There is no difference in level either in the room or in the passages from the room to other rooms.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no difference in level either in the room or in the passages from the room to other rooms, which is optimal and convenient for all users.
<p>Orientation of the selected room in relation to the cardinal system (which sides of the world do the windows face?): The room's windows face south and east and have curtains. The west-facing windows are shaded because they are in a passage on the ground floor of the building - a kind of gate leading to the courtyard (see photo 8).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The orientation of the room in relation to the world allows for good room lighting (aided by artificial light), the curtains help to control the insolation and counteract overheating and excessive sunlight. • Curtains: Should be easy to operate, preferably with accessible controls or cords. Traditional curtains are currently hung, (if possible) it is recommended to change them for better comfort of users.
<p>Size of doors in the selected room: Doors (see photos 1,2,3,4): Entrance A is a two-wing door, the wider wing when opened leaves a clear opening of approximately 85 cm, the other part can also be opened, which widens the door clear width to around 120 cm. Entrance A has a panic door - corridor side traditional handle, classroom side - panic push bar (easy to open). Entrance B has analogous dimensions, entrance C has a clearance of 140 cm when both wings are opened. Entrance D leads directly to the outside (partly glazed like windows). It has two wings of equal size which, when opened, have a clear width of at least 2 meters. Entrance D has a panic door - outside traditional handle, classroom side - panic push bar (easy to open). The height of the different doors varies but is no less than 200 cm clear height.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A comfortable clear width for all users (including those in wheelchairs) is 90 cm. The doors in the selected room can be opened to this width, but in the case of the most important (in terms of use) entrances A and B, this requires both leaves to be open. Therefore, for any renovation, it is recommended to replace these doors with doors whose wider leaf leaves a clear width of at least 90 mm when opened.

<p>Colour and material of doors (frame) in the selected room, handle height and shape: (see photos 1,2,3,4)</p> <p>Entrance A: The door is white; the door frame is also white with a contrasting black edge (see photo 2). Entrance A has a panic door. The traditional handle (corridor side) is positioned at a standard height, which is typically around 1 meter (100 cm) from the floor. The door handle (classroom side) is a horizontal bar type, commonly used for emergency exits. It has a red colour for visibility and is designed for easy push operation.</p> <p>Entrance B: The door is white; the door frame is also white with a contrasting black edge (see photo 1). Entrance A has a panic door. The traditional handle (corridor side) is positioned at a standard height, which is typically around 1 meter (100 cm) from the floor. The door handle (classroom side) is a horizontal bar type, commonly used for emergency exits. It has a red colour for visibility and is designed for easy push operation.</p> <p>Entrance C: The door is white; the door frame is also white with a contrasting black edge (see photo 1).</p> <p>Entrance D: Entrance D leads directly to the outside. It has two wings of equal size which, when opened, have a clear width of at least 2 meters.</p> <p>The door is brown, all elements (apart from the glass) are brown which creates a contrast against the white wall. Entrance D has a panic door. The traditional handle (outside) is positioned at a standard height, which is typically around 1 meter (100 cm) from the floor. The door handle (classroom side) is a horizontal bar type, commonly used for emergency exits. It has a red colour for visibility and is designed for easy push operation.</p> <p>There is a slight difference in level between the room and the outside pavement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The colour and material of the door (frame) in the selected room, the height and shape of the handle are appropriate and comfortable for all users.
<p>Size of windows and possibility to open them (height above the floor): There are 4 large windows allowing natural light to enter the room. The windows are fitted with horizontal bars and have the capability to be opened for ventilation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If windows need to be opened, the mechanisms should be reachable for people of all heights and abilities. The opening height of the window (handle) is too high, above 110 cm from the floor, and should be changed to a lower position (between 80 and

	<p>110 cm above floor level) when replacing the windows or the opening mechanism.</p>
<p>Description of lighting in the selected room: There are 4 large windows allowing natural light to enter the room. The room is also well-lit with ceiling-mounted fluorescent light fixtures, ensuring that the space remains bright even without natural light.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizontal and vertical surfaces in the selected room of the building are well-lit by the windows and light fittings incorporated into the suspended ceiling. The windows have curtains to prevent too much sunlight, the spacing of lighting fixtures allow for even light distribution. Light source is positioned high enough to reduce glare. • Fluorescent lights should be well-maintained to avoid flickering, which can be discomforting or problematic for some individuals. • Adequate lighting is crucial to help visually impaired individuals navigate the room. It must be ensured all lights are functional and provide even illumination without creating harsh shadows.
<p>Position of light switches in the selected room: Light switches and contacts are approximately 80 cm above the floor (see photo 10).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The light switches are mounted at the correct height and are accessible to all users, including those in wheelchairs.
<p>Suspended/elevated/protruding elements in the selected room:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Typical grid suspended ceiling • There is a projector suspended from the ceiling in the central part of the room. • Multiple ceiling-mounted lighting fixtures are visible, evenly distributed across the room. • There are ceiling-mounted air conditioning units. • Wall-mounted speakers can be seen on the side walls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elements are installed correctly and do not pose a risk to people with special needs are not a barrier to the daily use of the room.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curtain Rods: Alongside the windows, holding curtains. • Wall-mounted Equipment: Various other wall-mounted equipment including fire safety equipment near the windows and some electrical outlets. 	
<p>Floor in selected room (material, colour, contrast, pattern, slip/non-slip floor, even/ uneven etc.): <u>Material:</u> The floor is ceramic tiled. <u>Colour and pattern:</u> Light-coloured (very light beige), which can help brighten the room and make it feel more spacious. The tiles are not patterned, the pattern of the floor is shaped by the arrangement of the tiles. There is no significant colour contrast between the walls and the floor. <u>Slipperiness:</u> Tiles can be slippery, especially when wet. This poses a potential slip hazard.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tiled flooring in the room can be both comfortable and safe if appropriate precautions are taken. It is particularly important to manage the risk of slipperiness and ensure the tiles are well-maintained and level. • Generally good for wheelchairs as the hard surface allows for easy rolling. However, care must be taken to ensure that tiles are level to prevent tripping hazards. • The flat and hard surface is suitable for use with canes, walkers, and other mobility aids.
<p>Walls in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast): <u>Material and colour:</u> The walls are made of standard plaster, painted in white, no pattern, which helps in making the room feel bright and spacious. There is no significant colour contrast between the walls and the floor.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plain walls can sometimes cause echoes in a large room. Adding elements like wall panels, bulletin boards, or acoustic treatments can help in reducing noise levels. • There is no significant colour contrast between the walls and the floor. Recommended more contrast between wall and floor colour if renovating or installing wall panels. • The walls of the room are designed to be functional and safe, with elements that contribute to the room's usability. By ensuring that all wall-mounted items are securely installed and accessible, and by maintaining the walls' cleanliness and condition, the environment can remain both comfortable and safe for all users.

<p>Ceiling in selected room (material, colour, pattern, contrast): <u>Material:</u> the ceiling is standard grid suspended ceiling, commonly used in institutional or office settings. <u>Colour:</u> White <u>Lighting:</u> Embedded rectangular fluorescent light fixtures and air conditioning units are regularly spaced throughout the ceiling.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suspended ceiling tiles can help dampen noise, improving the acoustic comfort of the room. However, additional acoustic treatments may be beneficial if the room is prone to echoing. • The ceiling of the room is designed to be functional, providing necessary lighting and hosting various suspended elements. By ensuring regular maintenance and considering potential upgrades for improved energy efficiency and acoustic comfort, the ceiling can continue to support a safe and comfortable environment for all users.
<p>Information boards and tactile maps: Information boards are placed at a height of 1.2 - 1.6 m. Written, lettered, and graphic markings are contrasted in colour with the background. Sufficiently large font size has been used on all boards and markings. Sans-serif fonts have been used in the written text on markings and boards.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information boards are well designed, information for the blind is missing. No information boards and tactile maps illustrating the most important elements of the room. The presence of such signs and descriptions is recommended.
<p>Possibility for a person with reduced mobility or who is visually impaired to move around the chosen room (issue of obstacles, width of passageways, possibility of changing direction, guidance elements):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tables and chairs are arranged in rows with clear passageways between them. • There is manoeuvring space with minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 m at the end of passageways and near the entrance. • There are no tactile orientation paths in the room. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The passageways between the rows of tables are sufficiently wide for a wheelchair to pass through comfortably. • There is a large enough manoeuvring space at the end of passageways and near the entrance (space that is also used to access the door). • The room appears to have ample space for a wheelchair or mobility aid user to manoeuvre, including turning and changing directions. • Fire extinguishers and other wall-mounted items are installed at accessible heights and do not protrude into walkways.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should be considered to add tactile flooring to guide visually impaired individuals safely through the room in case of renovation.
<p>Adaptation of furniture and furnishings to the needs of impaired persons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The standard height of tables is suitable for most users. • Seated workstations provide free space under the desk (height x width x depth) min. 0.70 m x 0.90 m x 0.60 m? Desktop is at a height of 0.7 - 0.8 meters; integrated power strip is above the desk; additional access to electrical outlets has been provided from the desk. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room appears to have sufficient space to manoeuvre (manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m near the conference table, near the work desk) a wheelchair or mobility device, including turning and changing direction, and to drive to the chosen seat at the table (which should be provided directly at the aisle between the rows of tables). • The standard height of tables is suitable for most users but may need adjustments for wheelchair accessibility in some cases.
<p>An induction loop or other devices for the hearing impaired:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room is not equipped with an induction loop, which is recommended in lecture rooms.
<p>Is an evacuation plan posted in a clearly visible place in the room? Yes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Escape routes in case of fire are marked correctly.
<p>SUMMARY - PANEL REQUIREMENTS</p>	
<p>CEILING PANELS: not applicable</p>	
<p>WALL PANELS:</p> <p><u>Material:</u> Materials should be chosen that are durable, easy to clean, and have sound-absorbing properties, such as acoustic foam or fabric-covered panels.</p> <p><u>Colour and Contrast, surface:</u> Contrast colours should be used to aid visually impaired individuals. Light-coloured panels with dark borders can help in defining the space better. Attention should be paid to the contrast between the panels and the floor. Textured surfaces may be incorporated to provide tactile feedback for individuals with visual impairments.</p> <p><u>Placement and Installation:</u></p> <p>It must be ensured that panels do not cover or obstruct important features such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency Exits and Signs: Panels should be installed without covering them. Contrast colours should be used around exits and signs to enhance visibility. • Fire Extinguishers and Safety Equipment: Panels should be cut to fit around these items or items should be fixed to panels in a safe way, ensuring they remain easily accessible. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power Outlets and Switches: Panels should not block access to electrical outlets or light switches. These areas should be marked clearly if they are embedded in the panels. <p><u>Height and Reach:</u></p> <p><u>Mounting Height and place:</u> panels must be at a height that does not interfere with the general use of the room. The reach of individuals in wheelchairs or those with limited mobility must be considered. Panels must not block or restrict movement and manoeuvring space.</p> <p><u>Continuous Surface:</u> It must be ensured that panels provide a continuous surface, avoiding gaps that could catch on clothing or mobility aids.</p> <p><u>Acoustic Considerations:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound Absorption: Panels should be strategically positioned to reduce noise and echo in the room. Areas behind and around speaking areas, such as the front where the projector screen is located, are ideal. • It's better if panels are spread evenly across the room to provide uniform sound absorption. <p><u>Tactile Indicators:</u> It is recommended to add tactile markers or signs to assist visually impaired users in navigating the space if panel are located along the path/passage.</p> <p><u>Additional Features:</u></p> <p>Integrated Whiteboards/Bulletin Boards: Panels may be combined panels with functional elements like whiteboards or bulletin boards for multipurpose use.</p>
FLOOR PANELS: not applicable
FINAL COMMENTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The room is generally accessible for individuals with reduced mobility and those who are visually and hearing impaired. With some additional considerations and improvements, the space can become even more accommodating and user-friendly for everyone (see EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED ROOM AND UNIVERSAL DESIGN column above). • In the selected room, wall panels will be installed as part of the ongoing project, so the final recommendations are consistent with the recommendations for panels detailed above (see "SUMMARY - PANEL REQUIREMENTS")

6.7 Conclusions of the Herit4ages Accessibility Analysis.

Presented in report conclusions according to users' needs and universal design principles should be taken into account during designing the Herit4Ages solutions. Solutions should not reduce the accessibility of chosen rooms in the demo sites. Accessibility audit of buildings and recommendations for accessibility for the whole demo sites will be done in next WP. Particular attention should be paid to the synergistic design of panels in terms of utility, accessibility and aesthetics. Panels should not obscure elements of historical and aesthetic value. Implementation sites should be carefully selected so as not to detract from the aesthetics of the site. Adding accessibility-related elements should follow the

principles of universal design and facility aesthetics. When designing panels, the guidelines for individual demos should be followed. In order to universalize solutions, you can adopt limiting conditions and dimensions that will be beneficial for all examples. During further work, additional accessibility requirements can be introduced in subsequent work packages. The design of the panels should take into account the needs of the largest possible group of users.

7. Definition of the Herit4ages KPIs.

7.1 The Herit4ages KPIs categories.

Four categories are defined for the performance assessment of the solutions: low emission, inclusive evaluation, energy efficiency, and resilient evaluation. For each of them a brief description is included below.

a) Low Emission. It refers to the aspects involved on the sustainability assessment of the solutions, as it intends to quantify the environmental footprint of the products obtained during the project. The Life Cycle Assessment would be the main evaluation included within this category, for which is intended to evaluate the impact of the solutions first focusing on raw materials selected for the prototypes, as well as on the products developed for the living labs. The production recycled raw materials and performance it is included in the assessment. The LCA assessment is considered from the early stages of the project through the project validation of the demo sites, as it is intended to be used as a design support tool.

b) Inclusive Evaluation. Refers to the evaluation of the social engagement and innovation process, also considering Universal Design. The objective is to assess the practical adaptability and usefulness of the co-creation framework in conservation and energy renovation process for sustainable, accessible and inclusive heritage. The evaluations also analyse the transfer a social innovation into universal design process readiness and perception of end-users and other stakeholders in the cultural heritage renovation value chain for a wider adoption of the tested solutions. The evaluation report on social innovation will result from this category.

c) Energy Efficiency. This category will evaluate the aspects related to energy performance and cost-effectiveness of the renovation solutions; this includes Life Cycle Cost (LCC). The evaluation is performed with the use of a calibrated model at room and building level.

d) Resilient Evaluation. The conservation and maintenance aspects are also included within this KPI category, which is based on the principles of preventive conservation to ensure the preservation of the cultural values while reducing the maintenance and operational costs.

7.2 The Monitoring Plan and Layout.

7.2.1 The Romanesque Hermitage, Canduela, ES

The present section summarises the data collection process that is required to calculate the KPIs according to the methods explained in subsequent parts of this section. As the Heritage Laboratory (HL) of the Herit4ages project, the case of the Ermita de Santa Maria de Canduela is described first, which is located in Palencia, Spain (Romanesque hermitage of Canduela). The HL has been used as Heritage Laboratory from 2012; hence, it acts a reference for the installation of the monitoring system in the Herit4ages project demo sites. As HL, the Hermitage counts with infrastructure and equipment to test renovation solutions without human interaction. The process to obtain the data as well as the required input measurements is briefly introduced here, while a more extensive description is presented as part of deliverable 7.1. The description presented here include information about the monitoring devices (sensors, storage devices, loggers, etc.), the monitoring layout, the software employed as well as the monitoring strategy for the data acquisition. The monitoring system in the remaining four Herit4ages demo sites, follows a very similar approach than the one presented for the HL, it is also presented in detail as part of deliverable D7.1.

The Monitoring System at the Heritage Laboratory (HL)

The data collection process involves the following steps:

1. Sensors will collect data at predefined intervals, depending on the specific parameter being monitored.
2. Data will be transmitted via the LoRaWAN network to the installed gateways.
3. Gateways will relay the data to the LoRa Network Server.
4. The server will process and decode the data.
5. Processed data will be sent to the FSM IoT platform for storage and visualization.
6. Data will be securely stored in a database.

Monitoring sensors and Logging Hardware

For the collection of environmental data outdoors, the following environmental quantities will be collected using a weather station located in the exterior of the building (dimensions 430 x 190 x 220 mm). Measurements are taken at intervals typically set to every 30 minutes to capture daily climate variations. Ambient temperature (°C), Relative Humidity (%), Precipitation (mm), Wind Speed (m/s), Wind direction (degrees) and Air Pressure (hPa), are usually collected. Table 11 shows additional details of the parameters measured by the weather station and technical features.

TABLE 11 OUTDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS MEASURED BY THE WEATHER STATION IN THE HL DEMO SITE.

Environmental Parameter	Range	Resolution	Accuracy
Temperature	-40 °C a 60°C	1°C	+/-0.3°C
Humidity	0 a 100% HR	1% HR	+/-2% HR
Air Pressure	10 a 1300 hpa	0,1 hpa	+/-1 hpa
Wind Direction	0 ~360 °	1 °	+/-3°
Wind Speed	0 ~60 m/s	0,1 m/s	+/-0,3%
Precipitation	0 ~5 mm/min	0,2mm Accuracy:	+/-3%

In regard to the data collection indoors, sensors will be installed at key locations within the monitored room or in its adjacent spaces where necessary. As for instance, contact temperature sensors will be mounted on walls to measure surface temperature, as well as special probe sensors that allow measurement of ambient temperature away from the walls. Measurement intervals for indoor sensors will be set to 30 minutes, depending on the specific parameter being monitored. Table 12 shows details of the sensors to be installed in the demonstration site.

TABLE 12 INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS MEASURED IN THE HERITAGE LABORATORY, PALENCIA, SPAIN.

Device	Environmental Parameter	Operating Principle or Sensor Type	Range	Accuracy	Resolution
Temperature and Humidity Sensor	Temperature		-20°C ~ 60°C	± 0.2°C	0.1°C
	Humidity		0% RH ~ 100% RH	± 2% RH	0.5% RH
Indoor Air Quality Sensor (CO2 + TH)	Temperature	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	-20°C ~ 60°C	± 0.2°C	0.1°C
	Humidity	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	0% ~ 100% RH	± 2% RH	0.5% RH
	Carbon Dioxide (CO2)	Nondispersive Infrared (NDIR)	400 to 5000 ppm	± (30 ppm + 3% of reading) (0°C to +50°C)	1 ppm
Indoor Air Quality Sensor (TVOC + CO2 + PMs + TH + HCHO + O3)	Temperature	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	-20°C ~ 60°C	± 0.2°C	0.1°C
	Humidity	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	0% ~ 100% RH	± 2% RH	0.5% RH

	Motion	Passive infrared (PIR)	Detection range: 80° Horizontal, 55° Vertical, 5m		
	Light	Photodiode	0-60000 Lux (Determine as 6 levels, 0-5)		
	TVOC	MOX (MEMS)	1.00 ~ 5.00 (IAQ Rating)	±1	0.01
	Barometric Pressure	Piezoresistive absolute pressure sensor (MEMS)	260 ~ 1260 hPa	±0.5 hPa	0.1 hPa
	Carbon Dioxide (CO2)	Photoacoustic	400 to 2000 ppm	± (50 ppm + 5% of reading) (-10°C to +60°C)	1 ppm
	PM2.5 & PM10	Laser Scattering	0 ~ 1000 µg/m3	0100(±10µg/m3), 1001000(±10%) (-10°C ~ 60°C)	1 µg/m3
	Formaldehyde (HCHO)	Electrochemical	0 ~ 1.25 mg/m3	±10 %	0.01 mg/m3
	Ozone (O3)	Electrochemical	0 ~ 10 ppm	±5 % FS	0.01 ppm
Indoor Air Quality Sensor (TVOC + CO2 + PMs + TH)	Temperature	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	-20°C ~ 60°C	± 0.2°C	0.1°C
	Humidity	Digital CMOSens® technology (MEMS)	0% ~ 100% RH	± 2% RH	
	Motion	Passive infrared (PIR)	Detection range: 80° Horizontal, 55° Vertical, 5m		
	Light	Photodiode	0-60000 Lux (Determine as 6 levels, 0-5)		
	TVOC	MOX (MEMS)	1.00 ~ 5.00 (IAQ Rating)	±1	0.01

	Barometric Pressure	Piezoresistive absolute pressure sensor (MEMS)	260 ~ 1260 hPa	±0.5 hPa	0.1 hPa
	Carbon Dioxide (CO2)	Nondispersive Infrared (NDIR)	400 to 5000 ppm	± (30 ppm + 3% of reading) (0°C ~ 50°C, 0% ~ 85% RH)	1 ppm
	PM2.5 & PM10	Laser Scattering	0 ~ 1000 µg/m3	0 ~ 100(±10µg/m3), 100 ~ 1000(±10%) (-10°C ~ 60°C)	1 µg/m3

Data storage and IoT platform

The FSM platform will manage and store monitoring data through the following process:

1. The platform will generate real-time graphs and reports for analysis, as well as perform calculations for KPIs and advanced analytics.
2. Visualizations and customizable dashboards will be generated for user interaction.
3. Alerts based on predefined thresholds will be implemented for proactive monitoring.
4. Data will be exported for integration with the HERIT4AGES project platform.

7.2.2 Residential Building, Funchal, PT

The present description represents the case of the Heritage Living Laboratory (HLL) in Funchal Madeira, which is a residential house built in 1937 and renovated in 2006, located at the Funchal historic downtown. In the Funchal HLL, the Smart Energy Router and the Non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) will be implemented as energy improvement measures. The former, would be developed to support the energy management in historic buildings using intelligent algorithms built from a previous insight of the energy requirements in the residential building. The NILM will support the operations of the Smart Energy Router by extracting energy loads patters using the electric current of an installation (appliances consumption patterns and the occupant’s usage period) to support energy flexibility. The process would lead to an optimization of the energy usage in a non-intrusive way, additionally addressing privacy and security concerns. The sections below include a brief description of the process to obtain the data at the Funchal HLL, including the description of devices (sensors, storage devices, loggers, etc.), the monitoring layout, software as well as the strategy for the data acquisition. Details are provided in Table 13.

Regarding energy performance, the following resources will be used:

- The smart energy router will measure the energy provided by the PV panels, and the energy flow (charge / discharge) with the battery storage system

- The smart energy router will measure all electrical variables associated with the system (electrical power, electrical energy, current, voltage...)
- A dedicated sensor will measure the overall consumption of the house (energy coming from the DSO)

TABLE 13 INDOOR AND OUTDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL MEASUREMENTS IN THE DEMO SITE IN FUNCHAL, PORTUGAL.

Measurements	Details
Heat related measurements	No heating/cooling system installed in the Funchal demonstration site.
Electricity related measurements	<p>A dedicated sensor will measure the overall consumption of the house (energy coming from the DSO):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Energy (kWh) ○ Active power (kW) ○ Reactive power (kVAr) ○ Apparent power (kVA) ○ Power factor ○ Current (A) ○ Voltage (V) <p>- Electrical power (kW) and electrical energy (kWh) of major appliances will be computed using the NILM algorithm. No sensors will be installed. The NILM algorithm will use the data from the previous sensor.</p>
Energy Router Measurements	<p>- Energy Router will measure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ From PV panels: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy (kWh) ▪ Active power (kW) ▪ Current (A) ▪ Voltage (V) ○ From battery storage system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ State of Charge (%) ▪ Charging and discharging power (kW) ▪ Current (A) ▪ Voltage (V) ○ At the PCC (point of common coupling): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Energy (kWh) ▪ Active power (kW) ▪ Reactive power (kVAr) ▪ Apparent power (kVA) ▪ Power factor ▪ Current (A)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Voltage (V)
Fuel consumption related quantities.	n/a
Environmental quantities Outdoors.	Outdoors: Ambient temperature (°C), Relative Humidity (%), Precipitation, Average Solar Radiation (W/m2), Wind speed (m/s), Wind direction (degree), Atmospheric air pressure (hPa).

Logging Hardware and Data storage and IoT platform

The data acquisition system architecture is graphically described in Figure 44. Only Wi-Fi communication is foreseen inside the house, and data will be sent directly to the UNINOVA server through the cloud. All data will be acquired with 1-min resolution. Electrical currents on the main switchboard will be acquired with a sampling frequency of 2kHz (for the NILM algorithm).

FIGURE 44 IOT ARCHITECTURE FOR THE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM IN THE FUNCHAL DEMONSTRATION SITE.

7.3 The Herit4ages KPIs cards.

The KPIs employed to assess the performance of the Herit4ages solutions were determined based on the partners experience, they are grouped in four categories listed below:

- a) Low Emission (LE) led by partner CETIM.
- b) Inclusive Cultural Heritage (ICH), led by IBS, with participation of LWI and WUT partners.
- c) Energy Efficiency (EE), led by TYN, with participation of CETIM and UNINOVA partners.
- d) Resilient Evaluation (RE), led by FSMLR.

A total of 29 KPIs were proposed by the Herit4ages partners. For the first category (Low Emissions), four KPIs are proposed to assess the impact of the renovation solutions on the environment, such as determine the value for the carbon footprint, life cycle analysis (LCA), and the use of non-renewable primary materials. For the second category (Inclusive cultural heritage), seven KPIs are proposed to assess the capacity of the renovation solutions to preserve the cultural heritage of the demo site and to assess social participation. As for instance, the level of reversibility of the intervention, the installation time reduction, participants satisfaction and user's acceptance of the solutions. For the third category (energy efficiency), 15 KPIs are proposed to assess different aspects in which the renovation solutions impact the use of energy in the building, as for instance energy consumption, thermal comfort of the occupants, the renewable energy on-site generation. This category also includes KPIs to assess the financial benefits that signified the renovation implementation, such as Life cycle cost (LCC) or operational expenditure (OPEX). For the fourth category (resilience evaluation), three KPIs were proposed to assess aspects such as compatibility with cultural values and the state of conservation of the Herit4ages buildings.

7.3.1 The KPIs summary.

The 29 KPIs of the Herit4ages project as proposed by the partners are shown in Table 14, which consist of a summary of the main aspects to describe each of the indicators, the KPI name and responsible partner, the evaluation unit and a brief description of the aim and methods. Then detailed descriptions of the KPIs are presented in the form of 'KPIs cards' in Annex III

TABLE 14 SUMMARY KPIS IN THE HERIT4AGES PROJECT, CLASSIFIED BY CATEGORY.

KPI Category and card no.	KPI Name	KPI Partner	KPI unit	KPI source	Brief description	
Low Emission	LE-1	Embodied carbon savings	CET	%	GA	In order to determine a value for the carbon footprint, it is necessary to perform a life cycle assessment (LCA) for the Herit4Ages solutions, including its products and materials. The carbon dioxide content is considered as Global Warming Potential (GWP), which is why this category receives a lot of attention from the public and is therefore classified as one of the most important. This KPI determines the embodied carbon savings in Herit4Ages solutions compared to a reference scenario which could be the BAU building practice or the existing solution in the demo sites.
	LE-2	Material health savings	CET	%	EU project CIRCuiT with major modifications	This KPI evaluates, from a LCA perspective, the overall health risks of materials and products in the Herit4Ages solutions, quantified as impact on healthy life years of humans. The measure unit is the disability-adjusted life year per kilogram of solution (DALY/kg solution). One DALY represents the loss of the equivalent of one year of full health. The Herit4Ages solutions results in this issue are compared to a reference scenario to assess the potential savings.
	LE-3	Low carbon materials in composition	CET	%	GA	This KPI quantifies the use of low carbon materials in the composition of solutions. Herit4Ages aims to promote the use of local waste, recycled and lightweight aggregates, PCMs and vegetable fibres. Therefore, this KPI calculates the mass percentage of these materials that are part of the final solutions and should reach a minimum of 40% according to the GA.
	LE-4	Circularity (Material Origin)	CET	Score	EU project ICEBERG with minor modifications	To drive circularity in the building sector, the use of non-renewable primary materials should be minimized and replaced by waste or recycled resources. This KPI assesses the circularity of the materials used in the final solutions by prioritising the use of waste and recycled over by-products or waste streams that may be valorised for other uses or the main products in first manufacturing.
Inclusive Cultural Heritage	ICH-1	Reversibility of solutions	LWI	%	GA	This KPI evaluates the level of reversibility of the Herit4Ages renovation interventions, i.e. the possibility to install the solutions without using invasive connecting methods and remove renovation solutions without any lasting effects on the demo buildings. Relevant for: all demos.
	ICH-2	Installation time reduction	LWI	%	GA	Difference of the actual installation speed of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions from the typical installation speed of similar products in the market. Relevant for: all demos where panels will be installed (Tartu, Aguilar de Campoo, Bologna).

	ICH-3	Perceived level of disruption	IBS	low/moderate/high	Partner	The KPI assess the end users' perception of the level of disruption experienced during the installation of the Herit4Ages solutions at their demo sits. Relevant for: all demos.	
	ICH-4	User acceptance of Herit4Ages solutions	IBS	%	GA	End-users' level of acceptance of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions in terms of the perceived utility, aesthetic value, heritage preservation value and responsiveness to users' expectations. Relevant for: all demos	
	ICH-4	Number of participations in the co-creation process	IBS	number	GA	This KPI measures the reach of the Herit4Ages project in terms of stakeholder engagement by counting instances of stakeholder participation in the demo sites' co-creation processes activities (Heritage Living Labs). Relevant for: all demos	
	ICH-6	Participant satisfaction with the co-creation process	IBS	%	Partner	This KPI assesses the participants' satisfaction with the setup and outcomes of the co-creation processes in the Herit4Ages demos (heritage Living Labs). Relevant for: all demos.	
	ICH-7	Universal design integration	WUT	%	GA	Compliance is primarily concerned with the dimensions in the room to allow movement of all potential (including those with limitations) users (obstacles on the floor, widths of passageways, heights), colours (the issue of light and sound reflection, contrasts), material (ease of cleanliness and allergenicity), lighting and others. Relevant for: all demos where panels will be installed (Tartu, Aguilar de Campoo, Bologna).	
	Energy Efficiency	EE-1	Energy Consumption	TYN	kWh/m ² .y	Partner TYN.	This KPI determines the energy consumption for electricity and gas before and after the implementation of the solutions in the demonstration sites in FEUB, IBS and FSMLR.
		EE-2	Energy Savings	TYN	kWh/m ² .y	Partner TYN.	This KPI determines the reduction of the final energy consumption to reach the same services (e.g. comfort levels) after the interventions, taking into consideration the final energy consumption from the reference period.
EE-3		Energy Use Intensity (EUI)	TYN	kWh/m ² .y	Partner TYN.	Energy performance in buildings is commonly measured in kWh/m ² /yr, i.e. kilowatt hours of energy per square metre of building per year, referred as Energy Use Intensity (EUI).	
EE-4		Indoor Thermal Comfort – Adaptive Comfort	TYN	Category I, II	Partner TYN.	This KPI determines the acceptability of indoor thermal conditions, is intended to be used in naturally ventilated buildings, it also accounts for people's clothing adaptation in natural conditioned spaces by relating the acceptable range of indoor temperatures to the outdoor climate.	
EE-5		Discomfort Index	TYN	Unitless	Partner TYN.	A discomfort index measures how much discomfort a person feels with a given air temperature and relative humidity. The higher the relative humidity and the air temperature, the greater the discomfort index. Conversely, the lower the temperature and humidity the lower the discomfort.	

EE-6	Report on Subjective Thermal Comfort	TYN	%	Partner TYN.	The output from a subjective evaluation performed before and after the renovation implementation will be reported to assess the users' impressions regarding the thermal performance improvements.
EE-7	Air Quality Index (AQI)	TYN	Unitless	Partner TYN.	In the air quality index, equal importance is given to all the pollutants. Using observed and standards value, the quality rating for each pollutant is calculated.
EE-8	Risk of Condensation	TYN	Varies	Partner TYN	Assess the risk of condensation in the demo sites. Two methods are considered, one will be employed depending on data availability. First, the simplified calculations using the Glaser Method to assess the risk of surface and interstitial condensation. Secondly, the Heat and Moisture Transfer Calculation (HAMT), based on EnergyPlus, to calculate the heat and moisture transport in building components.
EE-9	Savings in electrical energy consumption	UNI	%	Partner UNI.	This KPI determines the reduction of the final electrical energy consumption to reach the same services after the Smart Energy Router system installation, taking into consideration the final energy consumption from the reference period (2022-2023).
EE-10	Self-sufficiency ratio	UNI	%	Partner UNI.	This KPI refers to the degree to which the on-site generation is sufficient to cover the final energy consumption of the building/system. It measures the amount of the building/system's energy consumption that is instantaneously matched by the building/system's on-site generation.
EE-11	Accuracy of NILM classification.	UNI	Unitless	Partner UNI.	This KPI is used to evaluate the efficiency of the NILM method. It is based on the F-measure providing a comprehensive measure of a NILM's performance by balancing precision and recall, making it an ideal metric for evaluating how well the system identifies and disaggregates electrical loads. Ensures that both false positives and false negatives are considered, providing a more balanced evaluation and is particularly useful in scenarios where the number of events is much smaller than the non-events, which is common in NILM.
EE-12	Percentage of improvement	TYN	%	Partner Tyndall.	Percentage of Improvement is used to calculate improvements in time reductions or cost savings, between two values representing the before and after the implementation of renovation measures.
EE-13	LCC savings	CETIM	%	Partner: CETIM.	LCC is widely used as an economic KPI to assess the financial performance of a product throughout its entire life cycle. It evaluates the total costs associated with a product, including raw material acquisition, processing, maintenance, and disposal. This approach enables organizations to make cost-effective and sustainable decisions. To determine the Life Cycle Cost (LCC) savings, it is necessary to calculate the LCC of the Herit4Ages solutions and compare it with a reference scenario consisting of commercial products not made with waste or by-products sourced near the demo sites.

	EE-14	CAPEX initial investment indicator.	CETIM	TBD	Partner: CETIM.	CAPEX (Capital Expenditure) is a critical economic KPI in construction projects because it reflects the initial investment required to acquire and build long-term physical assets. CAPEX represents a significant portion of the total budget of a project and helps to evaluate whether the required investment is justified to the expected economic or social/environmental service benefits. It will be compared with a reference scenario of equivalent products on the market.
	EE-15	OPEX indicator	CETIM	TBD	Partner: CETIM.	OPEX (Operational Expenditure) is an economic KPI in a building renovation project because it represents the ongoing operational costs incurred after the project is completed. Justifying its use as a KPI is based on its impact on the long-term financial and operational viability of the building. Monitoring OPEX ensures that the renovation aligns with the building's long-term operational goals, such as energy efficiency, maintenance, and resource utilization.
Resilient Evaluation	RE-1	State of Conservation	FSM	TBD	Partner (FSM)	The State of Conservation KPI evaluates the overall preservation status of heritage sites using data from installed sensors. The goal is to monitor the conservation conditions, ensuring they remain within optimal thresholds. This KPI will be categorized into three states: good condition, inadequate condition, and at-risk condition. The final output will be an annual average indicating the percentage of time the site was in each state. In addition to sensor measurements, there is an interpretation and know-how effort by FSM specialists, leveraging their expertise in preventive conservation of heritage.
	RE-2	Risk State Evaluation	FSM	TBD	Partner (FSM)	The Risk State Evaluation KPI measures the percentage of time the heritage site is in a state of risk based on sensor data and MHS-Algorithm analysis.
	RE-3	Compatibility with cultural values	FSM	TBD	EU project	This KPI assesses the degree of compatibility of retrofitting interventions with the building's cultural values. It evaluates the effectiveness and suitability of conservation solutions implemented at heritage sites and their impact on the preservation of original elements. The purpose is to ensure that interventions do not harm the cultural heritage, balancing conservation needs with improvements in environmental conditions and energy efficiency. This will be measured through a coefficient that considers technical parameters that can be quantitatively measured, such as the time the site was at risk and improvements in energy efficiency after solutions are implemented, along with a comprehensive evaluation by experts to ensure that the cultural significance of the site is respected.

8. Conclusions

An analysis of the building demo sites at different levels was presented in this deliverable, the study started by presenting the overall context of the sites in regards of surroundings and location and weather conditions. Secondly, a detailed analysis of the building and the monitored rooms followed, to be able to understand the building's characteristics, and therefore their requirements at level of improvement, also associated to the needs of the occupants. Results of a subjective evaluation in the way of surveys applied to the demo site building's occupants were presented also in this deliverable. The regular and occasional (in the case of the hotel) occupants of the building expressed their opinion about the building conditions in winter and summertime, assessed in the range of aspects that goes from comfort indoors to the conservation state of the building. The results indicate that the occupants in overall feel comfortable with the interior environment or find it 'acceptable', on some occasions they would prefer slight changes, but seem to accept the conditions and propose simple solutions. The result of the accessibility analysis, indicate that the rooms show certain deficiencies for universal design, as in many cases the needs for persons with different mobility or visually impaired are not considered, adaptations at reasonable costs are possible. The KPIs that will be used to assess the performance of the solutions is also studied in this deliverable, a total of 29 KPIs were proposed for the assessment of the performance of the Herit4ages solutions, divided into four categories that analyse: inclusive heritage (4 KPIs), low emissions (7), energy efficiency (15) and resilience (3).

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Annex I – Subjective Assessment Survey.

T2.4 b) Survey - building users/owner (summertime version).

This survey is being conducted as part of the implementation of the Herit4ages project. For a detailed explanation of its purpose, please refer to the Informative Note delivered to you along with the Consent Agreement Form. This survey intends to collect information about the demo-site building regarding demographics of the users, perception of the interior environment, energy use, as well as the value of the historic building from the user's point of view. The survey is intended to be applied in two versions, wintertime and its present version corresponding to summertime. Thank you for your participation.

To complete by the inquirer.

Demo-site ID: ES-PSMR, IT-FEUB, PT-SM24, EE-KV	Room ID:
Date/Time to apply the questionnaire:	Describe outdoor conditions (cloudy, sunny, rainy day).

Key of demo-sites: ES-PSMR (Spain), IT-FEUB (Italy), PT-SM24 (Portugal), EE-KV (Estonia).

Part 1. Demography and Occupancy patterns

1.1 Identify the interviewed, are you:

- a) The building owner/titleholder b) A tenant (renting apartment) c) An employee/staff member
d) A student e) Other _____

1.2 Which of the following gender categories best describes how you self-identify?

- a) Woman b) Man c) non-binary
d) Prefer to describe _____
e) Prefer not to state

1.3 Please state your age range:

- a) 18-25 b) 26-35 c) 36-45 d) 46-55
e) 56-65 d) 66-75 e) 76-85 f) > 86

1.4 What is the main purpose of your presence in this building (selecting more than one option is allowed)?

- a) educational (study) b) educational (teaching) b) working
c) living (permanent stay) d) temporal stay (visit) e) other _____

1.5 Can you specify:

Your nationality:	Your educational level:	Your occupation:
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1.6 Occupancy patterns: Which one of the following options better describes your presence in the building room?

- a) On daily basis b) Once a week c) Several times a week d) once a month
e) several times a month f) once a quarter g) several times a quarter h) once every six months
i) occasionally every six months j) once a year k) less than once a year l) never

1.7 Occupancy patterns: How long do you stay in the building per day, on average basis?

- a) Maximum 1 hour b) Maximum 4 hours c) Maximum 6 hours
d) Maximum 8 hours e) Maximum 10 hours f) More than 10 hours

1.8 Occupancy patterns: Can you be more specific about the time schedule of your regular presence in the room?

Educational environments

- a) specific days option 1 _____ time from/to _____
b) specific days option 2 _____ time from/to _____
c) specific days option 3 _____ time from/to _____

Part 2. Physical Comfort: Identify issues related to quality and satisfaction with the interior environment.

Purpose: to assess the subjective perception of the interior environment. Survey method based on ISO 10551:2019

2.1 Thermal Comfort

Please specify the temperature level to which the cooling system is currently and/or usually adjusted during summertime (if unknown please leave it empty). Indoor set temperature °C

Answering the following questions at different times of the day would be ideal (morning, afternoon, late afternoon), if that is not possible, you can refer to the different times of the day (use your experience in the room) or answer only one of the questions (to describe the 'right-now' moment).

Morning hours
from 8:00 am to 12:00 pm

Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied.

Update outdoor conditions:	Visual assessment: cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate (sun and clouds), Rainy day.	Fill using information from the Weather App: Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, wind speed (km/h), wind direction.
----------------------------	---	---

2.1.1 How do you feel about the thermal environment in this room in this moment?

-3 very cold	-2 cold	-1 cold	0 Neutral	1 Warm	2 Hot	3 Very hot
--------------	---------	---------	-----------	--------	-------	------------

2.1.2 Do you find that the thermal environment at this moment is...

Slightly not Acceptable	Not Acceptable	Slightly Acceptable	Acceptable
-------------------------	----------------	---------------------	------------

2.1.3 How do you prefer the environment to be in this moment?

-1 would prefer cooler	0 no change	1 would prefer warmer
------------------------	-------------	-----------------------

Afternoon hours from 12:00 am to 15:00 pm	Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied.	
Update outdoor conditions:	Visual assessment: cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate (sun and clouds), Rainy day.	Fill using information from the Weather App: Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, wind speed (km/h), wind direction.

2.1.4 How do you feel about the thermal environment in this room in this moment?

-3 very cold	-2 cold	-1 slightly cold	0 Neutral	1 Warm	2 Hot	3 Very hot
--------------	---------	------------------	-----------	--------	-------	------------

2.1.5 Do you find that the thermal environment at this moment is...

Slightly not Acceptable	Not Acceptable	Slightly Acceptable	Acceptable
-------------------------	----------------	---------------------	------------

2.1.6 How do you prefer the environment to be in this moment?

-1 would prefer cooler	0 no change	1 would prefer warmer
------------------------	-------------	-----------------------

Late afternoon hours from 15:00 am to 18:00 pm (or later)	Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied.	
Update outdoor conditions:	Visual assessment: cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate (sun and clouds), Rainy day.	Fill using information from the Weather App: Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, wind speed (km/h), wind direction.

2.1.7 How do you feel about the thermal environment in this room in this moment?

-3 very cold	-2 cold	-1 slightly cold	0 Neutral	1 Warm	2 Hot	3 Very hot
--------------	---------	------------------	-----------	--------	-------	------------

2.1.8 Do you find that the thermal environment at this moment is...

Slightly not Acceptable	Not Acceptable	Slightly Acceptable	Acceptable
-------------------------	----------------	---------------------	------------

2.1.9 How do you prefer the environment to be in this moment?

-1 would prefer cooler	0 no change	1 would prefer warmer
------------------------	-------------	-----------------------

Open-Ended Questions: The following questions intend to get the user's 'own words' opinion about the thermal environment indoors in summertime. □

2.1.10 Is the thermal environment sufficiently cool and comfortable with the use of the cooling system?

2.1.11 Are you able to adjust the temperature levels by yourself (heating switches, controls, or by opening the window? If not, please specify why.

2.1.12 Do you need to remove or add some clothing indoors to feel more comfortable?

2.1.13 For the place where you are sitting, do you need to adjust the solar protection device (movable blinds) to control the solar admission? If yes, for which reason: a) glare control, b) excessive heat.

2.1.14 Have you identified a temperature range/level that you usually find comfortable?

2.2 Visual Performance

This section is intended to assess the visual perception of the interior environment by the users. For natural lighting, as the sun elevation changes according to seasons (it is higher in summertime), the interior lighting conditions would also vary.

Answering the following questions at different times of the day would be ideal (morning, afternoon, late afternoon), if that is not possible, you can refer to the different times of the day (use your experience in the room) or answer only one of the questions (to describe the 'right-now' moment).

Morning hours. From 8:00 am to 12:00 pm.

Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied: dd/mm/yy/hh:mm

Specify current outdoor conditions:

Cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate, Rainy day. Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, Wind speed km/h, wind direction.

2.2.1 With the electric lights OFF, how do you feel the interior visual environment in this room?

Too dark	Slightly dark	Adequate	Slightly bright	Too bright
----------	---------------	----------	-----------------	------------

2.2.2 Right now, I would prefer a luminous environment to be:

-3 much darker	-2 darker	-1 slightly darker	0 no change	+1 slightly lighter	+2 lighter	+3 much lighter
----------------	-----------	--------------------	-------------	---------------------	------------	-----------------

Afternoon hours. From 12:00 pm to 15:00 pm.	
Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied: dd/mm/yy/hh:mm	Specify current outdoor conditions: Cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate, Rainy day. Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, Wind speed km/h, wind direction.

2.2.3 With the electric lights OFF, how do you feel the interior visual environment in this room?

Too dark	Slightly dark	Adequate	Slightly bright	Too bright
----------	---------------	----------	-----------------	------------

2.2.4 Right now, I would prefer a luminous environment to be:

-3 much darker	-2 darker	-1 slightly darker	0 no change	+1 slightly lighter	+2 lighter	+3 much lighter
----------------	-----------	--------------------	-------------	---------------------	------------	-----------------

Late afternoon hours. From 15:00 pm to 18:00 pm or later.	
Specify the date/time in which this section of the questionnaire is applied: dd/mm/yy/hh:mm	Specify current outdoor conditions: Cloudy, Sunny, Intermediate, Rainy day. Outdoor temperature °C, humidity %, Wind speed km/h, wind direction.

2.2.5 With the electric lights OFF, how do you feel the interior visual environment in this room?

Too dark	Slightly dark	Adequate	Slightly bright	Too bright
----------	---------------	----------	-----------------	------------

2.2.6 Right now, I would prefer a luminous environment to be:

-3 much darker	-2 darker	-1 slightly darker	0 no change	+1 slightly lighter	+2 lighter	+3 much lighter
----------------	-----------	--------------------	-------------	---------------------	------------	-----------------

2.2.7 With the electric lights ON, how do you feel the interior visual environment?

Too dark	Slightly dark	Adequate	Slightly bright	Too bright
----------	---------------	----------	-----------------	------------

Open-Ended Questions: the following questions intend to get the user's 'own words' opinion about the visual environment indoors in summertime.

2.2.8 Do you consider that the place its sufficiently and naturally lit?

2.2.9 During daytime, do you need to turn the lights ON due to a darkened environment?

2.2.10 Do you need to turn the lights ON in the morning or the afternoon?

2.2.11 Do you prefer natural or artificial lighting?

2.2.12 About artificial lighting, what colour of light do you prefer when you perform activities in the building in summertime (cool or warm)? Please specify if this preference changes during the day:

i) Morning time 8:00 – 12:00	a) warm white	b) natural white	c) cool white
ii) Afternoon time 12:00 – 15:00	a) warm white	b) natural white	c) cool white
iii) Late afternoon time 15:00 – 18:00 (or later).	a) warm white	b) natural white	c) cool white

www.hfmmagazine.com/media/photos/62-health-facility-lighting

Warm white Natural white Cool white

2.3 Acoustic Environment

In this section, we collect feedback from the users, to judge the acoustic environment indoors, as for instance, regarding frequent noise from interior/exterior sources.

2.3.1 Please state how you would prefer the acoustic environment to be now.

1 no change

2 slightly quieter

3 quieter

4 much quieter

Open-Ended Questions: the following questions intend to get the user's 'own words' opinion about the acoustic environment indoors.

2.3.2 In case of discomfort due to noise, can you identify the origin? And if its localized internal/external to the room?

2.3.3 Is there a specific time of the day when the noise occurs?

2.3.4 What actions are taken to reduce or eliminate the problem?

2.3.5 How helpful these actions are?

2.3.6 What do you think it could be a permanent/ideal solution?

2.4 Air quality environment

In this section, the users would manifest their impressions regarding the perception of the air quality environment indoors.

2.4.1 How do you judge this environment on a personal level:

1 clearly acceptable	2 just acceptable	3 just unacceptable	4 clearly unacceptable
----------------------	-------------------	---------------------	------------------------

2.4.2 How would you qualify the quality of the air environment here, please select from the list below:

Pure	fresh	cool	clean	healthy	breezy	sufficient	irritating	dry	heavy
dense	enclosed	damp	moist	thick	stagnant	dusty	dull	unhealthy	stuffy

Open-ended questions: the following questions intend to get the user's 'own words' opinion about the air quality environment indoors.

2.4.3 Can you feel the air movement in the room?

2.4.4. Do you need to open the windows to clean the air very often?

2.4.5 Do you use an additional device, mechanical/electrical (fan, AC)?

2.5 Humidity

In this section, the users would manifest their impressions regarding the humidity in the room.

2.5.1 How do you feel about the humidity in this room?

-3 too dry	-2 dry	-1 slightly dry	0 Neutral	1 slightly humid	2 humid	3 too humid
------------	--------	-----------------	-----------	------------------	---------	-------------

2.5.2 How would you prefer it to be?

-1 would prefer drier	0 no change	1 prefer more humid
-----------------------	-------------	---------------------

2.5.3 Do you observe any permanent or frequent manifestation of humidity in the building? If so, what would be the source? (leaks, infiltration, condensation, mould). _____

2.5.4 In Summary, if you manifest dissatisfaction with the interior environment in this room. How can you best describe the origin of this discomfort? (check all that apply).

a) Humidity too high (damp)	b) humidity too low (dry)	c) Air movement too high
d) Air movement too low	e) incoming sun	f) drafts from windows or vents
g) my area is colder than others	h) my area is hotter than others	i) unavailable heating/cooling
j) heating/cooling systems not sufficient or not working properly	k) Inaccessible controls for temperature or controlled by others	l) I can't open or close the windows
m) other _____		

Part 3. Energy Use please direct these questions to the owner/tenant/responsible person (when applicable)

3.1 What do you think about the energy expenditure in the building?

Normal	High	Too high
--------	------	----------

3.2 What do you think it would contribute to reduce the energy use in this building?

- a) Use space heating/cooling appliances as little as possible.
- b) Use less artificial lighting.
- c) Use energy efficiency appliances.
- d) Reduce standby power consumption.
- e) No energy saving actions.

Part 4. Value and impact of the heritage building

This section intends to establish the connection/impact between the interviewed and the heritage building, please skip this section if you have already answered these questions for the previous 'wintertime' version of the questionnaire.

4.1 For how long have you been living/working/studying in this building? _____

4.2. How do you describe your perception of the building that you use/occupy?

Negative	Indifferent	Positive
----------	-------------	----------

4.3 If positive, how do you perceive your attachment/connection to the building that you use/occupy?

Emotional (family or personal history)	Cultural/Historical/Architectural Appreciation	Practical (I study, work, stay there)	Practical (personal, economic benefit)	Other
--	--	---------------------------------------	--	-------

Open-Ended Questions: the following questions intend to get the user's 'own words' opinion about their connection with the historic building.

4.4. Are you familiar with the history of the building that you use/occupy? _____

4.5 Which one do you feel that is the most important feature of this building in terms of history/architecture? E.g. Courtyard, Façade, other.

4.6 Can you identify, is there a part of the building that means more to you? _____

4.7 At personal level, Working/Living/Studying in an historical building represent any benefit for you?

4.8 How do you find the level of conservation of the building?

-2 Highly deteriorated	-1 Slightly deteriorated	0 Neither good nor bad	1 In good state of conservation	2 Highly conserved, in very good conditions
------------------------	--------------------------	------------------------	---------------------------------	---

4.9 How do you think that the renovation of historical buildings it's important for the local community?

Cultural life/tourism Attractiveness of locality to business, image,	Ecological, embodied energy, as their replacement with new constructions would increase green-house emissions	General well-being of society, community cohesion, educational benefit	Other
--	---	--	-------

4.10 Do you think that 'ENERGY RENOVATION' of heritage buildings, would be beneficial for the community/society? How?

4.11 Do you have any opposition to the ENERGY RENOVATION of the building that you use/occupy? If yes, please explain why.

4.12 What level of intervention do you think the building needs and you would agree with?

- a) Low - maintenance level
- b) preservation (stop deterioration)
- c) renovation for less energy use
- d) high - adaptive for reuse

4.13 Would you agree with the implementation of permanent renovation measures or those should be reversible?

- a) Permanent renovation.
- b) Reversible renovation.

Explain why: _____

Annex II – Accessibility Survey.

Questionnaire included in Annex 1 of the report for Task 3.4 presented by WUT partner.

TABLE 15 ACCESSIBILITY SURVEY FOR DEMONSTRATION BUILDINGS.

SURVEY FOR DEMONSTRATION BUILDINGS ON THEIR ACCESSIBILITY – EXISTING STATUS
<p>THE SURVEY WAS BASED ON:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AN ACCESSIBILITY MODEL DESCRIPTION DEVELOPED BY THE CAPITAL CITY OF WARSAW https://wsparcie.um.warszawa.pl/documents/67381/66522991/Za%C5%82.5_Wzorcowy_opis_dost%C4%99pno%C5%9Bci.pdf/1caee417-55f5-5e4e-4777-80063abf882c?t=1669816772307 • UNE EN 17210:2021 Accessibility and usability of the built environment - Functional requirements <p>The following survey gathers information about the entire building. Additionally, at a later date, there may be a need to prepare a questionnaire focusing on the part of the building where changes are planned as part of the project implementation.</p> <p>The survey is primarily addressed to managers of buildings or its individual parts. It is also addressed to members of the project consortium who use the building.</p> <p>The question of architectural accessibility is a complex issue, so for chosen questions there is an opportunity to comment on the selected answer, if the person answering feels it is necessary, the comment is optional. To the comment you can also attach photos.</p> <p>Definition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A surface’s LRV is the measurement of the percentage light reflected and ranges from 0% (black) to 100% (white) although 100%. Measuring the percentage points difference between the LRV’s of two adjoining surfaces will determine the contrast between the surfaces. The standards recommend an LRV contrast of at least 30 points.
OWNER/USER
<p>1. Which of the following gender categories best describes how you self-identify?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Woman • Man • Non-binary • Prefer to describe: • Prefer not to state. <p>2. Do you identify as a person with disability or other chronic condition?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, if the answer is "Yes," how would you describe your disability or chronic condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Attention deficit / difficulty with learning ○ Autism ○ Blind or visually impaired ○ Deaf or hard of hearing ○ Health-related disability ○ Mental health conditions ○ Mobility-related disability

- Speech-related disability
- Other (please specify, optional):
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

3. Do you have difficulty seeing, even if wearing glasses?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes," please specify the type of seeing difficulty (optional):
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

4. Do you have difficulty hearing, even if using a hearing aid?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes," please specify the type of hearing difficulty (optional):
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

5. Do you have difficulty walking or climbing steps?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes," please specify what mobility aids do you require for getting around?
 - I don't need any special aids, but I have difficulty walking or climbing steps.
 - Wheelchair
 - Crutches
 - Walking cane
 - Walkers
 - Other, please specify (optional):.....
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

6. Do you have difficulty remembering or concentrating?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes" and you feel comfortable, please share additional information about your remembering or concentrating difficulty and your needs (optional):
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

7. Do you have difficulty communicating, for example understanding or being understood in the official language (country of demo-site)?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes" and you feel comfortable, please share additional information about your communicating difficulty and your needs (optional):
- No
- Prefer not to answer.

8. Do you currently require or anticipate needing any accessible products, solutions, or services for support?

- Yes, if the answer is "Yes" please provide what types of accessible products, solutions, and services you require or believe would be beneficial for you? (optional, please provide any additional details not previously mentioned in the survey (in question 5):
.....
- No

- Prefer not to answer
9. Please indicate your status in the building (You can choose more than one):
- Owner
 - User (permanent resident)
 - Temporary renter
 - Guest/visitor
 - Pupil/student
 - Building Maintenance Crew/Building Services Team
 - Property Management/Facility Management/Building Administration
 - Other (please specify)
10. "Which age group do you fall into?"
- Under 18
 - 18-29
 - 30-49
 - 50-69
 - 70 or older

BUILDING SURROUNDINGS

1. Does the main entrance to the building provide access to individuals with special needs (e.g., no level differences, paved surface in front of the entrance with a slope of up to 3%, ramps, elevators, lift)?
- Yes, because there are no level differences between the ground floor and the surroundings of the building
 - Yes, because the level difference issue has been resolved using (please specify the type of solution)
 - No

Comment + photos (optional).

2. If the main entrance to the building does not provide access to users with special needs, is there another adapted and accessible entrance available?
- Yes
 - No

Comment + photos (optional).

Subsequent questions about the entrance to the building refer to the accessible entrance, and if there is none, they refer to the main entrance to the building (which should be adapted to such needs in the future).

3. Does the access route from the main gate of the property to the entrance of the building (building access route) have a width of at least 150 cm free of any narrowing and obstacles such as posts, uneven sidewalk, uneven terrain, high curbs, intersections with car accesses?
- Yes
 - No, if not, describe what limits/impedes a collision-free access width of at least 150cm

Comment + photos (optional);	
4.	Is the access route to the building well lit (i.e., does the spacing of the fixtures allow for even light distribution, are there no underlit areas, and is there no glare)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No, if not describe why.....
Comment + photos (optional);	
5.	Does the access route to the building include a tactile guiding system component? (tactile guiding system/tactile wayfinding/tactile paving is a system of textured ground surface indicators located on sidewalk surfaces to help find the way intended primarily for people with visual impairments). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Comment + photos (optional);	
6.	Has the access route to the building been clearly marked for a person with special needs, using, among other things, directions, information boards in symbolic language, pictorial language, signposts, etc.? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, if yes, describe which • No
Comment + photos (optional);	
7.	In your opinion, is access to the building entrance accessible to people with special needs, including, in particular, people with visual impairments and wheelchair users? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No, if not, describe what restricts/ prevents people with special needs from accessing the building
Comment + photos (optional);	
ENTRANCE TO THE BUILDING	
1.	Is there a difference in levels between the surroundings of the building and the ground floor level, i.e. when entering the building, do you have to overcome the difference in levels? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <p style="color: #c08040;">If answer no, skip questions 9-15</p>
2.	If an outdoor ramp is used, is its minimum width 1.2 m, length less than 9 m, and is a ramp handrail of two heights 0.75 and 0.9 m and a curb with a minimum height of 7 cm used? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no ramps) • Yes • No, specify which of the listed requirements have not been provided
3.	If an outdoor ramp is used, is its slope less than 5% (without a canopy) or less than 8% (with a canopy)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no ramps) • Yes • No, provide values for the existing ramp and write whether it is canopied.....
4.	Is the number of external steps to be climbed less than 10? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no stairs) • Yes

• No

5. Are the first and last steps marked in contrast?

- Not applicable (no stairs)
- Yes
- No

6. Is a double-sided stair handrail used and is the stair handrail extended by 0.3 m before the first and last step?

- Not applicable (no stairs)
- Yes
- No, specify which of the listed requirements have not been provided

7. Do the steps have the following dimensions: step height maximum 0.175 m, step width minimum 0.35 m?

- Not applicable (no stairs)
- Yes
- No

8. Is the handrail of the ramp extended by 0.3 m, with the end of the railing pointing downward?

- Not applicable (no ramps)
- Yes
- No

9. Is the landing (in front of the door to the building) of stairs, ramps have a minimum size of 1.5 x 1.5 m outside the door opening range?

- Not applicable (no stairs)
- Yes
- No

10. Is the door without thresholds in or, in the case of an entrance with a threshold, its height is a maximum of 1 cm, and the wedge of the threshold is bevelled and marked in contrast (LRV30)?

- Not applicable (no threshold or lower than 1 cm)
- Yes
- No
- I don't know, it's hard to tell/measure

Comment + photos (optional);.....

11. Is there an entrance canopy for protection from rain and sun?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

12. Is the information board at the entrance easy to read for a person with a disability, is it placed at a height that is readable from a seated person's level, are instructions in symbolic, pictorial language placed near the entrance?

- Not applicable (no information board)
- Yes
- No
- No, specify which of the listed requirements have not been provided

Comment + photos (optional);.....

13. Has a tactile surface (tactile paving) been used at the entrance to the building?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

14. Is the door's frame clearance width a minimum of 0.9 m and clear height a minimum of 2.0 m, with a minimum 0.9 m wide movable leaf for double doors?

- Yes
- No

15. Is the handle provided for a height between 0.8 and 1.1 m?

- Yes
- No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor.

16. Does the manoeuvring space in the vestibule (hallway) have minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 m outside the door opening range?

- Yes
- No

17. In your opinion, does the door require significant force to be opened?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

18. Does the manual door have a door closer?

- Yes
- No

19. Did you plan for the door closer to be equipped with actuators enabling automatic or semi-automatic opening? (The door closer may offer significant resistance when opening the door, which is particularly burdensome for people with limited mobility. If the force required to open the door exceeds 25 N, it is necessary to equip them with actuators enabling automatic or semi-automatic opening.)

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

20. Do the doors have handles that are easy to grip in the shape of the letter "L" or "C"? (The use of spherical handles, circles, small grips, or handles installed too close to the door leaf requires rotating the hand and/or strong squeezing, making it difficult to open the door easily).

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

21. In the case of glass doors, have contrasting markings been provided?

- Yes
- No

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE BUILDING

Please provide:

Building area:.....

Building volume:.....

Number of floors above ground.....

Number of underground floors.....

Is there a usable attic in the building? (if so, please count it as one of the above-ground floors)

- Yes
- No

Functions of the building and their arrangement in the building (e.g. in relation to floors)

LIGHTING AND INTERIORS

1. Are horizontal and vertical surfaces in the entrance zone of the building well-lit, and does the spacing of lighting fixtures allow for even light distribution? Are there any poorly lit areas, and if directional lighting is used, is the light source positioned high enough to reduce glare?

- Yes
- No, if not describe why.....

Comment + photos (optional);.....

2. Is the lighting inside the building uniform, minimizing glare?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

3. Are light switches in the building positioned at a height of 0.8-1.1 m?

- Yes
- No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor.

4. Has contrasting marking been generally applied throughout the building in public spaces, such as contrasting door surfaces with wall colour LRV≥30 or contrasting door frames with wall colour LRV≥30?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know, it's hard to tell/measure

Comment + photos (optional);.....

5. Are there any suspended/elevated/protruding elements in the building that could cause collisions? (Suspended, protruding elements such as technical equipment housings, display cases should be positioned and secured to not pose a threat to blind or visually impaired individuals.)

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

6. Has the building been finished with surfaces of walls and floors in uniform colours, without patterns or with patterns having a colour contrast of less than LRV = 20?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know, it's hard to tell/measure

Comment + photos (optional);.....

7. Has non-slip flooring been applied in the building?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Are the internal door widths in the building, measured within the door frame, at least 0.9 m wide and a minimum height of 2.0 m, for double doors, is the movable leaf at least 0.9 m wide?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
HORIZONTAL CIRCULATION IN THE BUILDING, RECEPTION, SERVICE
<p>1. Is the reception/information desk located near the entrance, and is the attending person visible from outside the counter?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no reception/information desk) • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f2f2f2; padding: 2px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
<p>2. Has at least one reception/information desk been provided with a reception counter with a minimum width of 0.9 m, a height of 0.8 m, and clear space for wheelchair user knees with minimum dimensions of 0.7 m height x 0.6 m depth?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no reception/information desk) • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f2f2f2; padding: 2px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
<p>3. Has manoeuvring space with minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 m been provided in front of the reception/information desk for a wheelchair user?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no reception/information desk) • Yes • No
<p>4. Is at least one reception/information desk equipped with an induction loop, and is this workstation marked with the symbol?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no reception/information desk) • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f2f2f2; padding: 2px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
<p>5. Is the approach to the reception/information desk marked with varying textures or a floor guidance system?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no reception/information desk) • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f2f2f2; padding: 2px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
<p>6. Are the corridors in the building free of obstacles, thresholds, and other obstructions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f2f2f2; padding: 2px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
<p>7. Do the corridors in the building have a clear and intuitive layout?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Do the corridors have a width of at least 1.2 m without any narrowing?

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

9. Do the corridors have a width of at least 1.5 m without any narrowing?

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

10. Is there manoeuvring space with minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 m at the end of the corridor and in places requiring turning around, for example, in front of doors?

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

MARKINGS, INFORMATION BOARDS, SIGNPOSTS

1. Have information boards and tactile maps illustrating the most important elements of the building and the layout of each floor's spatial functionality been provided?

• Not applicable (no boards and tactile maps)

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

2. Are information boards placed at a height of 1.2 - 1.6 m?

• Not applicable (no boards)

• Yes

• No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor.

Comment + photos (optional);.....

3. Is the tactile map located between 0.9 m (bottom edge) and 1.05 m (top edge) and tilted at a 25% angle?

• Not applicable (no tactile maps)

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

4. Are directional signs and floor markings visible and legible?

• Not applicable (no directional signs and floor markings)

• Yes

• No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

5. Have symbols and infographics been used to indicate basic facility functions and directions to key areas?

• Not applicable (no symbols and infographics)

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

6. Are written, lettered, and graphic markings contrasted in colour with the background (LRV60)?

- Not applicable (no lettered, and graphic markings)
- Yes
- No
- I don't know, it's hard to tell/measure

Comment + photos (optional);.....

7. Has a sufficiently large font size been used (minimum text height of 15 mm, calculated based on the formula: $HT = 0.02-0.03 \times L$, where HT represents the text height, and L represents the distance from the text)?

- Not applicable (no lettered markings)
- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Have sans-serif fonts, such as Arial, Helvetica, or Verdana, been used in the written text, with both uppercase and lowercase letters?

- Not applicable (no lettered markings)
- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

9. Signalling in the building: Is there visual and auditory signalling provided to activate in case of evacuation?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

VERTICAL CIRCULATION

1. Does the building have stair elevators, ramps for vertical circulation of wheelchair users?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

2. Are there elevators in the building?

- Yes
- No

If answer no, skip questions 58-70

3. Is there at least one lift in the building that is accessible, that is, suitable for the transport of people with special requirements, that is, the internal dimensions of the cabin are at least 1.1 m wide x 1.4 m long?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

The next question concerns the accessible elevator; if there isn't one, please refer to the other elevators in the building.

4. Is the elevator's location easy to identify near the main lobby/main entrance?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

5. Is the distance from the elevator doors to the opposite wall at least 1.6 meters?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

6. Does the elevator have visual indication of arrival, informing which elevator has arrived and which direction it is heading?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

7. Does the elevator have sound signalling indication of arrival, informing which elevator has arrived and which direction it is heading?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Does the elevator have sound signalling indication informing about the closing and opening of doors?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

9. Is there an external control panel installed at the height of 0.8 - 1.1 m at the entrance to the elevator?

- Yes
- No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor.

Comment + photos (optional);.....

10. Is there an internal control panel installed at the height of 0.8 - 1.1 m in the elevator, at a distance not less than 0.5 m from the corner of the cabin?

- Yes
- No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor:.....

Comment + photos (optional);.....

11. Is the internal and external control panel equipped with Braille numbers or raised numbers, and is the "zero" floor button additionally distinguished by colour and touch?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

12. Do the elevator doors have a minimum width of 0.9 m, do they open and close automatically, and are they equipped with a system to stop closing in case of an obstruction at the entrance?

- Yes
- No, if no, please, estimate the height above floor:.....

Comment + photos (optional);.....

13. Is the elevator equipped with handrails on both sides of the cabin, and is at least one handrail installed parallel to the same side as the control panel?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

14. Is a mirror placed on the cabin wall opposite the elevator doors? (This applies when the internal dimensions of the cabin are 1.1 m width x 1.4 m length, and turning around for a wheelchair user is not possible.)

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

INTERNAL STAIRCASES

Are there stairs in the building?

If answer no, skip questions 70-77

1. Can the stairs in the building be bypassed using an elevator or lift? Is the minimum usable width of the stair tread 1.2 meters?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

2. What is the maximum number of steps in one flight of stairs?
.....

3. What is the maximum height and depth of the steps (does not apply to stairs leading to basements and unused attics and not intended for permanent occupancy)?
.....

4. Is the handrail diameter between 0.035 - 0.045 meters extended by 0.3 meters, and is the end of the handrail directed downwards?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

5. Is the handrail mounted along the walls at least 0.05 meters away from the wall? Is the internal handrail placed within the stairwell continuous and uninterrupted?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

6. Are the first and last steps contrastingly marked on the vertical and horizontal surfaces?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

7. Are the surfaces of stairs and floors (near the stairs) even and stable, with anti-slip properties?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Does the landing of the stairs have minimum dimensions of 1.5 x 1.5 meters and is it located outside the door swing range?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

SANITARY FACILITIES: TOILETS FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES, ROOMS FOR PARENTS WITH BABIES

8. Is there a wheelchair accessible toilet on each floor?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

9. Is the possibility of transferring to the toilet bowl from both sides (left and right) provided in at least 1 accessible toilet (cabin) on each floor?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

10. If there is no access to a toilet for a person with a disability on a particular floor, is there a means of access by elevator to another floor where there is a accessible toilet?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

11. Is an infant changing area provided at a height of 0.75 - 1.1 meters that does not restrict the transfer area to the toilet bowl?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

12. Is there a separate room with a changing area for parents with babies?

- Yes
- No

<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
13.	<p>Are showers accessible to persons with disabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
14.	<p>Is a baby changing table 0.5 x 0.7 m, 0.8 - 0.85 m high, capable of supporting a weight of up to 80 kg, provided with a safety device to prevent the child from slipping?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
<p>ROOMS (LECTURE HALL, WORK ROOM/OFFICES, other according to the characteristics of the institution)</p>	
1.	<p>Does the conference / auditorium / work / other room provide a simple arrangement and layout of tables and seating to allow mobility by a person in a wheelchair?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
2.	<p>In a conference / auditorium room designed for dozens or hundreds of participants, are at least 1% of the seats, but not less than one, designated for wheelchair users? With 51-100 people min 3 seats, 100-200 people min 4 seats, and for each additional 200 seats started min 1 additional seat. (The dimension of the space allocated for a person in a wheelchair must not be less than 0.9 x 1.4 m.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no conference / auditorium room) • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
3.	<p>Has stage (In a conference / auditorium room) access to the lectern been provided for a person in a wheelchair?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no conference / auditorium room) • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
4.	<p>Is the conference/auditorium room equipped with fixed induction loops or other devices for the hearing impaired?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not applicable (no conference / auditorium room) • Yes • No
<p>Comment + photos (optional);.....</p>	
5.	<p>In the conference/auditorium room is there a manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m near the entrance that is also used to access the door?</p>

- Not applicable (no conference / auditorium room)
- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

6. Is there a manoeuvring area of at least 1.50 m x 1.50 m near the conference table, near the work desk?

- Not applicable (no conference table)
- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

7. Does the seated workstation provide access to documents within the reach of a seated person, i.e. at a height of up to 1.4 m?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

8. Does the seated workstation provide free space under the desk (height x width x depth) min. 0.70 m x 0.90 m x 0.60 m?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

9. Are mobile tables provided as additional workspace?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

10. Is there an integrated power strip above the desk?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

11. Is the desktop at a height of 0.7 - 0.8 meters?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

12. Has additional access to electrical outlets from the desk level also been provided in the work areas, conference rooms?

- Yes
- No

Comment + photos (optional);.....

FIRE SAFETY AND EVACUATION OF THE BUILDING	
15. Is an evacuation plan posted in a clearly visible place on each floor?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
16. Are floor markings at 1.2-1.4-meter height?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
17. Has provision been made for evacuating the building for people with disabilities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, if yes, please, describe what kind of solutions are provided:..... • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
18. Have collision-free evacuation accesses and accessible evacuation routes been provided?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
19. Have evacuation devices and procedures been provided: directional signs, emergency lighting, a notification and warning system, an audible system to indicate the direction of evacuation or the location of doors?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
20. Are emergency elevators provided?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
21. Are level differences clearly marked?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>
22. Are special evacuation systems used for the deaf and visually impaired persons, e.g., visual and audible signals, vibrating devices?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, if yes, please, describe what kind of solutions are provided. • No <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #f4b084; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> Comment + photos (optional);..... </div>

Annex III - KPIs cards.

a) KPIs corresponding to the Low Emission Category

LE-1/CET	Embodied carbon savings			
	KPI responsible partner	CETIM		
	KPI supporting partners			
	Source of KPI:	GA, partner.		
KPI description	<p>In order to determine a value for the carbon footprint, it is necessary to perform a life cycle assessment (LCA) for the Herit4Ages solutions, including its products and materials. The carbon dioxide content is considered as Global Warming Potential (GWP), which is why this category receives a lot of attention from the public and is therefore classified as one of the most important. This KPI determines the embodied carbon savings in Herit4Ages solutions compared to a reference scenario which could be the BAU building practice or the existing solution in the demo sites.</p>			
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the LCA: ISO 14040, ISO 14044.			
Brief description of the data source.	The partners in charge of renovation solutions and green sensors should provide data about composition, energy consumption in processing, type and lifespan of equipment used and transportation distance of the materials used in Herit4Ages solutions.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value			
KPI formula	<p>The global warming impact (GWP) is calculated by applying the Life Cycle Assessment methodology (LCA). ReCiPe2016 Midpoint assuming an hierarchise perspective is applied for the calculations.</p> $\%: GWP_{savings} = \left(\frac{1 - GWP(\text{Herit4Ages solution})}{GWP(\text{baseline scenario})} \right) \times 100$ <p> GWP_{savings} = Percentage of embodied carbon savings GWP (Herit4Ages solution) = GWP for the Herit4Ages solution [kg CO₂ equivalent/ m³ solution] GWP (baseline scenario) = GWP for the baseline scenario [kg CO₂ equivalent/ m³ solution] </p>			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)			
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	>20%
Scale of evaluation	Technology and service providers			
	Building level		Monitoring interval	n/a
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component	x	Measurement Interval	n/a
Temporal scale of evaluation	Occupant/User			
	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.1
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.1

LE-2/CET	Material health savings			
	KPI responsible partner CETIM	Source of KPI: Partner CETIM.		
KPI supporting partners	Based on EU project CIRCuiT (Circular Construction in Regenerative Cities) with major modifications			
KPI description	This KPI evaluates, from a LCA perspective, the overall health risks of materials and products in the Herit4Ages solutions, quantified as impact on healthy life years of humans. The measure unit is the disability-adjusted life year per kilogram of solution (DALY/kg solution). One DALY represents the loss of the equivalent of one year of full health. The Herit4Ages solutions results in this issue are compared to a reference scenario to assess the potential savings.			
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the LCA: ISO 14040, ISO 14044.			
Brief description of the data source.	The partners in charge of renovation solutions and green sensors should provide data about composition, energy consumption in processing, type and lifespan of equipment used and transportation distance of the materials used in Herit4Ages solutions.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value			
KPI formula	The Human Toxicity (HT) is calculated by applying the Life Cycle Assessment methodology (LCA). The characterization method is USEtox Endpoint $\%: HT_{savings} = \left(\frac{1 - HT(Herit4Ages\ solution)}{HT(baseline\ scenario)} \right) \times 100$ HT _{savings} = Percentage of embodied carbon savings GWP (Herit4Ages solution) = HT for the Herit4Ages solution [DALY/ m ³ solution] GWP (baseline scenario) = HT for the baseline scenario [DALY/ m ³ solution]			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	>20%
	Policy making/governance	x		
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	n/a
	Room level	x	Measurement Interval	n/a
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.1
	End of project		Project Deliverable	D8.1
	Post project			

LE-3/CET	Low carbon materials in composition												
	KPI responsible partner CETIM		Source of KPI: GA										
	KPI supporting partners												
KPI description	This KPI quantifies the use of low carbon materials in the composition of solutions. Herit4Ages aims to promote the use of local waste, recycled and lightweight aggregates, PCMs and vegetable fibres. Therefore, this KPI calculates the mass percentage of these materials that are part of the final solutions and should reach a minimum of 40% according to the GA.												
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the KPIs												
Brief description of the data source.	Partners in charge of renovation solutions and green sensors should provide data on the mass composition of their solutions.												
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value												
KPI formula	Materials are categorised according to the GA requirements by assigning them a score as shown in the table below: <table border="1" data-bbox="477 1021 1361 1227" style="margin: 10px auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of material</th> <th>Quality factor</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>GA material</td> <td>1</td> <td>Materials promoted in GA: local waste, recycled and lightweight aggregates, PCMs and vegetable fibres.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No GA material</td> <td>0</td> <td>Other materials no promoted in GA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The weighting in this KPI is taken by the mass of each material used. So, to get a score for a <i>n</i> material Herit4Ages solution, the following formula should be applied:</p> $\% \text{ Low carbon material} = \left(\frac{\sum_i^n \text{Material mass [kg]} \times \text{Quality factor}}{\sum_i^n \text{Material mass [kg]}} \right) \times 100$				Type of material	Quality factor	Description	GA material	1	Materials promoted in GA: local waste, recycled and lightweight aggregates, PCMs and vegetable fibres.	No GA material	0	Other materials no promoted in GA
Type of material	Quality factor	Description											
GA material	1	Materials promoted in GA: local waste, recycled and lightweight aggregates, PCMs and vegetable fibres.											
No GA material	0	Other materials no promoted in GA											
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%									
	Consumers (end-users)												
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	>40%									
	Technology and service providers												
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	n/a									
	Room level												
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a									
	Occupant/User												
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.1									
	End of project												
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.1									

LE-4/CET	Circularity (Material Origin)															
	KPI responsible partner CETIM															
	KPI supporting partners															
	Source of KPI: Partner CETIM. Based on EU project ICEBERG (Circular economy in building materials) with minor modifications.															
KPI description	In order to drive circularity in the building sector, the use of non-renewable primary materials should be minimized and replaced by waste or recycled resources. This KPI assesses the circularity of the materials used in the final solutions by prioritising the use of waste and recycled over by-products or waste streams that may be valorised for other uses or the main products in first manufacturing.															
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the KPIs															
Brief description of the data source.	The data sources, in particular the composition and materials of renovations solutions and green sensors, shall be provided by the WP6 and WP7 partners. A description of the type of material, origin and stages of processing, if any, should be provided.															
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value															
KPI formula	Materials are categorised according to their origin by assigning them a score as shown in the table below: <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #c48e3a; color: white;">Type of material</th> <th style="background-color: #c48e3a; color: white;">Quality factor</th> <th style="background-color: #c48e3a; color: white;">Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Waste and recycled product</td> <td>1</td> <td>This material shall have no further use and shall be disposed of in landfill, incinerated or otherwise appropriately treated.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>By-product</td> <td>0.5</td> <td>This material is a product or waste stream that can be recovered for uses other than construction.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Primary product</td> <td>0</td> <td>This material has never undergone any processing other than manufacturing</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The weighting in this KPI is taken by the mass of each material used. So, to get a score for a n material Herit4Ages solution, the following formula should be applied:</p> $Score = \frac{\sum_i^n Material\ mass[kg] \times Quality\ factor}{\sum_i^n Material\ mass\ [kg]}$				Type of material	Quality factor	Description	Waste and recycled product	1	This material shall have no further use and shall be disposed of in landfill, incinerated or otherwise appropriately treated.	By-product	0.5	This material is a product or waste stream that can be recovered for uses other than construction.	Primary product	0	This material has never undergone any processing other than manufacturing
Type of material	Quality factor	Description														
Waste and recycled product	1	This material shall have no further use and shall be disposed of in landfill, incinerated or otherwise appropriately treated.														
By-product	0.5	This material is a product or waste stream that can be recovered for uses other than construction.														
Primary product	0	This material has never undergone any processing other than manufacturing														
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Score												
	Consumers (end-users)															
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	The higher score, the better												
	Technology and service providers															
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	n/a												
	Room level	x														
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a												
	Occupant/User															
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.1												
	End of project															
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.1												

b) KPIs corresponding to the Inclusive Cultural Heritage Category

ICH-1/IBS	Solution reversibility			
	KPI responsible partner LWI		Source of KPI: GA	
	KPI supporting partners UNINOVA, TYN			
KPI description	The level of reversibility of the Herit4Ages renovation interventions, i.e. the possibility to install the solutions without using invasive connecting methods and remove renovation solutions without any lasting effects on the demo buildings.			
Regulatory framework	National and local heritage conservation regulations (where applicable)			
Brief description of the data source.	Providers of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions (wall, ceiling and floor panels, environmental sensors, PV panels and the Smart Energy Router)			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<p>Wall, ceiling and floor solutions: Data from the Installation Guidelines (technical documentation) – basis of calculation: the guidelines <i>do not</i> include invasive methods (connectors, glue, etc.) for connecting the panel mounting solution to the walls, ceiling and floor.</p> <p>PV panels and Smart Energy Router: The PV panels will be installed in the rooftop in such a way that they could be removed and transferred elsewhere. The Smart Energy Router and the storage batteries are power electronics equipment that can be installed (as any other equipment) without being attached to ground or wall (they will be just placed), so they can also be transferred. Special attention should be paid to the electrical wiring but that should not pose any particular issues.</p> <p>Environmental sensors: The environmental sensor is to be placed on the wall and will be wi-fi connected. Considering its dimensions and weight its reversibility is assured.</p>			
KPI formula	The applied installation methods do not cause changes to the walls, floor, ceiling and roof of the demo buildings.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	% of solutions
	Consumers (end-users)		Threshold –Target Value	100%
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	once, after production of solutions
	Room level		Measurement Interval	once, after production of solutions
	Building system, component	x		
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T6.6, T.7.2, T8.2
	End of project		Project Deliverable	D8.3
	Post project			

ICH-2/IBS	Installation time reduction			
	KPI responsible partner LWI		Source of KPI: GA	
	KPI supporting partners IBS, UBO, FSM			
KPI description	Difference of the actual installation speed of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions from the typical installation speed of similar products in the market			
Regulatory framework	N/A			
Brief description of the data source.	Measurement of actual installation time of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions following standard documentation guidelines. Demo sites confirm the installation time in the installation protocol completed after the installation process.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The installation report of wall, ceiling and floor panels including information of installation time. The report of an alternative method of installing wall, floor and ceiling panels: installation time and preparation of the alternative system, including drying time. More detailed formula described below.			
KPI formula	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement of actual time consumed during the installation of H4A solutions to the demo sites (in hours), following standard installation guidelines (provided by LWI) Comparison of the total installation time per demo site to a reference time (reference to the report of an alternative method of installing wall, floor and ceiling panels) Calculation of the average percentage by which the actual installation speed of the Herit4Ages solutions differed from the reference time 			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	% of time reduction
	Consumers (end-users)		Threshold –Target Value	40%
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	During the installation process
	Room level		Measurement Interval	Once, during the installation process
	Building system, component	x		
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T7.2
	End of project		Project Deliverable	D8.3
	Post project			

ICH-3/IBS	Perceived level of disruption			
	KPI responsible partner IBS			Source of KPI: partner
	KPI supporting partners FSM, CMF, UBO			
KPI description	End users' perception of the level of disruption experienced during the installation of the Herit4Ages solutions at their demo site			
Regulatory framework	N/A			
Brief description of the data source.	<p>User survey, conducted as soon as possible after the installation of the renovation solutions at all demo sites.</p> <p>In the case of air quality, survey data can be compared with data from sensors to analyse possible differences between users' perception and actual air quality indicators.</p>			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<p>Users rate the level of disturbance they perceived during the renovation works on a 5-point Likert scale. Aspects of disruption to be covered in the survey questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Noise Air quality Visual disturbance Access to building/room Impact of the renovation on their daily routines <p>Sample survey questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent did the renovation works affect your normal activities or routines in the building? Rate the effect of the installation works on your ability to access and move around in the building? <p>etc.</p>			
KPI formula	<p>All aspects will be rated on a 5-point scale where 1 indicates no perceived disruption, 2 indicates low disruption, 3 moderate disruption and 4-5 high or very high levels of disruption. The responses will be aggregated to produce a single average value for the sub-indicator: "low", "moderate" or "high".</p>			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Perceived level of disruption
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	
	Policy making/governance			
Scale of evaluation	Technology and service providers	x	Monitoring interval	Once, after installation of solutions
	Building level		Measurement Interval	
	Room level			
	Building system, component		Once, after installation of solutions	
Occupant/User	x	Project Task		T8.2
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Deliverable	D8.3
	End of project			
	Post project			

ICH-4/IBS	User acceptance of Herit4Ages solutions			
	KPI responsible partner IBS		Source of KPI: GA	
	KPI supporting partners FSM, CMF, UBO			
KPI description	End-users' level of acceptance of the Herit4Ages renovation solutions in terms of the perceived utility, aesthetic value, heritage preservation value and responsiveness to users' expectations.			
Regulatory framework	N/A			
Brief description of the data source.	User survey among users of the 4 demo sites, conducted once at the end of the piloting period.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<p>Method: measuring users' agreement with statements on a 5-point Likert scale (e.g. 1 – strongly disagree, 2 – disagree, 3 – neutral, 4 – agree, 5 – strongly agree).</p> <p>Example statements:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The renovation solution improves the indoor climate/energy efficiency of the room/building (the exact wording will depend on the goals of the demo project) 2. I find the renovation solution aesthetically pleasing. 3. I believe this renovation solution helps preserve the building's cultural heritage value. 4. Overall, the renovation solution meets my expectations. 			
KPI formula	Quantitative analysis of the survey responses. Threshold: values 4 and 5 on the 5-point scale are considered as expressions of 'acceptance'. Based on the survey responses, the percentage of users who agree or strongly agree with the statements expressing acceptance of the H4A solution can be calculated.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	% of acceptance
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	80%
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Once (end of project)
	Room level		Measurement Interval	Once (end of project)
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe		Project Task	T8.2
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.3
	Post project			

ICH-5/IBS	Number of participations in the co-creation process			
	KPI responsible partner IBS		Source of KPI: GA	
	KPI supporting partners FSM, CMF, UBO			
KPI description	This KPI measures the reach of the Herit4Ages project in terms of stakeholder engagement by counting instances of stakeholder participation in the demo sites' co-creation processes activities (Heritage Living Labs).			
Regulatory framework	N/A			
Brief description of the data source.	Participant lists and registration sheets of workshops, interviews, focus groups, and other stakeholder events; pseudonymized/anonymized data on the number of respondents to online and offline user and stakeholder surveys conducted as part of the project			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	All demo coordinators collect the data on the number of participants in their local Living Lab co-creation processes. IBS aggregates the data for D8.3.			
KPI formula	Counting and aggregating the number of participants in every co-creation activity in all demos (e.g. workshops, meetings, surveys, interviews, focus groups).			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	number
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	Tartu: 70 Bologna: 100 Ag. de Campoo: 40 Funchal: 25 Total: 235
	Policy making/governance	x		
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Continuous throughout project
	Room level		Measurement Interval	after each co-creation activity; totals to be calculated at the end of project
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.2
	End of project	x		
		Post project		Project Deliverable

ICH-6/IBS	Participant satisfaction with the co-creation process			
	KPI responsible partner IBS		Source of KPI: partner	
	KPI supporting partners FSM, CMF, UBO			
KPI description	Participants' satisfaction with the setup and outcomes of the co-creation processes in the Herit4Ages demos (heritage Living Labs)			
Regulatory framework	N/A			
Brief description of the data source.	User feedback surveys, administered by all demos regularly after local co-creation activities.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<p>Method: standard feedback survey questionnaire measuring users' evaluation of the co-creation process on a 5- or 10-point Likert scale (e.g. 1 – strongly disagree, 2 – disagree, 3 – neutral, 4 – agree, 5 – strongly agree). The key dimensions of participant satisfaction to be included in the feedback surveys are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Satisfaction with the used engagement methods 2.Overall satisfaction with individual co-creation events 3.Satisfaction with communication during the co-creation process 4. Satisfaction with the extent to which participants' input was valued and considered in the co-creation process 			
KPI formula	Threshold: values 4-5 on a 5-point scale and values 7-10 on a 10-point scale are considered as expressions of 'satisfaction'. At the end of the project, the aggregated percentage of survey respondents satisfied/dissatisfied with the co-creation process can be calculated based on their feedback to individual co-creation events.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	% of participants satisfied with the co-creation processes
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	90%
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Continuous throughout project
	Room level		Measurement Interval	After each co-creation event
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.2
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.3
	Post project			

ICH-7/WUT	Universal Design integration			
	KPI responsible partner WUT		Source of KPI: GA	
	KPI supporting partners IBS, FSM, UBO			
KPI description	The KPI Universal Design integration measures the extent to which the installations at demo sites comply with accessibility standards. Compliance primarily concerns the dimensions of the rooms to allow movement of all potential (including those with limitations) users (obstacles on the floor, widths of passageways, heights), colours (the issue of light and sound reflection, contrasts), material (ease of cleanliness and allergenicity), lighting and others.			
Regulatory framework	N/A (accessibility standards – guidelines that do not have the status of legislation)			
Brief description of the data source.	Accessibility evaluation questionnaires, to be filled out by all demo sites where floor, ceiling or wall panels will be installed (Bologna, Tartu, Aguilar de Campoo).			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	The evaluation follows, among other things, the principles contained in the survey “Survey for demonstration buildings on their accessibility” prepared for T2.4. and the requirements for panels developed under T3.4 (“Universal design solutions and measurements”).			
KPI formula	Based on accessibility principles, a questionnaire/checklist will be prepared for the evaluation of the implemented solutions for each demo site, to be filled out by demo site coordinators. The questionnaire will identify the demo sites’ compliance with mandatory and complementary (recommended) accessibility requirements. Mandatory requirements refer to solutions without which the use of the rooms by users with special needs is not possible at all (for example, if the width of the passage prevents the passage of a wheelchair), recommended solutions mean improvements that enhance the quality of the space such as handholds, directional signage, high-quality lighting. The mandatory requirements should be followed 100 percent, recommended requirements as much as possible, but not less than 50 percent of the requirements.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	% of compliance with accessibility requirements
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	Mandatory requirements – 100%; recommended requirements – 50%
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Period before and after installation
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	The evaluation should be repeated twice: 1) before the installation at the stage when it will be known exactly what the panels will be and how they will be installed; 2) after the installation.
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.2
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.3

c) KPIs corresponding to the Energy Efficiency Category

EE-1/TYN	Energy Consumption			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partner (TYN).	
	KPI supporting partners UNIBO, IBS, FSMLR			
KPI description	This KPI determines the energy consumption for electricity and gas in the demonstration sites in FEUB, IBS and FSMLR demo sites.			
Regulatory framework	<i>Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the KPIs.</i>			
Brief description of the data source.	The data will be generated using computer simulations using EnergyPlus software. A virtual model will be created where geometry and the material properties of each of the demonstration sites will be reproduced and used to perform the simulations, to obtain: 7.5.1.2.7 EnergyConsumptionElectricityNautralGas 7.5.1.2.13 EndUseEnergyConsumptionElectricityMonthly 7.5.1.2.16 EndUseEnergyConsumptionFuelOilMonthly [1] InputOutputReference.pdf			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1. Data collection: Data of energy consumption will be obtained from energy simulations using a calibrated virtual model. 2. KPI calculation 3. Comparison with threshold target value.			
KPI formula	Electricity: Interior lights, Interior Equipment, Fans, Pumps, Heating, Cooling, Heat Rejection, Humidifier. Gas: Interior Equipment, Heating (natural gas), Cooling (natural gas), Water Systems Natural Gas.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	kWh/m ² . y. MWh/y
	Consumers (end-users)		Threshold –Target Value	TBD
	Policy making/governance	x		
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	Monthly/Yearly
	Room level		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.4
	Post project			

EE-2/TYN	Energy Savings			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partner (TYN).	
	KPI supporting partners UNIBO, IBS, FSMLR			
KPI description	This KPI determines the reduction of the final energy consumption to reach the same services (e.g. comfort levels) after the interventions, taking into consideration the final energy consumption from the reference period. It may be calculated separately determined for thermal (heating or cooling) energy and electricity, or as an addition of to consider the total savings. It might also be calculated as a percentage.			
Regulatory framework	<i>Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the KPIs.</i>			
Brief description of the data source.	Data from energy bills (electricity, gas) from previous years will be employed first for the calculation of the KPI. After the installation of the monitoring system in the demo-sites, data collected from energy meters in regular intervals to establish the baseline (or simulations using a calibrated model). Once that the renovation solutions are installed, a second set of data will be collected for about a year to compare the performance of the solutions in the reference and the demonstration situations.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data collection: Data for consumption (as well as reference values) can be provided by energy utilities from energy meters 2. KPI calculation 3. Comparison with threshold target value 			
KPI formula	$EST = ERT - TEC$ <p style="text-align: center;"><i>or in %: $EST = 1 - TEC/ERT$</i></p> <p><i>EST = Thermal energy savings</i> <i>ERT = Thermal energy reference demand or consumption (simulated or monitored) of demonstration-site [kWh/(m² year) ; MWh/(year)].</i> <i>TEC = Thermal energy consumption of the renovated demonstration-site [kWh/(m² year); MWh/(year)].</i></p> $ESE = ERE - EEC$ <p style="text-align: center;"><i>or in %: $ESE = 1 - EEC/ERE$</i></p> <p><i>ESE = Electric energy savings</i> <i>ERE = Electric energy reference demand or consumption (simulated or monitored) of demonstration-site [kWh/(m² year) ; MWh/(year)].</i> <i>EEC = Electric energy consumption of the renovated demonstration-site [kWh/(m² year); MWh/(year)].</i></p> $EStotal = ERE + ERT - TEC - EEC$ <p style="text-align: center;"><i>or in %: $EStotal = 1 - TEC + EEC/(ERT + ERE)$</i></p>			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	kWh/m ² . y. MWh/y; %
	Consumers (end-users)		Threshold –Target Value	TBD
	Policy making/governance	x		
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	Monthly/Yearly
	Room level		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.4
	Post project			

EE-3/TYN	Energy Use Intensity (EUI)			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partner (TYN).	
	KPI supporting partners IBS, UNIBO, FSMLR			
KPI description	Energy performance in buildings is commonly measured in kWh/m ² /yr, i.e. kilowatt hours of energy per square metre of building per year, referred as Energy Use Intensity (EUI).			
Regulatory framework	Indoor Environment Assessment: ISO 7730-1995, ASHRAE 55-2004			
Brief description of the data source.	kWh energy consumption can be directly taken from gas and electricity utility bills or by measurements of energy meters at the location (monthly over a year). Annual consumption of on-site renewable energy should be also considered if the energy is not sold back to the grid. This is the total generated renewable energy minus the energy exported back to the grid. If no smart export meter is present, it can be assumed that 50% of the generated energy is used on site and 50% is sold back to the grid. The sum of both will provide the annual operational energy consumption of the property. The buildings gross internal floor area (GIA) needs to be obtained in square meters, taken from building plans or measured on-site.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	Energy data from the building is required, ideally 12 months of data (summer and winter must be represented). The data must include energy delivered by the grid at whatever tariff. The building internal floor area is also required. Reference Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA).			
KPI formula	$EUI = \text{Annual Energy Consumption (kWh)} / \text{Gross internal floor area (m}^2\text{)}$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	kWh/m ² .y
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	120 kWh/m ² /y new buildings < 60 kWh/m ² /y 2025 target < 35 kWh/m ² /y 2030 targets
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

EE-4/TYN	Indoor Thermal Comfort – Adaptive Comfort			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI:	
	KPI supporting partners FSMLR, FEUB, IBS		Partner (TYN).	
KPI description	Determines the acceptability of indoor thermal conditions, is intended to be used in naturally ventilated buildings, it also accounts for people’s clothing adaptation in natural conditioned spaces by relating the acceptable range of indoor temperatures to the outdoor climate.			
Regulatory framework	Calculated based on standards: ASHRAE 55-2010, CEN 15251, EN15251-2007.			
Brief description of the data source.	When measured data is not available, the data employed for the calculation of the KPI will be obtained from BEM simulation outputs using EnergyPlus (7.5.1.1.16 Adaptive Comfort Summary). [1] InputOutputReference.pdf			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<p>ASHRAE STANDARD 55-2010. The model defines two comfort regions 80% and 90% acceptability, if T_o is less than 10 (°C) or greater than 33.5 (°C) the model is not applicable. EnergyPlus Engineering Reference 19.1.6 Adaptive Comfort Model based on EN15251-2007.</p> <p>CEN EN 15251-2007. Different comfort limits apply regarding indoor operative temperature and acceptability limits. The model is intended for naturally ventilated buildings, determines the acceptability of indoor conditions given the 7-day weighted mean outdoor temperature and the indoor operative temperature. The model defines three comfort regions:</p> <p>I – High level of expectation, recommended for spaces occupied by very sensitive persons with special requirements (sick, handicapped, elderly and very young children).</p> <p>II – Normal level of expectation and should be used for new buildings and renovations.</p> <p>III – Acceptable, moderate level of expectation may be used for existing buildings.</p> <p>IV – Only acceptable for a limited part of the year.</p>			
KPI formula	<p>ASHRAE Standard 55-2010, the base of this model is the operative temperature which is obtained by:</p> $T_{ot} = 0.31 \cdot T_o + 17.8$ <p>T_{ot} – operative temperature (°C), calculated as the average of the indoor air dry-bulb temperature and the mean radiant temperature of zone inside surfaces.</p> <p>T_o – monthly mean outdoor air dry-bulb temperature (°C), calculated as the weighted mean of the previous 7-day daily mean outdoor air dry-bulb temperature (T_{od}).</p> <p>CEN EN 15251-2007:</p> <p>Category I, 90% Acceptability Limits: $T_{ot} = 0.33 \cdot T_o + 18.8 \pm 2.0$</p> <p>Category II, 80% Acceptability Limits: $T_{ot} = 0.33 \cdot T_o + 18.8 \pm 3.0$</p> <p>Category III, 65% Acceptability Limits: $T_{ot} = 0.33 \cdot T_o + 18.8 \pm 4.0$</p>			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	Category I, II
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level	x	Measurement Interval	n/a
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.4
	Post project			

EE-5/TYN	Discomfort Index			
	KPI responsible partner TYN	Source of KPI:		
	KPI supporting partners IBS, UNIBO, FSMLR	Partner (TYN).		
KPI description	A discomfort index measures how much discomfort a person feels with a given air temperature and relative humidity. The higher the relative humidity and the air temperature, the greater the discomfort index. Conversely, the lower the temperature and humidity the lower the discomfort.			
Regulatory framework	n/a			
Brief description of the data source.	Data of hourly air temperature and Relative humidity (RH) is required to calculate this index. The data can be obtained by on-site measurements using sensors, or as output of simulations using a calibrated model.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	The Discomfort Index is primarily affected by air temperature and relative humidity. However, factors such as wind speed, solar radiation, and personal factors like clothing and activity level can also influence how comfortable or uncomfortable a person feels in each environment.			
KPI formula	$DI = T - .55 * (1 - .01 * RH) * (T - 14.5)$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where Di is the discomfort index • T is the air temperature (°C) • RH is the relative humidity 			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Unitless
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	The higher the value, the higher the discomfort. Comfort: 15 to 19.9 DI Number of hours of discomfort reduction 40%
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	Critical times of the year, summer, winter
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

EE-6/TYN	Report on Subjective Assessment of Thermal Comfort			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partner (TYN).	
	KPI supporting partners IBS, UNIBO, FSMLR, FUNCHAL			
KPI description	The output from subjective evaluation performed before and after the renovation implementation will be reported to assess the users' impressions regarding the thermal performance improvements.			
Regulatory framework	n/a			
Brief description of the data source.	Output from Surveys performed in winter and summertime before and after the implementation of the renovation measures in the Herit4ages demo sites.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	The output from the surveys before and after the implementation of the solutions will be compared using data analysis to assess the improvements according to a subjective analysis, considering the opinion of the occupants.			
KPI formula	<p>The rating scales employed in the surveys (D2.4, Annex 1, 2.1.4, 2.1.5, 2.1.6) will be assigned a maximum value which will be multiplied by the number of answers. The maximum possible value (if all the respondents had chosen the highest level of satisfaction) will be then determined.</p> <p>The 'Actual Total Vote' is then calculated by multiplying the value assigned to every answer choice by the total number of times that each answer choice was selected.</p> <p>The 'Satisfaction Rate' is then calculated by dividing the 'Actual Total Value' with the 'Maximum Possible Value' and then multiplying by 100 to get the percentage of satisfaction. This process will be implemented to compare the before and after results of the surveys.</p>			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Unitless
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	% of satisfaction
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Critical times of the year, summer, winter
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Occupant/User	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.4
	Post project			

EE-7/TYN	Air Quality Index (AQI)			
	KPI responsible partner TYN	Source of KPI:		
KPI supporting partners IBS, UNIBO, FSMLR	Partner (TYN).			
KPI description	In the air quality index, equal importance is given to all the pollutants. Using observed and standards value, the quality rating for each pollutant is calculated.			
Regulatory framework	EU Directive 2008/50/EC, WHO 2010 Guidelines for indoor air quality: selected pollutants; Commission of the European Communities 'Indoor Air Quality & its Impact on Man', Report No. 11: Guidelines for Ventilation Requirements in Buildings, EUR 14449 EN 1992.			
Brief description of the data source.	An indoor ambience monitoring sensor (AM300L) will be employed to measure the air concentration of the following particles: CO2 concentration, HCHO/O3 level, TVOC, PM 2.5, PM 10.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	The air quality index can be derived by comparing the existing concentrations of pollutants with ambient air quality standards (with the standard being assumed as reference base line for each pollutant) and accordingly the quality rating for a particular pollutant is derived with the formula shown below.			
KPI formula	$Q1 = 10 \left(\frac{Ci}{Si} \right)$ <p>Where: Qi = quality rating for an ith pollutant, Ci = concentration of ith pollutant Si = air quality standard for ith pollutant</p> $\text{Air Quality Index (AIQ)} = (Q1 \times Q2 \times Q3 \dots \times Qn)^{1/n}$ <p>where n = number of pollutants considered.</p> <p>Threshold Target Values: Averaging period of 1 year:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fine particles (PM 2.5) à Concentration 25 µg/m³ Target value to be met as of 1.1.2010 • Particle matter (PM 10) à Concentration 40 µg/m³ Limit value to be met as of 1.1.2005 • Carbon dioxide (CO2) à Concentration of 1000 ppm (1,800 mg/m³) above those values can cause feelings of unwellness such as fatigue, headaches and loss of concentration. • Formaldehyde gas (HCHO/O³) à WHO recommends a maximum value for indoor air of 0.1 mg/m³ for 30-minute average exposure. Eye irritation is demonstrated after only four hours of exposure to a concentration of 0.36 mg/m³. • Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) à 300 µg/m³ for the TVOC value in indoor areas. 			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Unitless
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	Indicated above.
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Once with baseline and once with testing cases.
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	Per year
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

EE-8/TYN	Risk of Condensation			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partners	
	KPI supporting partners UBO, FSM, IBS			
KPI description	Determine the risk of condensation, by employing methods to assess the risk of condensation in the demo sites. Two methods are being considered, to select depending on data availability, first, the simplified calculations using the Glaser Method to assess the risk of surface and interstitial condensation, and the Heat and Moisture Transfer Calculation (HAMT) to calculate the heat and moisture transport in building components, based on EnergyPlus simulations.			
Regulatory framework	BS EN 13788, DIN 4108, ISO 10456.			
Brief description of the data source.	-For EnergyPlus the calculation is performed using a 'heat and moisture transfer finite (HAMT) algorithm, that simulates the movement of storage of heat and moisture in surfaces from/to internal and external environments. It also simulates the effects of moisture buffering, provides temperature and moisture profiles through composite building walls, it helps to identify surfaces with high surface humidity [9] [10]. 1.9.12 – 1.9.17 MaterialProperty:HeatAndMoistureTransfer(Settings – Thermal conductivity) [11] one dimensional finite solution. -The Glaser Method assess the risk of surface and interstitial condensation using specific data of materials and climate, the method accounts for vapour transport, hence it would be employed as an assessment method, not as a solutions design method [12].			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	Data about outdoors and indoor environmental conditions, the structure of the envelope (number of layers, thickness, weight), material properties (e.g. moisture, water content, air permeability, porosity, heat from the surfaces), and combination of materials, is used by EnergyPlus to calculate room air temperature and room's moisture content. -The Glaser Method requires input data such as, thermal conductivity, thermal resistance, water vapour resistance factor, water vapour diffusion-equivalent air, layer thickness, heat transfer, water vapour transfer. It also requires, information about the external boundary conditions relative to the location of the building (outdoor temperature, air humidity conditions, and internal boundary conditions (internal air temperature, internal humidity).			
KPI formula	-EnergyPlus: HAMTHeatBalanceEquation to describe the storage of moisture, transport of liquid moisture and of vapor. (EnergyPlus, Engineering Reference, Section 3.3). -The Glaser Method: Output, risk of surface mould growth, corrosion or moisture damage, risk of interstitial condensation, condensation rate (ISO 13788-2012, Section 6).			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	Rate of condensation (kg/m ²). Surface avg. water content ratio (kg/kg), surface face temperature (C).
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	TBD
Scale of evaluation	Technology and service providers		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Building level			
	Room level	x	Measurement Interval	TBD 6, 20, 60 steps per hour
	Building system, component	x		
Temporal scale of evaluation	Occupant/User		Project Task	T8.3
	In project timeframe	x		
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

EE-9/UNI	Savings in electrical energy consumption			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: GA, partner (UNI).	
	KPI supporting partners UNI			
KPI description	This KPI determines the reduction of the final electrical energy consumption to reach the same services after the Smart Energy Router system installation, taking into consideration the final energy consumption from the reference period (2022-2023).			
Regulatory framework	NA			
Brief description of the data source.	Data from energy bills (electricity) from previous years will be employed first for the calculation of the baseline. After the installation of the Smart Energy Router system, data will be collected from Smart Energy Router and energy meters.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below.			
KPI formula	ES – Electrical energy savings (%) EC – Electric energy consumption of the demonstration-site (kWh/year) ER – Electric energy reference consumption of demonstration-site (kWh/year) $ES = \left(1 - \frac{EE}{ER}\right) \times 100$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	TBD
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level			
	Building system, component	x	Measurement Interval	15 min
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe		Project Task	T5.2 and T5.4
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D5.3

EE-10/UNI	Self-sufficiency ratio			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: GA, partner (UNI).	
	KPI supporting partners UNI			
KPI description	This KPI refers to the degree to which the on-site generation is sufficient to cover the final energy consumption of the building/system. It measures the amount of the building/system's energy consumption that is instantaneously matched by the building/system's on-site generation.			
Regulatory framework	NA			
Brief description of the data source.	After the installation of the Smart Energy Router system, data will be collected from Smart Energy Router and energy meters.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below.			
KPI formula	SSR – Self-sufficiency ratio (%) EPV – PV energy that is used directly within the demo site plus energy delivered back to the storage system (batteries) (kWh) EF – Final energy consumption (kWh) $SSR = \frac{EPV}{EF + EPV} \times 100$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	X	Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	X		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	TBD
Scale of evaluation	Technology and service providers	X		
	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level			
	Building system, component	x	Measurement Interval	Monthly
Temporal scale of evaluation	Occupant/User			
	In project timeframe		Project Task	T5.2 and T5.4
	End of project	X		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D5.3

EE-11/UNI	Accuracy of NILM classification			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: GA, partner (UNI).	
	KPI supporting partners UNI			
KPI description	This KPI is used to evaluate the efficiency of the NILM method. It is based on the F-measure providing a comprehensive measure of a NILM's performance by balancing precision and recall, making it an ideal metric for evaluating how well the system identifies and disaggregates electrical loads. Ensures that both false positives and false negatives are considered, providing a more balanced evaluation and is particularly useful in scenarios where the number of events is much smaller than the non-events, which is common in NILM.			
Regulatory framework	NA			
Brief description of the data source.	After the installation of the dedicated sensor that measures the overall consumption of the house, data will be collected from it.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below.			
KPI formula	TP – True positives FP – False positives TN – True negatives FN – False negatives TRP – Precision RC – Recall (sensitivity)			
	$F - measure = 2 \times \frac{TRP \times RC}{TRP + RC}$ $TRP = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$ $RC = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	-
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	80%
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	TBD
	Room level			
	Building system, component	x	Measurement Interval	TBD
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe		Project Task	T5.2 and T5.4
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D5.3

EE-12/TYN	Percentage of improvement			
	KPI responsible partner TYN		Source of KPI: Partner (TYN).	
	KPI supporting partners IBS, UNIBO, FSMLR			
KPI description	Percentage of Improvement is used to calculate improvements in time reductions or cost savings, between to values, before and after the implementation of renovation measures.			
Regulatory framework	n/a			
Brief description of the data source.	Using results obtained in EE-2, Energy Consumption.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	Energy use of the baseline multiplied by the cost of the energy (electricity or gas) and compared to the testing case (with the use of the renovation solution). Alternative to the lack of energy meters to measure the electricity consumption of the renovated room, consider consumption and the building the room area, obtained from computer simulations.			
KPI formula	$PI = (NV-OV)/OV*100$ NV = Energy use after renovation measurements * cost of energy OV= Energy use baseline case * cost of energy			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	n/a
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level	x	Measurement Interval	n/a
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe		Project Task	T8.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D8.4
	Post project			

EE-13/CET	LCC savings		
	KPI responsible partner CETIM		
	KPI supporting partners		
	Source of KPI: Partner: CETIM. HOUSEFUL EU project (innovative circular solutions and services for new business opportunities in the EU housing sector).		
KPI description	LCC is widely used as an economic KPI to assess the financial performance of a product throughout its entire life cycle. It evaluates the total costs associated with a product, including raw material acquisition, processing, maintenance, and disposal. This approach enables organizations to make cost-effective and sustainable decisions. To determine the Life Cycle Cost (LCC) savings, it is necessary to calculate the LCC of the Herit4Ages solutions and compare it with a reference scenario consisting of commercial products not made with waste or by-products sourced near the demo sites.		
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the LCC and cost for buildings and constructed assets: ISO 15686, ISO 21500:2021		
Brief description of the data source.	The partners in charge of renovation solutions should provide data on cost related to raw materials, energy consumption in manufacturing as well as maintenance and disposal or end of life of Herit4Ages solutions.		
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7, WP8 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formulas indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value		
KPI formula	Total Life Cost, obtained from LCC analysis, including all externalities, both positive and negative: $LCC = CAPEX + OPEX + Disposal\ cost - Residual\ value - External\ benefits + External\ cost$ $\%: LCC\ savings = \left(\frac{1 - LCC(Herit4Ages\ solution)}{LCC(baseline\ scenario)} \right) \times 100$ LCC _{savings} = Percentage of cost savings along the entire life of HERTI4AGES solutions LCC (Herit4Ages solution) = LCC for the Herit4Ages solution [€] LCC (baseline scenario) = LCC for the baseline scenario [€]		
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement
	Consumers (end-users)		%
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value
	Technology and service providers	x	>5 %
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval
	Room level	x	n/a
	Building system, component	x	Measurement Interval
	Occupant/User		n/a
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task
	End of project		T8.3
	Post project	x	Project Deliverable
			D8.4

EE-14/CET	CAPEX initial investment indicator			
		KPI responsible partner CETIM		
		KPI supporting partners		
		Source of KPI: Partner: CETIM. Fissac EU project (Fostering industrial symbiosis for sustainable resource intensive industry across construction value chain) with modifications.		
KPI description	CAPEX (Capital Expenditure) is a critical economic KPI in construction projects because it reflects the initial investment required to acquire and build long-term physical assets. CAPEX represents a significant portion of the total budget of a project and helps to evaluate whether the required investment is justified to the expected economic or social/environmental service benefits. It will be compared with a reference scenario of equivalent products on the market.			
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the LCC and cost for buildings and constructed assets: ISO 15686, ISO 21500:2021			
Brief description of the data source.	The partners in charge of renovation solutions and green sensors should provide data on cost related to raw materials, their transport, and energy consumption in manufacturing of Herit4Ages solutions.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value			
KPI formula	The initial investment costs quantified in the CAPEX include the costs of raw materials, water and energy consumed as well as the prorated cost of equipment used. $\text{CAPEX } (\text{€}/\text{m}^2) = \text{Raw material and transportation cost } (\text{€}/\text{m}^2) + \text{Water consumption cost } (\text{€}/\text{m}^2) + \text{Energy consumption cost } (\text{€}/\text{m}^2)$ The baseline scenarios have been established according to the type of HERIT4AGES solution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Floor reference solution cost: 14 €/m² ○ Wall reference solution cost: 70 €/m² ○ Ceiling reference solution cost: 15 €/m² 			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	data
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	Lower than the reference scenario
	Policy making/governance	x		
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	n/a
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

EE-15/CET	OPEX indicator			
		KPI responsible partner CETIM		
		KPI supporting partners		
		Source of KPI: Partner: CETIM. Fissac EU project (Fostering industrial symbiosis for sustainable resource intensive industry across construction value chain) with modifications		
KPI description	OPEX (Operational Expenditure) is an economic KPI in a building renovation project because it represents the ongoing operational costs incurred after the project is completed. Justifying its use as a KPI is based on its impact on the long-term financial and operational viability of the building. Monitoring OPEX ensures that the renovation aligns with the building's long-term operational goals, such as energy efficiency, maintenance, and resource utilization.			
Regulatory framework	Standards and norms relevant to the calculation of the LCC and cost for buildings and constructed assets: ISO 15686, ISO 21500:2021			
Brief description of the data source.	Partners in charge of renovation solutions and green sensors should provide data related to installation, maintenance and labour as well as environmental cost savings if any of HERIT4AGE solutions.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	1-Data collection from WP6, WP7, WP8. 2-KPI calculation will be performed using the formula indicated below. 3-Comparison with threshold target value			
KPI formula	The calculation of operating expenditures is based on the following formula and is assessed annually: $OPEX (\text{€}/y) = \text{Prorated installation cost } (\text{€}/y) + \text{Labour cost } (\text{€}/y) + \text{Maintenance cost } (\text{€}/y) + \text{Environmental savings}$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	data
	Consumers (end-users)			
	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	Lower as possible
	Technology and service providers			
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	n/a
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T8.3
	End of project			
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.4

RE-1/FSM	State of Conservation			
	KPI responsible partner FSM		Source of KPI: Partner (FSM)	
	KPI supporting partners IDP			
KPI description	The State of Conservation KPI evaluates the overall preservation status of heritage sites using data from installed sensors. The goal is to monitor the conservation conditions, ensuring they remain within optimal thresholds. This KPI will be categorized into three states: good condition, inadequate condition, and at-risk condition. The final output will be an annual average indicating the percentage of time the site was in each state. In addition to sensor measurements, there is an interpretation and know-how effort by FSM specialists, leveraging their expertise in preventive conservation of heritage.			
Regulatory framework	National heritage conservation standards and local regulations.			
Brief description of the data source.	Data will be collected from environmental sensors installed at the pilot sites. These sensors measure variables such as temperature, humidity and luminosity and will be placed strategically within each room to provide comprehensive data coverage. Data is transmitted to a central server and analysed by the MHS-Algorithm.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental data will be collected from sensors. 2. The data will be analysed by the MHS-Algorithm to indicate whether the conservation condition is in 'good' condition, 'inadequate' condition, or 'at-risk' condition. 3. Real-time (30-minute interval) data will be available through the Herit4ages DTE platform. The data will also be stored by FSM to generate historical reports for different periods if needed. 			
KPI formula	The MHS Algorithm, using previously loaded information about the use case, evaluates the data and classifies the conservation state as either 'good' condition, 'inadequate' condition, or 'at-risk' condition based on the software analysis.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x	Threshold –Target Value	> 50% of the annual data should be categorized as in 'good' condition (TCB)
	Policy making/governance			
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level	x	Measurement Interval	30 min
	Building system, component			
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T7.3
	End of project	x	Project Deliverable	D7.2
	Post project			

RE-2/FSM	Risk State Evaluation			
	KPI responsible partner FSM		Source of KPI: Partner (FSM)	
	KPI supporting partners IDP			
KPI description	The Risk State Evaluation KPI measures the percentage of time the heritage site is in a state of risk based on sensor data and MHS-Algorithm analysis.			
Regulatory framework	National heritage conservation standards and local regulations.			
Brief description of the data source.	Data will be collected from environmental sensors installed at the pilot sites. These sensors measure variables such as temperature, humidity and luminosity and will be placed strategically within each room to provide comprehensive data coverage. Data is transmitted to a central server and analysed by the MHS-Algorithm to determine risk states. The final evaluation after a one-year period will show what percentage of the time the pilot conditions indicated being 'at risk'.			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data will be collected from environmental sensors. 2. The data will be analysed by the MHS-Algorithm, enabling the consultation at the end of a one-year period to determine what percentage of the time the conservation conditions of the pilot were in an 'at-risk' condition. 3. Real-time (30-minute interval) data will be available through the Herit4ages DTE platform, and efforts will be made to try to develop an alarm system that triggers alerts if the 'at-risk' condition is recorded for a period exceeding established limits, allowing heritage managers to receive a notification and provide immediate attention to critical situations. Additionally, the data will be stored to generate historical reports for different periods. 			
KPI formula	<p>The MHS-Algorithm analyses sensor data to identify periods when the heritage site is in a risk state. This is done by comparing the data against predefined risk thresholds. The algorithm calculates the percentage of time the site is in a risk state.</p> $\text{Risk State Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Time in Risk State}}{\text{Total Monitoring Time}} \times 100\% \right)$			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities		Unit of Measurement	%
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
	Policy making/governance		Threshold –Target Value	< 15% of the annual data should be categorized as 'at risk' (TBC)
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level		Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level	x		
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	30 min
	Occupant/User			
Temporal scale of evaluation	In project timeframe	x	Project Task	T7.3
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D7.2

RE-3/FSM	Compatibility with cultural values			
	KPI responsible partner FSM	Source of KPI:		
	KPI supporting partners IDP, TES, UNI	EU project		
KPI description	This KPI assesses the degree of compatibility of retrofitting interventions with the building's cultural values. It evaluates the effectiveness and suitability of conservation solutions implemented at heritage sites and their impact on the preservation of original elements. The purpose is to ensure that interventions do not harm the cultural heritage, balancing conservation needs with improvements in environmental conditions and energy efficiency. This will be measured through a coefficient that considers technical parameters that can be quantitatively measured, such as the time the site was at risk and improvements in energy efficiency after solutions are implemented, along with a comprehensive evaluation by experts to ensure that the cultural significance of the site is respected.			
Regulatory framework	National heritage conservation standards and local regulations.			
Brief description of the data source.	Data for this KPI will be collected from multiple sources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-site sensor measurements of temperature, humidity, and luminosity Material studies conducted by TESELA Energy savings analysis from EE-1 Assessments using FSM's monitoring algorithm Input from site managers and conservation experts 			
Relevant methods, and use of data resources to calculate the KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Consideration of the specific case and material characteristics of each pilot site. Environmental data will be collected from sensors. The data will be stored to generate annual reports. Analyse energy savings from EE-1 Consult the annual 'State of Conservation' from RE-1 Calculation of the Resilient Conservation Coefficient. Final evaluation to determine the effectiveness and suitability of implemented conservation solutions. Interpretation of data and application of know-how by FSM specialists, leveraging their expertise in preventive conservation of heritage. 			
KPI formula	The study to quantify the Resilient Coefficient will be developed throughout the project. This comprehensive coefficient will provide a holistic view of how well conservation solutions are preserving heritage sites, ensuring both material integrity and environmental sustainability, while respecting and maintaining the cultural values of the site.			
Relevant stakeholders	Energy Utilities	x	Unit of Measurement	TBD
	Consumers (end-users)	x		
Scale of evaluation	Policy making/governance	x	Threshold –Target Value	TBD
	Technology and service providers	x		
Scale of evaluation	Building level	x	Monitoring interval	Yearly
	Room level			
	Building system, component		Measurement Interval	n/a
Temporal scale of evaluation	Occupant/User			
	In project timeframe		Project Task	T8.4
	End of project	x		
	Post project		Project Deliverable	D8.5

